

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DELL'AQUILA

**Department of Information Engineering, Computer
Science and Mathematics**

Doctoral Program in Information and Communication Technology
Curriculum in Emerging Computational Models, Software architectures, and
Intelligent Systems

XXXVII CYCLE

**Ex-ante
Cognitive Design Methods
for
Explainable Intelligent Systems**

IINF-05/A

Coordinator
Prof. Davide Di Ruscio

Tutor
Prof. Giovanni De Gasperis

Candidate
Sante Dino Facchini
282656

Academic Year 2023-2024

“It is customary to offer a grain of comfort, in the form of a statement that some peculiarly human characteristic could never be imitated by a machine. I cannot offer any such comfort, for I believe that no such bounds can be set.”

Alan Turing, 'Can digital computers think?'. Talk broadcast on BBC Third Programme, 15 May 1951

Abstract

This PhD thesis presents the research activities conducted over the past three years at the University of L'Aquila, outlining both the theoretical contributions and practical applications achieved. The research focused on Intelligent Systems, specifically the development of an innovative architecture to embed Explainability by design within systems leveraging Cognitive Artificial Intelligence paradigms.

The proposed framework introduces a "design-for-explainability" methodology, ensuring that key properties such as Accountability, Trust, and Transparency are inherent from the outset rather than retrofitted. Central to this approach is the use of Production Rules, Behavioural Trees and Propositional Logic, which facilitate structured reasoning and interpretable decision-making processes. These paradigms enable the design of agents capable of reasoning within a predefined logical framework while making their decisions and actions traceable. During the implementation phase, Distributed Ledgers were integrated to ensure tamper-proof, timestamped tracking of all actions, enhancing both Immutability and Reliability.

Beyond foundational methods, the research incorporates also advanced second level technologies to address complex systems. Agent-Based Modelling was utilized through Multi-Agent System tools to simulate and analyse intricate scenarios, while Distributed Autonomous Organizations built on Blockchain provided decentralized mechanisms for system governance and identity management. These innovations empower the architecture to tackle high-complexity challenges while maintaining its commitment to Explainability and Accountability.

This work offers a viable alternative to traditional Generative Artificial Intelligence paradigms, which often rely on post-execution justifications to explain decisions. Instead, the proposed architecture embeds Interpretability, Trust and Immutability into the decision-making process, turning Cognitive AI into a particularly suitable solution for applications in real-time systems and human-machine interactions, where generative models may fail.

The versatility of this architecture is demonstrated through its application in diverse fields. Implementations include the modelling of public sector processes such as tax credit lifecycle management, the tokenization of building documents for seismic restoration, and advancements in the robotics sector, including swarm robotics and human-swarm teaming applications. Additionally, the framework was successfully applied to the financial sector, streamlining and securing Over-the-Counter transactions.

By combining theoretical rigour with practical relevance, this thesis establishes a robust foundation for future advancements in Explainable Artificial Intelligence. The results highlight the framework's potential to transform critical domains, emphasizing its adaptability and the value of integrating Explainability by design.

Keywords: Intelligent Systems, Distributed Ledger Technology, Multi-agent Systems, Cognitive Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Explainability.

Contents

List of Figures	v
List of Tables	vii
Acronyms	ix
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Brief Travel Notes on AI Journey	1
1.2 What are Artificial Intelligences?	3
1.3 The Eternal Struggle Between Good and Evil: Cognitive and Generative AI	5
1.4 Intelligent Systems and Computational AI	7
1.4.1 Belief-Desire-Intention Paradigm	8
1.4.2 The Computational Agent	10
1.5 Trust and Explainability in Intelligent Systems	12
1.5.1 Trust Definition and Measure	13
1.5.2 Explainability as a trait d’union between Ethics and Practical Applications	15
1.5.3 Other Paradigms	17
1.6 Research Questions	18
1.7 Thesis Contribution and Structure	19
2 Literature Review and State of the Art	20
2.1 Regulatory Framework: A Comparative Analysis of China, United States and European Union	20
2.1.1 China: Centralized Approach and Govern-driven Ethics	20
2.1.2 United States: A Market-Driven Approach	21
2.1.3 European Union: A Pioneering Regulatory Approach	21
2.2 Explainable Artificial Intelligence	22
2.3 Multi-agent Systems	24
2.4 Distributed Ledger Technologies	25
2.5 Decentralised Autonomous Organisations	27
3 Theory Framework	29
3.1 The Multilayer Nature of Cognitive Computational Agents	29
3.1.1 Peripheral Layer: The Interface to the Environment	30
3.1.2 Control Layer: Perception and Proprioception	30
3.1.3 Decision-Making Layer: Strategic Planning and Learning	31
3.1.4 Explainability Layer	32
3.2 Production Rules, Reasoning and Logic Programming Languages	33
3.2.1 Production Rules	33
3.2.2 Reasoning	35
3.2.3 Logic Programming Languages	36
3.3 Knowledge Base through Constraints Definition	38

3.4	Operational Instruments for Explainability	39
3.5	Explainable Computational Agents	43
4	Methods to Implement Explainable Computational Agents	47
4.1	How to Define Trust in <i>MAS</i> and <i>DAOs</i>	47
4.2	How to Define Explainability in <i>MAS</i> and <i>DAOs</i>	49
4.3	Behavioural Trees	51
4.3.1	Behavioural Trees in Robotics	52
4.4	Fuzzy Logic to measure Trust and Explainability	54
4.5	Languages for Intelligent Systems	59
4.5.1	DALI: A Declarative Language for Programming Intelligent Agents	60
4.5.2	TeleoR and Qlog: two advanced logic-based languages designed for artificial intelligence and agent control	63
5	Results	68
5.1	DLT for Finance: Over-the-Counter transactions	68
5.2	DAO and DLT for Tax Credit Tracking: Secure Fiscal Credit Model	73
5.3	Digital Twin and BC for seismic prevention: the Building Ledger Dossier	80
5.4	DLT, MAS and DAOs for Cognitive Robotics	82
5.4.1	Enhancing Robotics with Advanced Reasoning Capabilities: SkRobot with TeleoR/QuLog	83
5.4.2	Increasing Accountability in Swarm Robotics: HST-4 Architecture	88
5.5	Connecting and Using DAO via Scripting	92
6	Discussion, Conclusions and Future Works	95
6.1	Definition of Trust and Explainability	95
6.2	Adding Trust and Explainability	96
6.3	Applications to Real World Scenarios	97
6.4	Future Works	97
6.4.1	Real-Time DLT Deployment in Swarm Robotics	97
6.4.2	Enhanced Integration of DAOs	98
6.4.3	Integration of Cognitive and Generative AI: LLM as Perception Tools for Facts Grounding	99
6.4.4	Conclusions	100
	bibliography	101
A	List of Publications	111
A.0.1	Journals and International Conference Proceedings	111
A.0.2	National Conferences and Pre Prints	112

List of Figures

- 1.1 Agent Architecture. A Computational Agent has reactive, proactive and social abilities. Elaborated from Poole and Macworth [114] 12
- 1.2 Explainable Agent Architecture. We need an explainability module able to certify, store and illustrate decisions taken by the Computational Agent. Elaborated from Poole and Macworth [114] 17
- 3.1 Explainable Computational Agent architecture 43
- 4.1 Behavioural Tree of a robot performing a simple search and retrieval task. 53
- 4.2 Membership function for *Level of Experience* 55
- 4.3 Membership function for *Age in System* 56
- 4.4 Membership function for *Speed of Response* 56
- 4.5 Membership function for *Financial Contribution* 57
- 4.6 Membership function for *Consistency in Voting Behavior* 57
- 4.7 Defuzzified Trustworthiness output 59
- 5.1 The Over-the-Counter (OTC) trade scheme between a Counterparty (CTP) and a Front Office Investor (FOI). DSMATCH (Credit Default Swap) and MARKIT (Interest Rate Swap) functions of the Post Trade Confirmation (PTC) process is designed through a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) proposal. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17] 70
- 5.2 Business Process Modeling Notation View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17] 71
- 5.3 Business Process Modeling Notation View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17] 72
- 5.4 Ledger Evolution View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17] 72
- 5.5 Typical Work Progress Status distribution. The lower boxes represent the phases of work. The upper boxes are the actions/sub-phases requested for each principal phase of the workflow. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36] 74
- 5.6 Multi-agent System architecture of the demonstrator illustrates the interaction between the DAOs and MAS to Superbonus 110% simulation. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36] 77
- 5.7 On the left side, the demonstrator dashboard for setting the parameters is varied by moving each slider, thus modifying the success threshold of each scenario. To the right side is the agent’s status during the simulation. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36] 79
- 5.8 MAS architecture of Building Ledger Dossier. Three types of agents allow accountability, DAOs management, and interaction with smart contracts. DLT blocks are also presented to provide a more precise understanding of MAS functions. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [34] 81

5.9	Sequence diagram of Plates installation. Two actors, DoW and Installer, interact to install, produce proof documentation and certify works on BC. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [34]	83
5.10	Simple Two Thread TeleoR Agent Architecture. Courtesy of D'Ottavio et al. [32]	85
5.11	(a) Satellites in a Mono-centralized FlowNetwork. They are applications that manage sensors and actuators exchanging data with SkRobots. (b) Multi-centralized FlowNetwork/DipoleNetwork where multiple hubs have their own satellites, arrows are P2P connections. Courtesy of D'Ottavio et al. [32]	86
5.12	Simulation of the NAO humanoid robot after running the QuLog/TeleoR control program, getting close to its target. Courtesy of D'Ottavio et al. [32]	87
5.13	The HST-4 Block Diagram. It is derived from a modification of the one in [71]. We enhanced it by adding a Publish/Subscribe channel and DLT functions. In white are represented novel elements that extend the original blocks in gray.	89
5.14	IOTA transactions happen in 3 steps. The node creates the transaction (violet) and signs it with a private key, then chooses two unconfirmed transactions (green) using a random algorithm and finally solves a hash to finalize the operation. In blue existing confirmed transactions.	90
5.15	Coppelia Simulation environment. The swarm of three Pioneer 3-DX robots moves inside a fence trying to avoid obstacles. The simulation is connected to IOTA Sandbox through a Python module that starts it and reads the decisions taken by robots.	90
5.16	Transactions on IOTA Testnet Explorer. Each action executed by the robots (in this case "turn left") is minted as an NFT along with relevant information and timestamping. The NFT is then sent to the Accountability agent wallet. Each transaction is public and visible on IOTA Testnet.	91
5.17	Decision block scheme to model a robot trying to enter an already formed swarm.	92
5.18	Typescript execution results of a robot in a swarm setting up a DAO and a Voting Poll.	93
5.19	Aragon DAO Console illustrating wallets and a voting poll details.	94

List of Tables

- 1.1 Comparison of Generative AI and Cognitive AI Properties 7
- 2.1 Comparison of AI Regulatory Frameworks: EU, USA, and China 22
- 3.1 Summary of Computational Agent Layers with Properties and Technologies 34
- 5.1 Relationship between the actors and their affiliation DAOs in comparison to the user actions. 76

Acronyms

ACT-R Adaptive Control of Thought-Rational

ADAS Advanced Driver-Assistance System

AI Artificial Intelligence

APIs Application Programming Interfaces

ASP Answer Set Programming

ATP Automated Theorem Proving

BDI Belief-Desire-Intention

BTs Behavioral Trees

CKB Constraints Knowledge Base

CNNs Convolutional Neural Networks

CNP Contract Net Protocol

DACs Digital Autonomous Corporations

DAGs Directed Acyclic Graphs

DAI Distributed Artificial Intelligence

DAOs Distributed Autonomous Organizations

Dapps Distributed Applications

DL Deep Learning

DLT Distributed Ledger Technology

DNNs Deep Neural Networks

DT Digital Twin

EVM Ethereum Virtual Machine

FT Fungible Tokens

GANs Generative Adversarial Networks

GPS General Problem Solver

GPT Generative Pre-trained Transformer

HMMs Hidden Markov Models

HRI Human-Robot Interaction

HST Human-swarm teaming

IoT Internet of Things

KB Knowledge Base

LLMs Large Language Models

MAS Multi-agent System

MDPs Markov Decision Processes

ML Machine Learning

NFT Non-Fungible Tokens

NLP Natural Language Processing

OTC Over-the-Counter

OWL Ontology Web Languages

PoH Proof of History

PoS Proof of Stake

PoW Proof of Work

PRS Procedural Reasoning System

RL Reinforcement Learning

RRNs Recurrent Neural Networks

SA Situation Awareness

SVMs Support Vector Machines

SWRL Semantic Web Rule Language

XAI Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Chapter 1

Introduction

Presenting the history and scope of *Artificial Intelligence (AI)* is not an easy task. In fact, this paradigm has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of the modern era, connecting the domains of computation, cognitive science, and engineering to simulate and possibly enhance human intelligence. The path of *AI*, from its origin till today, has been both an intellectual effort and a practical application of understanding and recreating the mechanisms of thought and decision-making. This introduction explores the historical evolution of *AI*, its most popular definitions as proposed by widely recognized researchers, and the conceptual divergence between Cognitive AI and Generative AI, two dominant paradigms defining contemporary lines of research and innovation in the field.

1.1 Brief Travel Notes on AI Journey

From an historical perspective, *AI* development has intellectual foundations that trace back to ancient philosophical inquiries into the nature of thought and reason. Early works by philosophers such as Aristotle laid the groundwork for formal logic, which became instrumental in the development of computational systems. During the 17th century, the idea of representing human thoughts as a symbolic reasoning process, started to take place. Many philosophers and mathematicians like Descartes, Pascal and Leibnitz, leveraging the works of the "Grandfather of AI" Hobbes [70], posed the theoretical foundations for the Analytical Machine envisioned by Babbage [11]: the first general-purpose Turing-complete computer. The advent of digital computing in the mid-20th century transformed *AI* into a scientific discipline, in particular Alan Turing's 1950 paper, "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" [140], formulated the question, "Can machines think?" and introduced the Turing Test as a measure of machine intelligence. This period also saw the development of *Automated Theorem Proving (ATP)*; an important technique that allows computers to prove automatically theorems using formal logic rules [88]. Relying upon Kurt Goedel findings on incompleteness theorems, *ATP* leverages methods like Backward and Forward Chaining as well as Resolution to prove correctness of algorithms and optimize complex systems. In this vein should also be framed the creation of first automated reasoning programs such as the Logic Theorist by Allen Newell and Herbert Simon [106], which for the first time resembled human like problem-solving processes [68].

The term "Artificial Intelligence" was coined in 1956 during the Dartmouth Workshop [133] ,

marking the official birth of the field. The participants, including among others John McCarthy and Marvin Minsky, envisioned machines capable of reasoning, learning, and performing tasks typically requiring human intelligence. Over subsequent decades, *AI* research oscillated between optimism and scepticism, influenced by technological breakthroughs and limitations that inevitably alternate. The 1960s and 70s saw, at the high level of conceptual modelization, the development of primitive systems capable of understanding natural languages, albeit limited to narrow and very specialistic domains and to simple structure of sentences. At the low level of computation architectures instead, the period spanning from the WWII post-war to the whole 60s witnessed the infancy of neural networks with three cornerstone papers defining (i) the concept of neuron and how it could be the base for a Turing-complete machine (McCulloch and Pitts [96]), (ii) the possibility of learning for neural networks (Minsky [99]) and (iii) the concept of perceptron (Rosenblatt [122]). During 1970s and 1980s two paradigms have been defined and developed which are relevant for our purpose: Expert Systems able to acquire, represent and replicate human knowledge in a particular field, like DENDRAL [12] in chemistry, and the rise of Logic Programming as implementation of *AI* reasoning, with languages like Prolog [28]. The 1990s, after a decade of the 80s where *AI* and Neural Networks seem to have a setback, witnessed a remarkable development in areas of great specialization and was transformative for *AI*, marked by key achievements that paved the ground for modern advancements. The most important results of research in this period are, in our opinion, the following:

- In *Machine Learning (ML)* area, main advances were represented by (a) formalization of *Support Vector Machines (SVMs)*, introduced by Drucker et al. [48], which became a powerful method for classification and regression tasks; and (b) introduction of *Recurrent Neural Networks (RRNs)* and their application in sequence modeling and time-series prediction;
- Coming to *Natural Language Processing (NLP)* the development of probabilistic models, such as *Hidden Markov Models (HMMs)*, improved tasks like speech recognition and machine translation;
- Expert Systems and Practical Applications experienced the (a) growth in the deployment in industries like healthcare (e.g., MYCIN for medical diagnosis [52]) and finance, and the (b) introduction of Fuzzy Logic systems [152] to foster intelligent behaviour in large-scale consumer appliances.
- Computer Vision progress regarded the advancements in image processing algorithms, including early efforts in face recognition and object detection.

To give the measure of the improvement of intelligent techniques obtained during this decade in 1997, IBM's Deep Blue[16] defeated world chess champion Garry Kasparov, marking a significant milestone in *AI*'s ability to handle complex decision-making and strategy. Finally the early 21st century is implementing the comeback of *AI* experienced in 2000s fueled by advancements in *ML*, data availability, and computational power. The trends of particular interest are:

- The rise of Data-Driven *AI* thanks to the growth in big data and computational power that enabled more sophisticated *ML* models. In particular, advances in Ensemble Learning methods like Random Forests [10] and Boosting algorithms (e.g., AdaBoost [58]), are giving support

to new paradigms in Neural Networks. Following this renewed interest in such networks, the research oriented towards configuration with more layers of neurons, setting the stage for *Deep Learning (DL)* [82] and fostering the development of *Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)* for image recognition and classification [23].

- The massive adoption of *AI* in Robotics with the introduction of humanoid robots like Honda's ASIMO¹ or Boston Dynamic's Atlas², showcasing improved navigation, speech, and gesture recognition. Also use of *Reinforcement Learning (RL)* [78] in Robotics has seen a rise in usage, especially for tasks requiring adaptive decision-making.
- *NLP* improved remarkably and produced, in the *Large Language Models (LLMs)* [104] area of research, one of the most important innovation of the decade: the use of *Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT)* [150] to generate human-like content in terms of text, images and other multimedia products.
- In the area of Autonomous Systems, DARPA's Grand Challenge in 2004 [7] pushed the boundaries of autonomous vehicle technologies, even though no vehicle completed the course in the first challenge. By 2005, several vehicles completed the revised course, demonstrating practical advancements in navigation and perception. Great steps forward have been made in *Advanced Driver-Assistance System (ADAS)* [137], with commercial solutions offering Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) Level 2 of automation products (Tesla Autopilot [44]).
- The expansion of AI Applications in everyday commercial needs as, for example, the application of AI in Recommendation Systems, as seen in e-commerce and entertainment platforms like Amazon³ and on-demand streaming platforms like Netflix [64]. In the field of content generation assistants, Open AI ChatGPT, Microsoft Copilot and Google Bard AI (now Gemini AI) represent, although controversial, three milestone application [136].
- Lastly advancements in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology thanks to *DL*, particularly in genomics and drug discovery, exhibited unprecedented performance and reliability [136].

Once we briefly outlined the history of *AI* and its recent hot topics of application, we should try to give a definition of the paradigm or at define the field of such technologies that are meaningful for our work scope.

1.2 What are Artificial Intelligences?

AI is a multifaceted discipline, and its definitions reflect the complexity of such wide area of research; the classic description, that is still widely recognized, is the one given during the Dartmouth Workshop: "every aspect of learning or any other feature of intelligence can in principle be so precisely described that a machine can be made to simulate it." [95]. This definition, however, is counterfactual and focuses on the system's behavior rather than its intrinsic nature and specifically, on what the system is 'thinking'. Also, the well known and still popular Turing Test for intelligent

¹<https://global.honda/en/robotics/asimo/>, accessed on January 2025

²<https://bostondynamics.com/atlas/>, accessed on January 2025

³<https://www.amazon.science/the-history-of-amazons-recommendation-algorithm>, accessed on January 2025

machines, based on the principle that a machine is intelligent if a human examiner can't distinguish its answers from a human being ones when questioned, is ultimately based on a counterfactual assumption and defines the intelligence in terms of the comparison of results. But two entities can give the same result, and even use the same steps to get it, without being the same thing or have the same nature.

In the need of having more scientific and applicable definitions of *AI*, recent research stems have taken the road of describing *AI* in terms of its products. Shapiro, for example, defines *AI* as "a field of computer science and engineering concerned with the computational understanding of intelligent behaviour and with the creation of artifacts that exhibit such behaviour" [128]. This perspective highlights the dual focus on understanding intelligence and replicating it artificially.

An interesting study for defining *AI* is given by Wang [144]. He envisions five different levels of human intelligence abstraction, modelling a human brain and an artificial agent as entities that have input perceptions P from the environment, taking actions A to modify the external world, and updating their internal states S during this input/output process. In this way if the human brain is defined as $HB = [P^{HB}, S^{HB}, A^{HB}]$ while the artificial one as $AB = [P^{AB}, S^{AB}, A^{AB}]$; with this premise, defining *AI* means to find a way to explain how the artificial agent can approximate or be identical to the human brain or $AB \sim HB$.

(i) The first approach of Wang, named Structure AI, aims to reproduce exactly the structure of human brain mental processes. Thus all the components at the base of modelling must be similar. We can describe such assertion using predicates logic notation:

$$(AB \sim HB) \Leftrightarrow (P^{HB} \sim P^{AB}) \wedge (S^{HB} \sim S^{AB}) \wedge (A^{HB} \sim A^{AB})$$

This solution of getting *AI* replicating exactly a human brain appears infeasible right away due to the complexity of the organ; furthermore, at the present level of technology, the feasible idea is to replicate mental capabilities of the human brain rather than its biological structure. (ii) Following these considerations, the second perspective postulated aims to replicate the behaviour of the human brain without implementing its complexity, and is in fact named Behaviour AI. Here the conditions that need to be satisfied are the similarity in perceptions get from the environment and consequent actions taken:

$$(AB \sim HB) \Leftrightarrow (P^{HB} \sim P^{AB}) \wedge (A^{HB} \sim A^{AB})$$

The sufficient condition enunciated by Turing for a machine to be intelligent, is an example of this type of approach where what matters is similarity in behaviour given coincident inputs. (iii) Another view of the problem consists in describing intelligence as the Capability of an artificial agent to solve problems with similar results of humans albeit in a different way. Considering i and j two moments in time, the idea is to see perception as a problem to solve p and the action as a solution s to the input. If the solution is similar for similar inputs the artificial intelligence is not distinguishable by the human one:

$$(AB \sim HB) \Leftrightarrow \sum_{i,j=0}^n (p_i^{AB} \sim p_j^{HB}) \wedge (s_i^{AB} \sim s_j^{HB})$$

This Capability AI paradigm leaves though open the question of what type of problems require "intelligence" to be solved; we'll explore better a declination of this quantitative perspective oriented to big data crawling and analysis to define p and s , the Generative AI, in section 1.3.

(iv) On the other way, exploring a qualitative approach Wang describe the Function AI. The idea is to mimic cognitive functions of human brain, and thus concentrate on mapping perceptions 'p' into action 'a' taken to solve the input problem; if 'f' is such function, defined as $a_i^{AB} = f^{AB}(p_i^{AB})$, $a_j^{HB} = f^{HB}(p_j^{HB})$ we can describe intelligence as the similarity of human mapping versus artificial agent one:

$$AB \sim HB \Leftarrow (f^{AB} \sim f^{HB})$$

The function f can be intended mainly as a reasoner that, worth to be noted, could yield different results between human and artificial agent (eg. results could be acceptable also within a certain grade of tolerance). A particular declination of this paradigm is Cognitive AI, which is of great interest for the present study, and will be better analysed in section 1.3 in comparison to Generative AI. This type of *AI*, generalised to a function that maps the whole possibility of input perceptions to the entire set of possible output actions, gives form to the last paradigm envisioned by Wang or (v) Principle AI. In fact in this case the reasoning function is enunciated as a principle valid in every possible condition of the world (all possible values of the variables defining the environment where the agent is acting).

To sum up a bit the considerations done above on definitions of *AI*, we can observe some common traits. The first one is that intelligence interpretation has changed during the years, bonding its meaning to the technologies and services that have been derived from its paradigm. Thus definitions varied when the research attention passed through theorem proving, expert systems, neural network, intelligent agents, big data and *DL*. Consequently, we can underline a second common aspect, the theoretical base upon which *AI* laid its foundations changed accordingly to the different perspectives that alternated during the years. We spanned from knowledge representation to *NLP* and Robotics passing through Reasoning and Planning, *ML* and Computer Vision. In conclusion we can say that probably we have to speak of Artificial Intelligences rather than of a single paradigm, all equally legitimate to exist and valid as a scientific field of research and application.

1.3 The Eternal Struggle Between Good and Evil: Cognitive and Generative AI

For the aim of our study we'll focus on the broad and widely accepted separation of *AI* paradigm in two stems: Cognitive AI that is dedicated to simulate human thought and Generative AI, oriented to creating new artifacts and products.

Cognitive AI, is a subfield rooted in cognitive science, and focuses on replicating human-like thinking processes. This paradigm seeks to model mental processes such as perception, memory, and reasoning, drawing inspiration from how the human brain processes information. Cognitive AI systems are often used in applications requiring contextual understanding, such as natural language processing, decision support systems, and autonomous agents. They emphasize interpretability and alignment with human cognition, making them integral to domains like healthcare, education, and human-computer interaction (see Xu et al. [147]).

This type of *AI* relies heavily on symbolic reasoning and knowledge representation, techniques that encode human knowledge into formal structures. Early AI systems, such as MYCIN [130] and Winograd's SHRDLU [145], exemplify this approach, where explicit rules and logical inferences

drove intelligent behavior. Modern developments integrate these techniques with *ML* to create hybrid systems capable of adapting to complex, dynamic environments.

Generative AI, on the other way, is oriented on the creation and the generation of novel content. It leverages advanced *ML* models, particularly Deep Learning architectures like *Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)* [65] and Transformers, to produce text, images, music, and other media. Unlike Cognitive AI, which simulates thought processes, Generative AI focuses on producing outputs that are indistinguishable from those created by humans.

Prominent examples of Generative AI include aforesaid OpenAI's GPT models⁴, which generate coherent and contextually relevant text, images and videos. These systems are trained on vast datasets, enabling them to learn patterns and relationships to produce high-quality outputs. The implications of Generative AI are profound, ranging from creative industries to scientific discovery, but they also raise ethical concerns regarding authenticity, misuse, and intellectual property.

The distinction between Cognitive and Generative AI lies in their objectives and methodologies. Cognitive AI is primarily concerned with understanding and emulating human thought processes, focusing on transparency and alignment with human reasoning. It seeks to enhance decision-making, problem-solving, and other cognitive functions by providing systems with a conceptual understanding of tasks.

In contrast, Generative AI prioritizes output quality and innovation over interpretability. It excels in creating original content but often operates as a "black box," with limited insight into the underlying decision-making process. This distinction reflects broader philosophical and practical debates within AI, including the trade-offs between explainability, autonomy, and creativity.

Furthermore, Cognitive AI, derived from the previously discussed Functional AI, is on our opinion a more equilibrated and general approach to the problem. In fact, despite its functions are mostly abstractly derived from the human mindset, is less anthropocentric providing the field with a stronger identity compared to Generative AI (which stems from Capability AI), by generalizing its capabilities from specific problems to abstract functions. However, one issue with this perspective is the fragmentation of *AI*, (see Brachman et al. [8]). This arises from challenges in combining diverse models, algorithms, and frameworks into a unified architecture capable of robust, context-aware decision-making. Since each reasoning function can be specified separately, there is no incentive to consider other functions. Also when a function is specified in this way, it may diverge significantly from its original brain one, where it is tightly integrated with other cognitive processes. As a result, Cognitive AI systems often demonstrate competence in narrow domains but fail to generalize knowledge. Another delicate aspect of Cognitive AI is underlined by Floridi in his book "Ethics of Artificial Intelligence" [56]. He ties the Generative AI to an engineering approach to intelligence where the aim is to reproduce the human one, while the Cognitive AI to a more philosophical activity of producing a real intelligent behaviour. In his view the Cognitive AI paradigm is an impossible goal to obtain, at least in the near future, while Generative AI is having impressive results albeit the need of always bigger and better data set could limit its progress. In table 1.1 we propose a small recap of relevant features of Cognitive AI vs Generative AI. For the scope of our thesis though, we must restrict the field of research of an otherwise too wide area of study; in particular, we want to refer to a subset of the Cognitive AI systems represented by the paradigm of Computational AI or Intelligent Systems. In the next section we'll define what is "intelligence" for our purpose and the

⁴<https://platform.openai.com/docs/models>, accessed on January 2025

Table 1.1: Comparison of Generative AI and Cognitive AI Properties

Property	Generative AI	Cognitive AI
Definition	Focuses on generating content such as text, images, or music.	Simulates human reasoning, learning, and problem-solving abilities.
Core Functionality	Produces novel outputs by learning patterns from data.	Mimics human cognitive processes like decision-making and understanding.
Examples of Applications	Text generation (e.g., ChatGPT), image creation (e.g., DALL-E).	Autonomous decision-making, contextual understanding in robots.
Learning Approach	Typically uses unsupervised or self-supervised learning to model data distributions.	Often integrates reinforcement learning and symbolic reasoning.
Primary Goal	Creativity and content generation.	Human-like intelligence and adaptability.
Strengths	Highly effective at pattern recognition and large-scale data synthesis.	Enables complex reasoning and contextual understanding.
Weaknesses	May lack deep understanding and interpretability of generated outputs.	Can struggle with handling vast unstructured data efficiently.
Technological Foundation	Deep neural networks like transformers.	A combination of neural networks, expert systems, and other symbolic approaches.
Interaction Style	Often reactive, responding to prompts or instructions.	Proactive, capable of autonomous behavior in dynamic scenarios.

funding brick of an Intelligent System: a computational agent.

1.4 Intelligent Systems and Computational AI

The aim of this thesis is ultimately to define methods to design Intelligent Systems, we need then to have a precise definition and modeling of what we think an intelligent entity is. In our opinion, the Cognitive paradigm of *AI* is the one that fits and represents better the human way of doing intelligent actions and decisions; thus the first basis for any further speculation on this matter is the definition of the atomic entity that could show sign of intelligence: the Computational Agent.

To better understand the nature of this entity, it may be useful to recall that the word "agent" originates from the Latin word "agens" or "agentis", which is the present participle of the verb "agere", meaning "to do," "to drive," or "to act." This root is central to the notion of an agent as "one who acts" or "a doer." Over time, the term has been adapted into various contexts with related meanings:

- Medieval Latin: It retained its sense of someone or something performing an action.
- Old French and Middle English: It evolved to refer to an intermediary or a person acting on behalf of another, such as in legal or diplomatic roles.

- Modern English: Its scope expanded to include entities that exert influence or cause change, such as chemical agents or computational agents.

The concept's core — an entity capable of action or causing effect — remains consistent across its uses. Having understood deeper the nature of an Agent, we have to decline it in a form that is useful for the theoretical design of agents to be used in practical applications. We will examine, in the next sections, some paradigms meant for such objectives.

1.4.1 Belief-Desire-Intention Paradigm

The *Belief-Desire-Intention (BDI)* paradigm, initially formulated by Bratman [9], has emerged as a cornerstone framework for understanding and modeling rational agency. This paradigm integrates formal logic and philosophical insights to represent how agents navigate decision-making processes in dynamic and often uncertain environments (see Rao et al. [119]). It is particularly influential in *AI* and *Multi-agent System (MAS)*, where it provides a foundation for creating agents that reason and act in ways that emulate human decision-making. The *BDI* model is built upon three interrelated components:

1. Beliefs (B): represent an agent's informational state or what the agent perceives or knows about the world. Beliefs can be formalized in epistemic logic, typically denoted as $B_a(\phi)$, meaning "agent a believes proposition ϕ ."
2. Desires (D): capture the agent's motivational state or what the agent wants or aspires to achieve. Desires are often treated as a set of potential goals without a commitment to pursuing any particular one.
3. Intentions (I): are the agent's deliberative state goals that the agent has committed to pursuing. Intentions influence an agent's future actions and are central to practical reasoning. A commitment to an intention implies consistency and persistence over time unless compelling reasons emerge to abandon it.

The connection among Beliefs, Desires, and Intentions underpins rational thinking and acting. Agents use their Beliefs to evaluate which Desires are feasible and then commit to specific Intentions that guide their actions. This dynamic process ensures that an agent's behavior is both goal-directed and context-sensitive. The *BDI* paradigm for an agent a can be formalized using Modal Logics to represent the three components:

- Beliefs (B): can be represented using a belief operator B_a , its logic must satisfy properties such as consistency and positive introspection. For example, if $B_a(\phi)$ is true, then $\neg B_a(\neg\phi)$ must also hold (an agent cannot simultaneously believe a proposition and its negation).

$$B_a(\phi) \rightarrow \neg B_a(\neg\phi)$$

- Desires (D): Desires are represented with an operator D_a , expressing what an agent values or seeks to achieve. These may conflict with one another, unlike beliefs, which must be consistent.

- Intentions (I): Intentions are represented with an operator I_a . Formal logic captures the commitment to intentions through axioms such as persistence:

$$I_a(\phi) \wedge B_a(\phi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow I_a(\psi)$$

This means that if an agent intends ϕ and believes that ϕ implies ψ , then the agent must also intend to do ψ .

Bratman’s foundational insight into the *BDI* paradigm lies in his conceptualization of intentions as plans. Unlike desires, intentions are stable and persist across time. They structure deliberation by constraining further decision-making and reducing the need for repeated evaluation of options. For example, if an agent intends to write a book, this intention will shape sub-goals such as conducting research, drafting chapters, and revising content. Bratman also emphasizes three key features of Intentions:

1. Stability: Once formed, Intentions are not easily abandoned.
2. Means-end Coherence: Agents adopt means that align with their intentions.
3. Consistency: Intentions must not conflict with one another or with the agent’s Beliefs.

Practical reasoning in the *BDI* model thus, involves two main processes: (i) Deliberation and (ii) Means-end reasoning. During the Deliberation phase, agents evaluate potential Desires against their Beliefs to form Intentions. Means-end reasoning then identifies actions that align with these Intentions. For example, an agent a who desires to travel and believes it is feasible, forms the Intention to book a flight. This Intention triggers further actions, such as selecting a destination and making reservations. The logic of practical reasoning can be formalized as follows:

1. Deliberation:

$$B_a(\text{feasible}(\phi)) \wedge D_a(\phi) \rightarrow I_a(\phi)$$

If an agent a believes ϕ , ϕ is feasible and desires ϕ , the agent intends ϕ .

2. Means-end Reasoning:

$$I_a(\phi) \wedge B_a(\phi \rightarrow \psi) \rightarrow I_a(\psi)$$

If an agent a intends ϕ and believes achieving ϕ requires ψ , the agent intends ψ .

The *BDI* paradigm has been widely adopted in computational models of agency, particularly in *MAS* and Robotics. Prominent frameworks, such as *Procedural Reasoning System (PRS)* of Geroeff and Ingrand [63] and *Jadex* (see Pokhar et al. [113]), implement the *BDI* architecture to enable agents to perform goal-directed actions in real-world environments. These systems rely on a cycle of perception, deliberation, and action:

1. Perception: Updating beliefs based on observations.
2. Deliberation: Selecting intentions by evaluating desires against current beliefs.
3. Execution: Acting on intentions by selecting and performing actions

The *BDI* paradigm has proven effective in domains such as autonomous vehicles, decision-support systems, and Game AI. Its ability to model agents that adapt to changing circumstances while pursuing long-term goals makes it especially valuable in complex, dynamic environments. However, challenges remain in scaling the paradigm to handle high-dimensional data and in ensuring robustness against unexpected events. Extensions to the *BDI* framework, such as Probabilistic Reasoning and Reinforcement Learning, aim to address these limitations.

The *BDI* paradigm offers also a robust framework for modeling rational behaviour, bridging philosophical theory and computational practice. Its logical foundations and practical applications continue to influence advancements in *AI* and Cognitive science, providing insights into how agents reason, plan, and act. As researchers address ongoing challenges, the *BDI* paradigm will remain essential for understanding and designing intelligent systems.

1.4.2 The Computational Agent

A second interesting paradigm is the one that defines Computational Agents. Here we will consider the definition, that we'll make our for the rest of this work along with other concepts presented in this section, given by Poole & Mackworth [114]:

"A computational agent is an agent whose decisions about its actions can be explained in terms of computation. That is, the decision can be broken down into primitive operations that can be implemented in a physical device."

Here the things that need to be evidenced are that the entity "Agent" acts in an environment and is defined only by its actions. So, the nature (eg. human / non-human) or other properties like behaviour, are not a discriminant. A second issue worth to be discussed is what are the aspects that make a computational agent "intelligent". We'll present in the next points some insights trying to formalize the concepts through Computational Logic on the base of Section 1.3.

Before talking of agent's properties, we have to define a relevant entity involved in the process: the Environment 'E' where the computational agent operates. It can be described as the external context or system within which an agent get perceptions, performs actions, and seeks to achieve its goals. Environments are characterized by several properties, including Observability (fully or partially observable), Determinism (deterministic or stochastic), Dynamics (static or dynamic), and Discreteness (discrete or continuous). These properties influence how agents model their surroundings and make decisions. To represent environments, frameworks like State Spaces [151] for discrete deterministic situations, and *Markov Decision Processes (MDPs)* [115] when uncertainty is taken into account, are commonly used. To illustrate the basic concepts if we consider, for the sake of simplicity, the Space State situation; we can then describe the aforesaid Environment as a tuple $E = [S, A, T]$ where:

- State Space S is the set of all possible states, where each $s_i \in S$ represents a unique configuration of the system:

$$S = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_n\}$$

We have $s_0 \in S$ as the starting state of the system, and one or more Goal States $G \subseteq S$ that are a subset of possible states satisfying the system's objectives.

- Actions A is the the set of all possible actions an Agent can take in the Environment E :

$$A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}$$

- Transition Function TF a function that maps a state $s \in S$ and an action $a \in A$ to a new state $s' \in S$, representing how actions transform the state.

$$TF : S \times A \rightarrow S$$

Coming to the properties that denote an intelligent behaviour of an agent, we can introduce and describe some high-level concepts summarized in the following list:

- Reasoning in order to reach a goal: the Agent perceives some type of information from the environment, elaborates it on the basis of its logic and past experience, and then acts on the environment to maximize its utility in terms of goals to reach.
- Autonomy: in doing this activity the Agent can be fully independent and makes the decisions it thinks are better to reach its goals, rather than have a human-in-the-loop controlling and authorizing its actions. In any case, it decides what needs to be done to satisfy the goals, rather than acting passively.
- Reactivity: the Agent maintains an ongoing interaction with its environment, and responds to changes and events that occur in it based on its abilities, previous knowledge, and past experiences.
- Pro-activity: furthermore, its behaviour is not only passive when receives stimuli from the environment; the Agent generates strategies and attempts to achieve goals; this must happen not driven solely by events; but it has to take the initiative and evaluate results.
- Social Ability: in real-world situations scenarios are complex and usually the agent must interact with the environment as well as other agents that are situated in the same environment. So it has to deal with many other entities - and possibly humans - via some kind of agent communication language. The mood of the agents could be either cooperative or competitive.

In Figure 1.1 we summarize the architecture, derived from the above paradigms, of a Computational Agent. We'll adopt it as the base entity making up the Intelligent Systems for the scope of the present work. To conclude this section we want to introduce few other concepts that are widely used in modeling of Computational Agents. Consider an Agent in the process of choosing its actions after reasoning of stimuli received, it generates a change in the Environment E that translates in a sequence of states s_i connected by actions a_i . This sequence of alternate states and actions is called Path P and is described as follows:

$$P = (s_0, a_1, s_1, a_2, s_2, \dots, s_k)$$

here the next state is obtained by applying the aforesaid Transition Function $TF(s_i, a_i) = s_{i+1}$ for all i . We may find it useful to introduce a function that assigns a numerical cost to each path or

Figure 1.1: Agent Architecture. A Computational Agent has reactive, proactive and social abilities. Elaborated from Poole and Macworth [114]

action; it can be defined in order to both represent the finite resources that an Agent has available, and to model the different difficulties of and reasoning to take some actions. This Cost Function C is defined below:

$$C : P \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$$

Finally we can introduce and formalize the aim of each Computational Agents, find a Solution or a path P^* from s_0 to a state $s_g \in G$ that minimizes or satisfies specific criteria, optimizing the Cost Function C :

$$P^* = \arg \min_P C(P) \quad \text{or satisfies constraints.}$$

This formulation of Agents is widely used in search problems, planning, and optimization tasks within *AI*. Finally, to sum up the concepts illustrated in this section, we can describe an Intelligent System:

"An Intelligent System is a computational entity, formed by one or more Computational Agent, capable of perceiving its environment, processing information, making decisions, and taking actions autonomously or semi-autonomously to achieve specific goals. In doing this it emulates cognitive functions such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, social ability and adaptation to external changes."

These systems typically integrate principles of *AI* and data analytics to perform such tasks. We will use this definition as a base for speculations and considerations in the next sections.

1.5 Trust and Explainability in Intelligent Systems

The rapid advancement of *AI* has revolutionized various domains, but it also brings doubts and worries, particularly where human lives are directly affected by AI-driven decisions. Central to addressing these concerns are concepts such as Trust, Explainability, Transparency, and Accountability, which are vital for ensuring ethical compliance and fostering end-user confidence. Trust in particular is fundamental to Human-AI interactions, shaping the effective and ethical deployment

of AI systems in society and misaligned trust levels can lead to misuse, abuse, or disuse. Despite its importance, there is a lack of clear models for trust between humans and *AI*.

1.5.1 Trust Definition and Measure

Trust refers to the reliance on the system to perform tasks, make decisions, or provide recommendations in a way that aligns with users' expectations of safety, accuracy, ethical conduct, and overall functionality. It is a multiform paradigm that includes both cognitive and emotional dimensions. We have to distinguish two different types of Trust.

In Generative AI trust refers to the confidence users place in the system's ability to produce reliable, accurate, and ethical outputs. Generative AI models, such as Chat GPT⁵ and DALL-E⁶, rely on probabilistic techniques to create content. Trust arises from factors like transparency in model training, robustness to adversarial inputs, and fairness in generated outputs. For example, a Generative AI system's trustworthiness can be mathematically evaluated using measures of predictive uncertainty and alignment with user expectations.

Trust in Cognitive AI instead extends beyond generation to encompass reasoning, learning, and adaptability. Cognitive AI systems are designed to mimic human-like thought processes, making trust contingent on their ability to reason transparently and align with ethical standards. Here Trust often involves validating the consistency of beliefs, decisions, and actions within a *BDI*-like framework (see Section 1.4.1). For instance, ensuring that system behavior aligns with observed evidence and that its intentions remain coherent under dynamic contexts builds user confidence. Cognitive trust is based thus on the system's perceived competence and reliability, while emotional trust is rooted in emotive connections users may develop with systems exhibiting human-like behaviors.

An interesting view of the problem is given by Jacobi et al. [75], they propose a model of Trust inspired by interpersonal trust but tailored to Human-AI interactions. Human-AI trust is defined as a directional relationship in which a human (the trustor) perceives an AI system (the trustee) as capable of upholding specific contracts while accepting vulnerability to the *AI*'s decisions. Unlike interpersonal trust, which involves intent and emotional dimensions, Human-AI trust focuses on the perceived Reliability and Predictability of the system's performance. The foundation of this model includes the introduction of two relevant concepts: (i) Vulnerability or the degree to which the trustor must accept risks associated with the trustee's actions; and (ii) Anticipation or the level to which the trustor should reasonably predict the *AI*'s behaviour. The two key elements of Human-AI trust are:

1. Capability to Maintain Contracts and Agreements: Trust depends on the AI system's ability to meet specific contractual expectations, such as fairness, accuracy, and transparency.
2. Acceptance of Vulnerability and Risk: Users accept the inherent risks of relying on the AI, recognizing that unfavourable outcomes are possible but not certain.

For Trust to exist thus, there must be risk involved as it enables the user to mitigate uncertainty by fostering a belief in the *AI*'s consistent and beneficial behaviour.

To give a possible basic definition of Trust we refer to sociology, here interpersonal trust exists when one party (eg. a Human agent *H*) believes another party (eg. Artificial Agent *A*) will act in

⁵<https://chatgpt.com/>, accessed on January 2025

⁶<https://openai.com/index/dall-e-3/>, accessed on January 2025

their best interest, accepting vulnerability to A 's actions (see Mayer's integrative trust model [94]). The idea is then to introduce a function T to measure the degree of Confidence of H in expectations of A ,

$$T_H(A) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

we will discuss a method for this problem in Section 4.1. This view of Trust facilitates predictability and collaboration, mitigating uncertainty and risk; in particular for Human-AI trust it may help to address:

- Risk Management: need of Trust measuring emerges when users perceive possible adverse outcomes from AI decisions.
- Distrust Avoidance: the user avoids unfavourable or dangerous outcomes by not accepting vulnerability to the AI when Trust measurement is not positive.

In this perspective we can envision a Contractual Trust because Trust in AI is connected to specific contracts clauses, expectations and commitments about the AI 's behaviour. Here we want to underline that a Contract, either among humans or hybrid agents, is by definition an ex-ante agreement meant to bond parties to some types of rules. Furthermore we can envision that an Artificial Intelligent Agent must guarantee such agreements to foster Trust in a human user of the system (we will apply this concept when introducing the decision-making and explainability layers in Sections 3.1.3 and 3.1.4). This modelling of Trust allows to define some important properties of its paradigm:

- Contracts and Contexts: Trust depends on the ex-ante and explicit recognition of the context and contract. Contracts include accuracy, fairness, transparency, and robustness.
- Model Correctness: Users trust the model to make correct decisions when they can anticipate its patterns.
- Evaluation Methods: Test sets, post-deployment data, and ex-ante expert assessments are tools for validating contracts.

Relying upon this "contract view" of Trust we can introduce the concepts of Trustworthiness and Warranted Trust

- Trustworthiness: The capability of an AI model to uphold a contract, independent of whether users trust it. Here again we underline the ex-ante and contest-independent nature of this property.
- Warranted Trust: Trust caused by the AI 's trustworthiness, and potentially evaluated through function T . When a minimum threshold T_min is overcome trust is warranted:

$$trust_warranted \leftarrow T_H(A) \geq T_min$$

- Unwarranted Trust: When users' perceived trust is not based on the AI 's capabilities but extraneous factors (e.g., user interface design).

Trust should be pursued only when warranted as mismatches between perceived trust and trustworthiness can lead to misuse (excessive trust) or disuse (insufficient trust). Coming to its intrinsic nature we can affirm that Trust arises from two sources, each contributing uniquely to the user's belief in an *AI* system:

1. Intrinsic Trust: Based on the *AI*'s reasoning process aligning with the user's expectations, requires transparency and interpretability. Intrinsic trust depends on:
 - (a) Comprehension: Users must understand the *AI*'s reasoning, possibly before they start to use it.
 - (b) Alignment: The *AI*'s decision-making process must align with the user's prior knowledge or expectations.

As an example of Intrinsic trust is a small, interpretable decision tree (see Section 4.3) enables users to grasp the *AI*'s reasoning, fostering trust.

2. Extrinsic Trust: Derived from observed performance and evaluation schemes, relies on metrics like accuracy, fairness, and robustness. A doctor's reputation for correct diagnoses fosters extrinsic trust, independent of their reasoning process. Methods to foster extrinsic trust derive from aforesaid activities of (i) Evaluation by Proxy: Trust derived from expert validation of *AI* performance; (ii) Post-Deployment Data: Trust based on real-world performance metrics; and (iii) Test Sets: Specialized datasets used to validate specific contracts, such as fairness or robustness. The last two can be integrated in a learning process of an agent and be part of its Knowledge-base (see Section 3.5)

Intrinsic and extrinsic trust are complementary: while intrinsic trust appeals to users' understanding of *AI* behavior, extrinsic trust reassures them through empirical evidence.

1.5.2 Explainability as a trait d'union between Ethics and Practical Applications

Some properties of Intelligent Agents, like degree of autonomy, privacy balance or potential bias in decision-making, raise ethical questions that are often of difficult solution. Many initiatives have been taken during the years to define a picture of relevant principles in *AI*, like Asilomar Principles of *AI* [101] or Montreal Declaration [100] to name few, but a widely general accepted framework is still far to come. An interesting effort towards a unified view of ethics principles is done by Floridi and Cowls [57] and Floridi [56]. The authors analyse six main declarations on *AI* Principles isolating 47 different principles to finally propose a synthesis of 5 recurring principles meant to represent a general framework for Ethics in *AI*. Four of them are borrowed from bioethics:

- Beneficence: *AI* must promote wellness of human, or more broadly biological, beings as well as the preservation of Earth;
- Non-maleficence: avoid the improper use of *AI* to hurt or cause damage to other human beings;
- Autonomy: regulate the degree of self decision of artificial agents and thus is connected to how much humans are in the loop of decisions. This also refers to concepts like delegation and reversibility of decisions;

- Fairness: *AI* must be equal, promote prosperity of people and avoid bias and discrimination.

the fifth one, emerged from the comparative analysis, is connected to the non-biological nature of *AI* and is a mix of the ethical principle of accountability and epistemological intelligibility: it is the principle of Explainability. In this perspective is the paradigm that interlaces the above properties of Trust with Ethics; an Explainable Intelligent System is where the system itself provides human-interpretable justifications for its decisions. It is a key component of Transparency, focusing specifically on making complex algorithms, models, and operations comprehensible to diverse stakeholders, including developers, users, and regulators. Explainability bridges the gap between a system's internal logic — often involving intricate statistical or machine learning models — and the external understanding needed to trust, evaluate, and interact with the system effectively. This involves presenting reasons, causal relationships, or contributing factors behind specific outputs or decisions in a manner that aligns with the audience's expertise. Explainability is particularly critical for mitigating risks associated with opaque "black-box" models, ensuring Accountability, addressing biases, and enabling debugging and refinement of Intelligent Systems. It fosters Trust and ethical usage by empowering stakeholders to critically assess the fairness, reliability, and safety of AI-driven solutions. *Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)* is positioned as a critical tool for trust:

- Increasing Trustworthiness: By revealing reasoning processes, *XAI* helps *AI* align with expectations.
- Promoting Warranted Trust: Users can better anticipate *AI* behavior through explanations.
- Mitigating Distrust: *XAI* can expose flaws, fostering warranted distrust when *AI* fails to meet a contract.

Explainability is fundamentally connected to the paradigm of *Situation Awareness (SA)*, which forms the basis of effective human-in-the-loop decision-making. As per Endsley's *SA* model [49], Explainability is intertwined with other two essential principles of awareness:

- Interpretability, which involves understanding both the internal structures of algorithms and the relationships between inputs and outputs;
- Explainability, which focuses on local parameter comprehension and global decision-making clarity; and
- Predictability, which allows users to anticipate future behaviours of agents.

In *MAS*, challenges such as non-cooperative behaviours and communication delays further complicate achieving these objectives. These principles collectively ensure that Intelligent Systems are not only functionally robust but also ethically and operationally transparent. This integrated approach highlights the multifaceted nature of Explainability, combining technical, ethical, and operational dimensions to address the complexities of modern *AI* applications. By embedding Trust, Transparency, and Accountability into their architecture, these systems can align with both user expectations and regulatory demands, creating a reliable and human-centered *SA* ecosystem. We need then to introduce an enhanced version of the Agent presented till now that may integrate such properties. Furthermore the idea is to give such properties by design to this enhanced agent which

Figure 1.2: Explainable Agent Architecture. We need an explainability module able to certify, store and illustrate decisions taken by the Computational Agent. Elaborated from Poole and Macworth [114]

could be called Explainable Computational Agent. In Figure 1.2 we have a scheme of the modules need for the enhancement of the basic agent described in Section 1.4. Here we integrate modules to foster the paradigms described above, they are added to the Explained Computational Agent by design in order to make possible to access and use them at any time of the life cycle of the system.

Explainability paradigms are thus an "ex-ante" property of the Agent in a way that are available before any event in the Environment occur, and rather are independent of the Environment or of the nature and other abilities of the Agent. This is probably the most important property of Explainable Computational Agent as we propose it, and is in contrast with the "ex-post" way of introducing Explainability in Generative AI where effort to explain "black-box" are usually done after the life-cycle of the system/agents.

1.5.3 Other Paradigms

Let's examine briefly other properties in Intelligent Systems and Computational Agents fields:

- Accountability is related to the obligation of Intelligent System architects to design, deploy, or utilize such systems to ensure their decisions, actions, and impacts are transparent, answerable, and subject to appropriate supervision and control. This articulate concept integrates answerability, the ability to justify actions; authority recognition, ensuring clear roles and responsibilities; and mechanisms to limit misuse or harm. Accountability integrate also Traceability, which allows for immutable registering the documentation, data inputs, and algorithmic logic in order to review and inspect the whole cycle of life of the systems.
- Transparency regards the clarity, comprehensibility, and accessibility of information about how these systems operate, make decisions, and produce outcomes. It encompasses the mechanisms, algorithms, data sources, and contextual factors that influence the system's behaviour. A transparent intelligent system provides stakeholders, including developers, users, and reg-

ulators, with the ability to understand and interpret its functions and decisions effectively. Transparency is crucial for building Trust, ensuring Accountability, and enabling informed decision-making by users or auditors. In the context of ethical and responsible *AI*, Transparency mitigates risks associated with bias of data, errors, and misuse, fostering equal and reliable interactions between humans and *AI* systems.

These elements become increasingly critical in complex Intelligent Systems like Swarm Robotics or *MAS*, where numerous independent agents interact either collaborating as a collective or competing among them. Unlike traditional Single-agent Systems, swarm intelligence introduces unique challenges in ensuring trustworthy AI, particularly as the number of interacting agents increases. Here, human-in-the-loop control and the potential for ethical dilemmas underscore the importance of Explainability at both the internal system level and the external impact level.

These factors grow exponentially complex as the number of agents increases, complicating the Explainability of their behaviors and decisions. Transparent decision architectures, Accountability mechanisms, and immutable data systems are paramount, especially in scenarios where human intervention may be required to oversee or correct system behaviors. Such architectures ensure that intelligent Computational Agents can operate with minimal risks while maintaining user confidence in their decisions.

Over the past decade, the applications of *AI* have expanded into increasingly sophisticated tasks, transitioning from research prototypes to commercial use. These systems often approach human-level performance, raising additional concerns about their security, controllability, and compliance with legal frameworks and societal norms. They demand that these systems provide clarity on their decision-making processes, ensuring ethical and transparent integration into human-centric environments (See Section 2.1 for a Regulatory Framework Analysis).

1.6 Research Questions

After having introduced the topics that will be discussed in this work we have to formalize the research questions we want to answer to. In the next points we'll explicate such questions, briefly introducing the technologies and paradigms that will be treated in the next chapters.

- RQ1: How to define Explainability and Trust by design? We want to define a theoretical framework that could potentially be the base for designing "ex-ante" Intelligent Systems. The aim is to integrate properties like Trust, Accountability, Transparency, and Traceability and define relative methods to apply in the design phase of Computational Agents.
- RQ2: How to add Explainability and Trust by design in Intelligent Systems fostering their ex-ante application? The aim is to survey and select technologies and paradigms that may be suitable to add properties defined in Q1 to Intelligent Systems.
- RQ3: What are the application fields of Explainable Intelligent Systems? We analyse the results of Doctoral Program projects evaluating pro and cons of using technologies defined in RQ2 in various scenarios (eg. Real Time, non Real-time, Swarm Robotics, etc)

1.7 Thesis Contribution and Structure

The Contribution of the Thesis to the field of Cognitive AI is the definition of a theoretical framework and of a set of technologies to foster "ex-ante" Explainability to Intelligent Systems. In particular an innovative architecture to add ex-ante properties relying the Explainable Computational Agent will be formalized. The paradigms that will be introduced to foster each components of Explainability in Intelligent Systems are in brief the following;

- *MAS* to manage complex systems and extend Explainability by design in real world scenarios;
- *Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)* to add Accountability and Traceability of Actions and Communications;
- *Distributed Autonomous Organizations (DAOs)* to foster Transparency and Trust in the decision-making process;

The Structure of the work is meant to divulge the theoretical and practical result obtained during the 3 year Doctoral Program undertaken at University of L'Aquila (2021-2024). After the Introductions of key concepts and paradigms done in this Section, we present the State-of-art of the research areas along with relevant bibliography in Section 2. In Section 3 we will formalize the theory at the base of the aforesaid three-legs architecture (*MAS*, *DLT*, *DAOs*) and the paradigms used to describe and define the behaviour of the Explainable Computational Agent. In following Section 4 the methodologies to apply the theory framework will be presented and how each of them can foster a specific Explainability component. Finally we will present some practical application implemented during the Doctoral Program illustrating the results in Section 5 and discussing them in Section 6 where ultimately will also analyze lessons learned and future developments.

Chapter 2

Literature Review and State of the Art

In this section we will present the state-of-the-art and the relevant literature for the areas of research object of our study. In particular, after introducing the actual situation in the three main legislation entities regarding AI, the review will cover the most relevant concepts in Explainable AI, *MAS*, *DLT* and Blockchain, and *DAOs*. The works cited have been choose for their impact on the topics covered by the thesis, measured as number of citations and innovation grade of ideas presented as per our personal evaluation. The databases utilized for the research, references, and classification of cited works (book chapters, journal articles, and conferences papers have been included in the results) have been Google Scholar ¹ and Elsevier Scopus ². Also, the generative AI tool ChatGPT-Scholar AI ³ has been used for advanced filtering and summarizing of scientific works.

2.1 Regulatory Framework: A Comparative Analysis of China, United States and European Union

The year 2024 has been an important one for the regulation of *AI*. In fact, in March the European Union has approved the first comprehensive legal scheme to regulate the use of *AI*: The Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)⁴. This is a pioneering legislative proposal designed to regulate *AI* across the European Union (EU) based on a risk-based framework. It sets compliance requirements for AI systems and introduces restrictions on high-risk applications. A key aspect of the framework is that AI system must explain how decision afflicting humans are taken, introducing for the first time of *XAI* as a non-negotiable property of Intelligent Systems. Let's examine briefly the different approaches of the three main regulatory players to regulation of *AI* use.

2.1.1 China: Centralized Approach and Govern-driven Ethics

China's regulatory framework, the first to be adopted among major players in 2017, is characterized by a centralized, government-driven model. The New Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan⁵ outlines ambitious goals for *AI* dominance by 2030, emphasizing national security and

¹<https://scholar.google.it/>, accessed on January 2025

²<https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=basic#basic/>, accessed on January 2025

³<https://chatgpt.com/g/g-L2HknCZTC-scholar-ai>, accessed on January 2025

⁴<https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>, accessed on January 2025

⁵https://www.unodc.org/res/ji/import/policy_papers/china_ai_strategy/china_ai_strategy.pdf, accessed on January 2025

economic growth as evidenced in Roberts et al. analysis [121].

Chinese regulations prioritize compliance with state objectives, exemplified by the Data Security Law⁶ and Personal Information Protection Law⁷, which focus on controlling data flows and *AI* applications affecting public security (see Filipova [55]). Unlike the European Union (EU), which emphasizes individual rights, or the United States of America (US), which prioritizes innovation, China's *AI* governance is deeply integrated with state surveillance and geopolitical strategies.

2.1.2 United States: A Market-Driven Approach

The United States lacks comprehensive federal legislation dedicated to *AI*. Instead, they rely on sector-specific laws and initiatives, such as the Algorithmic Accountability Act⁸ and guidelines from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)⁹. These efforts focus on voluntary standards rather than mandatory compliance, reflecting the U.S.'s market-driven approach (see Alic [3]). Moreover, US regulatory frameworks emphasize innovation and economic growth, favoring collaboration between the private sector and scholars. This contrasts with the EU's regulatory-heavy model. While the US has issued executive orders promoting *AI* leadership, its fragmented legal landscape poses challenges in addressing cross-sectoral *AI* risks (see Dixon [45]).

2.1.3 European Union: A Pioneering Regulatory Approach

The EU has positioned itself as a global leader in *AI* regulation, with its robust focus on ethics, explainability and accountability. The aforesaid EU's *AI* Act represents a significant attempt to create a harmonized framework, categorizing *AI* systems based on their risk levels and imposing stringent requirements on high-risk *AI* (see Bal & Gill [6]). This risk-based approach aligns with the EU's broader General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹⁰, ensuring data privacy and transparency in *AI* applications. The *AI* Act's emphasis on ethics stems from principles laid out in the EU Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy *AI*¹¹, prioritizing transparency, human oversight, and safety. For instance, *AI* systems used in healthcare or judicial decision-making are classified as high-risk, mandating rigorous compliance (see Pesapane et al. [112]).

In conclusion, the regulatory frameworks of the EU, U.S., and China reflect their unique socio-political priorities. While the EU leads in ethical and transparent *AI* governance, the U.S. emphasizes innovation, and China focuses on centralized control. These differences underscore the global challenge of harmonizing *AI* regulations, especially as cross-border *AI* applications grow. Collaboration between these regions could yield a more balanced and inclusive approach to *AI* governance. In Table 2.1 is reported a syntetic scheme to compare the three aforesaid approaches.

⁶http://www.npc.gov.cn/englishnpc/c2759/c23934/202112/t20211209_385109.html, accessed on January 2025

⁷http://en.npc.gov.cn.cdurl.cn/2021-12/29/c_694559.htm, accessed on January 2025

⁸<https://www.govtrack.us/congress/bills/118/s2892/text/is>, accessed on January 2025

⁹<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/ai/NIST.AI.100-5.pdf>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁰<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>, accessed on January 2025

¹¹<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>, accessed on January 2025

Table 2.1: Comparison of AI Regulatory Frameworks: EU, USA, and China

Aspect	European Union (EU)	United States (USA)	China
Regulatory Approach	Comprehensive, risk-based regulation (e.g., AI Act)	Sector-specific, market-driven with voluntary guidelines	Centralized, state-driven aligned with national priorities
Ethics and Accountability	Strong emphasis on ethics (e.g., Trustworthy AI Guidelines)	Ethical guidelines exist but lack binding force	Ethics integrated into state-controlled frameworks
Data Privacy	GDPR ensures strict data protection	Sector-specific privacy laws, no federal framework	Strict laws focused on state control and security (e.g., Data Security Law)
Innovation Regulation vs.	Balanced, regulatory oversight fosters trust in innovation	Innovation prioritized, limited regulatory intervention	Innovation driven by national strategies (e.g., 2030 AI Plan)
Key Legislation	AI Act, GDPR	Algorithmic accountability Act, NIST guidelines	Data Security Law, Personal Information Protection Law
Strengths	Global benchmark for ethical AI governance	Promotes rapid innovation and economic growth	Rapid implementation and alignment with national goals
Weaknesses	Regulatory delays and compliance costs	Fragmented legal framework, lack of overarching regulation	Overemphasis on control, limited focus on individual rights

2.2 Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Explainability in the area of Artificial Intelligence - or *XAI* - has its roots in the late 1970s, particularly in the development of expert systems, where the primary focus was on explaining behavior through applied rules (see Scott et al. [127]). With the advent of *Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)* [135] in the 2020s, explainability has taken on a critical role due to the opaque, black-box nature of these models (Lipton [86]). New explanatory tools have emerged to address these challenges, including post-hoc explanations, which elucidate how specific inference decisions are made, and transparency-by-design methods that aim to make models inherently interpretable. DARPA's *XAI* Program envisioned by Gunning [69], launched in 2017, serves as a modern milestone in the field, introducing innovative paradigms and framing explainability as a trade-off with prediction accuracy.

Traditional methods like LIME explanation approach (Ribeiro et al. [120]), SHAP to interpret model predictions (Lundberg and Lee [89]), and Saliency Maps (Simonyan et al.[131]) have set the groundwork for understanding complex models, while more recent innovations, such as Integrated

Gradients (Sundararajan et al. [134]) and counterfactual explanations (Wachter et al. [142]), offer new dimensions of interpretability. The field also splits into Data-driven or Perceptual *XAI*, which focuses on interpreting results from black-box models, and Goal-driven or Cognitive *XAI*, which explains systems by revealing their goals, intentions, and beliefs (Doshi-Velez and Kim [47]). Further advancements include domain-specific tools like Captum (Kokhlikyan et al. [79]), a library for PyTorch¹², and applications in high-stakes areas such as healthcare, autonomous systems, and climate science. Explainability in healthcare, for instance, has become vital for gaining clinicians' trust in diagnostic systems. *XAI* tools enable visualization of medical image models, highlighting areas critical to predictions, as seen in DeepSHAP implementations for radiology by Lundberg et al. [90]. In autonomous systems, transparency is necessary to ensure safety and public trust, prioritizing interpretable decision-making.

The challenges faced by *XAI* research continue to evolve. Scalability to large models, such as GPT-4 and other Generative AI systems, has introduced complexities in attributing decisions at different levels of abstraction. Fairness and bias mitigation remain pressing concerns, particularly in multi-stakeholder environments where competing values must be addressed. Furthermore, balancing explainability with performance remains a central theme. High-dimensional data pose additional challenges, necessitating approaches like concept-based explanations (see Yeh et al. [149]), which group features into human-interpretable clusters to facilitate understanding.

Applications of *XAI* are expanding rapidly across various fields. In climate science, *XAI* tools have been used to enhance interpretability in predictive models for extreme weather events (McGovern et al. [97]). Bioinformatics leverages *XAI* to understand gene expressions and disease pathways, as demonstrated in the use of neural networks to predict protein folding patterns. Fairness-aware AI applications, such as those in hiring and lending, deploy *XAI* to audit algorithms for biases, promoting ethical use. These examples highlight the versatility of *XAI* and its critical role in ensuring Responsible AI.

Regulatory frameworks, described in Section 2.1, are increasingly shaping the trajectory of *XAI*. The EU AI Act emphasizes transparency and accountability, mandating clear explanations for AI-driven decisions that impact individuals. This regulatory push has spurred innovation in explainability metrics and methodologies to meet compliance standards. The concept of interpretable AI is also gaining traction in academia, with interdisciplinary approaches that incorporate cognitive science and human-computer interaction to design user-centric explanations (see Miller [98]).

Emerging techniques in *XAI* include disentangled representations that separate latent variables into interpretable components, enhancing feature attribution and user trust. Counterfactual methods have seen significant development, offering actionable insights by generating alternative scenarios for decision outcomes. For example, in financial applications, counterfactuals can explain loan rejections by identifying minimal changes required for approval. In reinforcement learning, explainability frameworks elucidate the policies and rewards driving agents' decisions, as seen in Deep Q-Learning [53] interpretability efforts.

The integration of *XAI* into end-to-end systems is a promising frontier. Hybrid models that combine symbolic reasoning with neural networks aim to merge the interpretability of traditional AI with the flexibility of deep learning. This synthesis could pave the way for systems that are both powerful and transparent. For instance, neuro-symbolic AI approaches have shown potential

¹²<https://pytorch.org/>, accessed on January 2025

in logical reasoning tasks while maintaining explainability. Additionally, active research focuses on interactive explanations, where users can query models and receive dynamic, context-sensitive explanations, fostering deeper understanding and trust.

The increasing adoption of *XAI* in industry underscores its importance. Companies are leveraging *XAI* to improve customer satisfaction, compliance, and operational efficiency. For instance, explainability tools in recommendation systems provide transparency to users, enhancing trust and engagement. In the financial sector, *XAI*-driven risk assessment tools are gaining traction, ensuring that credit scoring models are interpretable and equitable. The integration of *XAI* into software development pipelines is also becoming more prevalent, with tools like What-If Tool enabling developers to explore model behaviors interactively.

In conclusion, the field of Explainable AI has made significant strides, from its early days in expert systems to addressing the challenges posed by modern black-box models. The proliferation of advanced methods, coupled with domain-specific applications and regulatory impetus, positions *XAI* as a cornerstone of Responsible AI development. However, ongoing challenges like scalability, fairness, and user-centered design will require continued innovation and collaboration across disciplines. By integrating explainability into every stage of the AI lifecycle, researchers and practitioners can ensure that AI systems are not only powerful but also transparent, trustworthy, and aligned with societal values.

2.3 Multi-agent Systems

MAS represent a critical field in *AI*, focusing on systems composed of multiple autonomous agents that interact to achieve goals beyond the capacity of individual entities. Early research activity explored problem-solving frameworks where agents shared partial solutions, evolving from the broader field of *Distributed Artificial Intelligence (DAI)* [109], which emerged in the late 1970s and beginning of 1980s as a means to address complex problems requiring decentralized solutions. Initially, *MAS* focused on distributed problem-solving, emphasizing collaboration among autonomous entities to achieve a unified goal. Over time, the paradigm matured into a robust integrated architecture emphasizing autonomy, interactivity, and distributed decision-making; examples include distributed control systems and early robotic coordination frameworks. The 1980s saw also advances in communication protocols, such as the *Contract Net Protocol (CNP)* developed by Smith [132], which laid a foundation for negotiation-based *MAS*. During the 1990s, the *BDI* model (See Section 1.4.1) became a cornerstone for agent-based reasoning; this model, rooted in philosophical logic, enabled agents to simulate human-like decision-making (see Rao and Georgeff [118]).

The technology underlying *MAS* is characterized by intelligent agents that are autonomous, reactive, and capable of learning and adaptation. Early aforesaid applications were confined to experimental simulations and theoretical modeling, but recent advancements have expanded *MAS*'s utility into fields such as robotics, industrial manufacturing, and decentralized networks. The integration of machine learning into *MAS* has further enhanced agents' ability to adapt and optimize behaviors dynamically, offering promising avenues for e-learning, manufacturing systems, and commerce (see Gawesha and Goonatilleke [60]). The contemporary *MAS* landscape spans diverse domains, including robotics, distributed systems, and social simulations. Core components and architectures of modern *MAS* are characterized by advances in agent communication, reasoning, and

cooperation. In particular, on the Inter-agent Communication area, standards like the Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents (FIPA)¹³ protocol have emerged to standardize *MAS* communication fostering interoperability across systems (see Wooldridge [146]).

An important field of application of *MAS* is Robotics, here it enables Swarm Intelligence, facilitating the coordination of multiple autonomous agents such as drones and ground robots. These systems excel in tasks like disaster management, autonomous vehicle coordination, and logistics. *MAS*'s ability to manage dynamic environments and coordinate among heterogeneous agents has been particularly impactful in real-world scenarios. Robotics remains a vital application domain for *MAS*, with specific focus areas including Swarms inspired by natural systems (e.g., ant colonies), that employ *MAS* for decentralized control and scalability (see Dorri et al. [46]). Also when coming to Human-Robot Interaction *MAS* are very important facilitating collaborative robots, or "cobots," in shared environments. Notable contributions include blockchain integration in robotic *MAS*, which enhances reliability and security. Afanasyev et al. [2]) provide an interesting classification of blockchain-based robotic systems.

Moreover, *MAS* is increasingly aligned with *DLT* and blockchain, where the need for secure, decentralized systems has grown. Blockchain enhances *MAS* by providing tamper-proof ledgers for interactions among agents, fostering trust in environments characterized by conflicting interests. Blockchain and *DLT* have emerged as transformative tools in *MAS*; in Decentralized Coordination are Blockchain enhances trust and transparency in operations among agents and between the system to the external environment. For example, Calvaresi et al. [15] conducted a systematic review showing blockchain's role in enabling tamper-proof records and consensus protocols. Also, in Fault Tolerance and Security area, Byzantine fault tolerance mechanisms, as explored by Salimpour et al. [125], utilize blockchain to enhance the resilience of *MAS* in adversarial settings. Recent work integrates AI techniques like *RL* into *MAS* for improved adaptive behaviors. For instance, Shen et al. [129] demonstrated Deep *RL*-driven coordination in collaborative multi-object tracking using the YOLOv3 method [143].

Despite its successes, *MAS* faces challenges, including scalability, real-time decision-making, and energy efficiency in blockchain-based applications. Research is exploring lightweight consensus algorithms and edge computing to address these limitations. Future trends indicate further integration of *MAS* with neuromorphic computing and bio-inspired models, promising unprecedented adaptability and efficiency.

2.4 Distributed Ledger Technologies

DLT, and its most famous declination Blockchain, are transformative technologies with roots tracing back to the foundational ideas of cryptographic security and distributed computing. Bitcoin, introduced in 2009 by the pseudonymous Satoshi Nakamoto [103], was the first successful application of blockchain as the underlying technology for peer-to-peer electronic cash (see Ramadoss [117]). Bitcoin's blockchain addressed the double-spending problem and introduced the concepts of decentralized consensus through *Proof of Work (PoW)* [77], cryptographic hashes, and immutable blocks. This innovation inspired further exploration into programmable blockchains, leading to Ethereum's launch in 2015 [14], which introduced smart contracts for Decentralized Applications

¹³<http://fipa.org/>, accessed on January 2025

(DApps). Concurrently, alternative DLT models like Hyperledger Fabric¹⁴ and R3 Corda¹⁵ emerged, catering to private and permissioned networks suitable for enterprise solutions (See Di Ciccio [42]).

Core features and innovations in *DLT* and Blockchain regards also the type of block concatenation and thus the structure of distributed database underling the network. Blockchain is a specific implementation of *DLT*, where records (blocks) are linked sequentially in a chain. The transparency, immutability, and decentralized control offered by this architecture have positioned it as a reliable solution for systems requiring trustless transactions. These features are achieved through cryptographic techniques and consensus protocols, with aforesaid *PoW* and *Proof of Stake (PoS)* [81] being among the most popular. Modern *DLT* solutions have though, expanded beyond blockchain to include Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), such as IOTA¹⁶, which optimize scalability and efficiency. These innovations address key challenges of early blockchain systems, including energy consumption and limited transaction throughput (see Gorbunova et al. [66]). *DLT*'s versatility has unlocked applications across diverse sectors. In finance, blockchain underpins cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin and Ethereum, Decentralized Finance (DeFi) platforms, and stablecoins. In supply chain management, its transparency ensures provenance and traceability, as exemplified by IBM's Food Trust¹⁷ network. Healthcare applications include secure sharing of medical records, and in eHealth, blockchain ensures privacy and consent management. *Internet of Things (IoT)* integration with blockchain offers a decentralized approach to data sharing and device coordination. For example, smart contracts enable autonomous operations in connected vehicles or energy grids. Furthermore, blockchain is central to the emerging Metaverse and *Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT)* markets, fostering digital ownership and economic incentives (see Tunio [139]). *DLT* is a high-potential paradigm, but faces challenges such as scalability, regulatory ambiguity, and interoperability. Early blockchain networks like Bitcoin and Ethereum suffer from high energy demands and transaction latency. Layer-2 scaling solutions, such as Lightning Network, and novel consensus mechanisms like *Proof of History (PoH)* by Solana (see Yakovenko [148]) are addressing these issues. Interoperability standards, such as Polkadot¹⁸ and Cosmos¹⁹, are emerging to enable seamless communication between disparate *DLT* networks. Regulatory frameworks remain fragmented, complicating adoption in regulated industries like finance and healthcare.

Future Directions of *DLT* and blockchain lie in the convergence of technologies. Hybrid blockchain architectures combining public and private features are gaining traction. Advances in quantum computing pose both threats and opportunities, pushing for the development of quantum-resistant cryptography. In decentralized finance, integration with traditional financial systems will foster greater adoption. Similarly, blockchain's role in global digital identity systems is expected to grow, providing individuals with sovereign control over their data. *AI* and *DLT* synergies are also anticipated, enabling intelligent autonomous systems.

In conclusion, from its inception with Bitcoin to its widespread adoption across industries, *DLT* and blockchain represent a paradigm shift in how systems manage trust, transparency, and decentralization. Ongoing research and innovation are addressing current limitations, ensuring their

¹⁴<https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/release-2.5/>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁵<https://r3.com/corda/>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁶<https://www.iota.org/>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁷<https://www.ibm.com/products/supply-chain-intelligence-suite/food-trust>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁸<https://polkadot.com/>, accessed on January 2025

¹⁹<https://cosmos.network/>, accessed on January 2025

relevance in the rapidly evolving digital landscape.

2.5 Decentralised Autonomous Organisations

A *DAOs* is a multi-criteria decision-making framework aimed at evaluating a set of alternatives to present a decision model to participants, facilitating consensus. It is a second-level paradigm that relies on Blockchain for the identification of participants, registration of transactions and voting resolutions, and internal tokenomics of the organization (Santana and Albareda [126]). In fact, *DAOs* are organizations governed entirely by computational algorithms implemented on smart contracts, which encode the rules of cooperation among participants.

The origins of the *DAOs* concept date back to the late 1990s when it was connected to the application of *MAS* in intelligent home sensors (see Liu et al. [87]). The first practical blockchain-based model, known as *Digital Autonomous Corporations (DACs)*, laid the groundwork for the modern *DAOs* (Lustenberger et al. [91]). The advent of Bitcoin's time-chain, which introduced a transparent and immutable ledger in 2009, followed by Ethereum in 2014, further advanced this concept by enabling asset tokenization and smart contracts (Li et al. [84]). In particular the article of Buterin "DAOs, DACs, DAs and more: An incomplete terminology guide." [13] is considered the origin of *DAOs* paradigm.

A milestone in *DAOs* development was the creation of the Aragon²⁰ platform in 2017, a project designed to provide tools for *DAOs* creation, governance, and dispute resolution. Aragon enables organizations to customize governance structures using templates and the ANT token, which powers its decentralized ecosystem. Its modular design allows *DAOs* to adapt to specific governance needs while offering scalability and security through Ethereum (Peña-Calvin et al. [110]) and Valiente et al. [141]). Aragon's unique contribution lies in its focus on empowering users with tools to set up *DAOs* with minimal technical expertise while maintaining flexibility for complex governance (Faqir-Rhazoui et al. [54]). *DAOs* inherit the defining features of blockchain: decentralization, security through asymmetric cryptography, and automated, incorruptible smart contracts. These characteristics enable them to facilitate governance processes independent of traditional regulatory frameworks, making them suitable for representing companies and complex organizations in a decentralized environment.

Historically, the *DAOs* ecosystem faced challenges with scalability, security, and governance. The infamous "The DAO" project in 2016 exposed vulnerabilities in *DAOs* architecture and management, leading to the infamous Ethereum hard fork (Dillon et al. [41]). Despite such setbacks, innovations like Aragon's modular architecture and tokenomics have significantly contributed to the resilience and expansion of the *DAOs* landscape (Mahmoud [93]).

To sum up, the common *DAOs* features that emerged from the literature analysis include the following core components:

- Smart Contracts: Self-executing code that automates processes and enforces rules.
- Consensus Protocols: Mechanisms such as *PoS* or *PoW* to validate decisions, inherited from underlying *DLT*.
- Non-fungible Tokens: Used for identification, governance, voting, and incentivization.

²⁰<https://www.aragon.org/>, accessed on January 2025

- Blockchain Infrastructure: Provides transparency and security.

By integrating these elements, *DAOs* achieve operational autonomy while maintaining trust and accountability. They are now applied across various sectors, including finance, education, and public governance, signalling a transformative shift toward decentralized systems (Ma et al. [92]).

In conclusion, the current state-of-the-art in the proposed research areas converges toward their integration, aiming to establish a coordinated framework that enhances trust and explainability in intelligent multi-agent systems and defines effective governance paradigms. An interesting example of this integration is the Ethical Technology and Holistic Oversight System (ETHOS) framework proposed by Chaffer et al. [20]. The authors envision the governance of intelligent agents through a decentralized approach, leveraging DAO and Web3 technologies such as smart contracts and tokens, with the goal of establishing a unified framework that promotes ethics, accountability, and dynamic risk classification.

Chapter 3

Theory Framework

In the previous sections we introduced some basic concepts regarding the nature of Cognitive Intelligence and Computational Agents to pave the ground for their use in design of Intelligent System, with the goal of integrating Explainability by design. In order to get such properties though, we need at first defining a common framework to model them and, most important, define an extension of the architecture to add the Explainability and its connected paradigms of Trust, Accountability and Transparency. In this section we will describe the theory that underlie the Computational Agent extending it with an Explainability layer, and will compose a framework of technologies and paradigms to model such extended agent.

3.1 The Multilayer Nature of Cognitive Computational Agents

We start recalling the concept of Computational Agent, defined in section 1.4: an entity "capable of perceiving its environment, processing information, making decisions, and taking actions autonomously or semi-autonomously to achieve specific goals. In doing this it emulates cognitive functions such as learning, reasoning, problem-solving, social ability and adaptation to external changes". So it is, to any extent, a Cognitive agent designed to emulate human-like cognition, able to engage in complex tasks by interacting with dynamic environments. These entities are thus an hybrid lying among *AI* and Cognitive Science research, connecting symbolic reasoning, embodied cognition, and dynamic decision-making.

Cognitive Computational agents, as just described, operate through a hierarchical architecture that enables both adaptive capacities, and autonomous behaviour. This structure includes historically three primary layers:

1. Peripheral Layer: an outer "skin" that interfaces both with the physical environment through sensors and actuators (eg. if we deal with robotic agents) and with software environments like other layers of the architecture or simulation programs primitives (eg. *MAS* simulators like MESA¹ or robotic simulators like CoppeliaSim²);
2. Control Layer: a middle-ware interpreter that manages feedbacks, produces perceptions, and controls internal systems. This is usually a pure software layer which translates outside phys-

¹<https://mesa.readthedocs.io/stable/>, accessed on January 2025

²<https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/>, accessed on January 2025

ical and non-physical signal into the agent "language", eventually doing some pre-elaboration (data aggregation, pruning, etc);

3. Decision-Making Layer: representing the "intelligent" part of the Agent, that evaluates perceptions, manages goals, and makes strategic decisions. In this layer will be inserted by design all the functionalities of intelligent paradigm that will be presented.

The aim of our work is to integrate, in this consolidated architecture, a fourth layer to foster *Explainability* and thus make the global Intelligent system both compliant to actual legislation and adoptable in a real-world use involving human beings. We can thus consider, referring to the idea presented in Figure 1.2 the following new layer:

4. Explainability Layer: a transversal module which integrates and orchestrates all the functions and resources needed to add Trust, Traceability, Accountability, and Transparency.

In the next paragraphs, we will examine deeper the functionalities of the presented layers to understand where and when the Explainability Module could intervene.

3.1.1 Peripheral Layer: The Interface to the Environment

The Peripheral layer handles interaction with the environment; sensors gather data about the external environment usually measuring physical quantities (eg. in case of embodied agents or robotics applications) but also electronic or software signals (eg. internal states controlling or dialouge with a simulation environment). Actuators on the other side, execute commands; here too we may have both peripheral acting physically on the environment (eg. robotic arms) or virtually (eg. software outputs to other modules). In any case both of these components are essential for monitoring progress and adjusting activities dynamically either in real-time or non real-time scenarios. Coming to the management of this layer we have two main areas of intervention:

- Sensors and Data Processing: Sensory systems collect raw environmental stimuli, converting them into structured perceptions. Efficient data aggregation and filtering are vital for maintaining responsiveness, especially in real-time applications. An interesting cognitive architecture for the acquisition of perceptions in Robotics is DAC-h3 presented by Moulin-Frier et al. [102].
- Actuators and Feedback: Actuators combine commands from the Decision-making and Control layers with feedback from sensors to modulate their actions. This feedback loop ensures the accuracy of complex movements, essential in robotic applications.

This layer acquires a relevant importance in fields such as Robotics and IoT sensors monitoring; here acquisition of data/perceptions form the environment and the actuation of Agents' reasoning results is of capital importance, especially in real-time scenarios.

3.1.2 Control Layer: Perception and Proprioception

The Control layer integrates data coming from sensors (or software modules in case of *MAS* and Simulation environments) into actionable insights, generating Perceptions and managing Proprioception, two important concepts that lay the foundation for the Agent Control paradigm.

Perception refers to the process of acquiring signals from sensors, interpreting them, and organizing them into intelligible information to understand the environment. This involves integrating data from various sensors to form a coherent representation of the external world, enabling the agent to make informed decisions and interact effectively with its surroundings. Perception is fundamental for tasks such as object recognition, navigation, and responding to environmental changes.

Proprioception, on the other hand, is the agent's ability to sense the position, movement, and orientation of its own body parts. This internal feedback mechanism allows the agent (in this case a Robot) to maintain balance, coordinate movements, and interact with objects accurately. In artificial systems, Proprioception is achieved through sensors that monitor joint angles, limb positions, and other internal states, facilitating self-awareness and adaptive behaviour.

This layer filters irrelevant stimuli, ensuring that only contextually significant data is processed (eg. Data filtering and Data pruning). Advanced middleware architectures facilitate real-time, parallel, and asynchronous communication, critical for distributed systems; in particular, there are the following techniques that are popular to increase the efficiency of Control layers:

- **Attention Mechanisms:** Simulating cognitive systems often requires attention models to prioritize relevant stimuli. These mechanisms improve computational efficiency and responsiveness in real-time scenarios.
- **Distributed Programming:** Distributed architectures enable scalability and fault tolerance, crucial for multi-agent systems operating in dynamic environments.

The aspects of this layer are very important when Cognitive Agents lie in Embodied AI; in particular, they are crucial for the development of embodied cognitive agents that can interact seamlessly with their environment. Research in this area has explored various approaches to model artificial body self-perception, including Bayesian estimation and deep learning techniques. For instance, Diez-Valencia et al. [43] discuss sensorimotor learning for artificial body perception, highlighting the potential of unsupervised or semi-supervised crossmodal learning approaches. Embodied AI also emphasizes the interaction between agents and their physical environments. Cognitive agents designed within this paradigm demonstrate the following characteristics as per Chrisley [21]:

- **Situated Perception:** Agents perceive their environments contextually, prioritizing relevant stimuli.
- **Dynamic Interaction:** Embodied agents adjust their actions in response to environmental feedback, improving adaptability.
- **Physical Realization:** Cognitive agents in robotics exemplify these principles, where sensors and actuators mediate their interactions with the real world.

An application of concepts described in this layer and of the one before is presented in Section 5.4.1 where the SkRobots framework is presented.

3.1.3 Decision-Making Layer: Strategic Planning and Learning

The Decision-making layer is where the intelligence of the Agent resides, it is responsible for analysing perceptions, managing goals, and generating strategic actions. It relies on a combination of rule-based reasoning, probabilistic models, and other AI techniques (eg. machine learning)

to adapt to changing conditions of the environment. This layer distinguishes between reactive and proactive behaviour, yielding the correspondent agents categories:

- **Reactive Agents:** These agents execute predefined actions in response to stimuli, suitable for simple tasks but prone to errors in complex scenarios.
- **Proactive Agents:** Proactive systems analyze information, apply contextual knowledge, and leverage past experiences to make autonomous decisions.

The separation between these two behaviours is not always clear and definite, in fact, often they are present in a mixture; both in the sense of having proactive and reactive agents in the same systems and of the agent that may have proactive and reactive behaviour depending on the type of perception.

The Decision-making layer is, in our opinion, the most important one. Here the cognitive intelligent properties of the agent must be described and enforced in the design of the Computational Cognitive Agent structure. It is of capital importance to define flexible instruments and techniques that can, on one side model the "mind" of the agent and on the other side define the limitations and the constraints to which the system must submit. In the next sections, we'll analyse more in detail what paradigms are, in our opinion, a good mix to obtain such goals creating an innovating mix to foster "intelligence" in Computational Agents. In particular, we'll examine how to implement Reasoning and Production rules through Logic Programming in Section 3.2 and how to define Constraints in Section 3.3 with the aid of Propositional Logic.

3.1.4 Explainability Layer

One innovative idea that we want to offer with this work is to enrich the framework creating new techniques to add Explainability in Cognitive agents. Thus we need to model a new layer, integrated with classic ones just described below, that may take care of all the aspects involved in this complex function. The first activity to do is to define the main functions that this layer must have, in order to get the goals of adding Trust, Accountability, Transparency and all the relevant properties an explainable intelligent system requires. The recurring idea is that some features of interest and selected data need to be in some way saved, both to answer potential questions from external entities (eg. a human in the loop trying to reconstruct a malfunction) and to produce spontaneous explanation of the system's decisions. So let's examine some valuable points the Explainability layer should have in performing this process:

- **Access to perceptions:** this aspect is connected with how the Agent perceives the real world, raw data coming from sensors are elaborated and perceived. The system must be able to say what "in his opinion" a physical measurement or an acquired image "means"; for example to check if an error is caused by a misinterpretation of such measure or image.
- **Access to proprioceptions:** very important is also to explain, especially in embodied AI and Robotics, if the perception of its body is correct. We may move a robotic arm too close or too far and create problems in particular if interacting with a human being; and again can be important to be able to reconstruct a malfunction of a system and understand what didn't work.

- Access to actions, reactive and proactive functions: coming to a higher level of abstraction, the capability to explain how data percept from the environment are reasoned on and what decisions are taken and actuated is probably the most important feature of the entire system. In doing this, the explainability layer must have access to all programs and coding implemented in the intelligent part of the agent, as well as to the information transiting in there.
- Capability of saving and retrieving information: track changes of relevant parameters and actions, save them in a safe way and retrieve them quickly is another requirement an explainable system must have. This ensures a high availability of explanations possibly fostering an on-request service, very valuable for real-time applications.
- Guarantee immutability and referencing of data: guarantee that data, actions, messages, and in general all decisional processes cannot be counterfeited. Once a decision is taken or a message has been sent, for example, there should be no way to alter it. Also timestamping of such events should be immutably registered. Being capable of demonstrating what decision and when was taken is of capital importance.
- Communicate explanations: last but not least is important also make information on explainability available and readable in an interpretable format. This could be both in relation to other Agents (eg. robots in a Swarm requesting some kind of information to other robots) and to human beings controlling intelligent systems in the loop.

As a consequence of the above analysis, the Explainability layer should interact closely both with the Decision-making level and with the Control one. The Peripheral layer, which function remains important in the architecture, will not be considered for the extent of our work as bond to the specific implementation rather than to the general context we aim for explainability. In table 3.1 we report a synthetic prospect of properties, layers, and functionalities to foster aforesaid features.

3.2 Production Rules, Reasoning and Logic Programming Languages

Let's start examine what tools and paradigms can we use to implement the functionalities of the Decision-making Layer. This is where the intelligence lies in the Computational Cognitive Agent entity and thus is where Explainability should integrate mainly and build its foundations. We aim to have some writing tools to add reasoning capabilities to the Agent. The first paradigm we consider to describe such integration are production Rules

3.2.1 Production Rules

Production rules serve as a foundational concept in Cognitive science and *AI*, particularly in modelling the behaviour and decision-making processes of cognitive agents. The framework of production rules has been widely adopted due to its simplicity, modularity, and alignment with how humans are theorized to process and act on knowledge. These rules, which typically follow an "if-then" structure, represent the procedural knowledge that governs an agent's responses to specific conditions.

```
if <condition> then <action_1> else <action_2>
```

Listing 3.1: General production rule example

Table 3.1: Summary of Computational Agent Layers with Properties and Technologies

Layer	Properties Required	Candidate Technologies
Peripheral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors and Data Processing • Actuators and Feedback • Environment interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT devices • Sensors (e.g., cameras, microphones, LIDAR) • Actuators (e.g., engines, arms)
Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time response where required • Feedback mechanisms • Perception and Proprioception implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attention Mechanisms (Data filtering, Pruning, etc.) • Distributed Programming (Edge systems) • Real-time operating systems (RTOS, SkRobots5.4.1)
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level strategy • Context-aware planning • Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Rules and Reasoning • Constraints Knowledge Base • Reinforcement Learning
Explainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency • Interpretability • Trust-building • Immutability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explainable AI (XAI) frameworks • Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and Blockchain • Distributed Autonomous Organisations (DAO) • Natural Language Processing (NLP)

This format enables agents to respond dynamically to specific inputs or environmental states. Conditions often include logical statements or sensory data evaluations, while actions correspond to changes in the agent’s state or operations executed on the environment. For instance, an agent in a pasta cooking task might use the rule:

```
t = read(temperature_sensor)
water_is_boiling = (t >= 100)
if water_is_boiling then pasta_in_pot else wait
```

Listing 3.2: Pasta cooking rule example

This declarative format of Production Rules makes it easier to design systems where rules can be added, modified, or removed without altering the underlying framework.

The origins of production rules in cognitive modeling can be traced back to early cognitive architectures such as the *General Problem Solver (GPS)* by Newell and Simon [107], [105]. *GPS* utilized production systems to simulate human problem-solving by encoding strategies as condition-action pairs. This early work laid the groundwork for subsequent cognitive architectures like *Adaptive Control of Thought-Rational (ACT-R)* and *Soar*, which have played a pivotal role in advancing the understanding of human cognition and reasoning.

- *ACT-R* Framework: developed by John R. Anderson, is one of the most influential cognitive architectures employing production rules. In *ACT-R*, production rules interact with declarative memory to model complex cognitive tasks such as language comprehension, decision-making, and learning. For example, studies have shown how *ACT-R* can simulate the Stroop effect³ by using production rules to handle the conflict between reading a word and naming its ink color (Anderson et al. [5]). The architecture’s emphasis on modularity and correspondence with brain regions provides a biologically plausible model of cognition (Anderson et al. [4])
- *Soar* Cognitive Architecture: initially envisioned by Allen Newell, represents another milestone in the application of production systems. It emphasizes the integration of learning, problem-solving, and reasoning within a single framework. *Soar* employs chunking—a mechanism for learning new production rules from problem-solving episodes—to enable cognitive agents to acquire and refine their knowledge over time (Laird et al. [80]).

3.2.2 Reasoning

Reasoning in cognitive agents represents a critical aspect of *AI* and Cognitive science, enabling these systems to simulate human-like problem-solving, decision-making, and adaptability. Cognitive agents are designed to perceive their environments, process information, and take actions based on their understanding and goals. Reasoning serves as the bridge between perception and action, allowing agents to derive conclusions, make informed decisions, and plan effectively.

The process of reasoning is typically rooted in structured frameworks such as logic-based systems, production rules, and probabilistic models. These frameworks empower agents to process complex inputs, evaluate multiple possibilities, and adapt to changing contexts. Unlike simple rule-based systems, cognitive agents aim to exhibit higher-level intelligence, characterized by adaptability, learning, and self-reflection.

³https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Stroop_effect, accessed on January 2025

The study of reasoning in cognitive agents draws inspiration from multiple disciplines, including psychology, neuroscience, and computer science. Production rules facilitate various types of reasoning processes, including:

- **Deductive Reasoning:** Using logical rules to derive conclusions from known premises. For instance, a cognitive agent might apply the rule "If the weather forecast predicts rain, then take an umbrella" to prepare for a rainy day. Deductive reasoning ensures that the conclusions drawn are logically valid if the premises are true. This type of reasoning is central to tasks such as verifying mathematical proofs or determining the eligibility of a loan applicant based on strict criteria.
- **Inductive Reasoning:** Deriving generalized rules from specific observations. For example, an AI observing that "customers often purchase pasta when buying tomato sauce" might formulate a rule to suggest pasta when tomato sauce is added to a shopping cart. Inductive reasoning is widely applied in machine learning, where systems generalize patterns from data to predict future outcomes or recommend actions.
- **Abductive Reasoning:** Inferring the most likely explanation for a set of observations. A medical diagnosis system might use the rule "If a patient exhibits symptoms X, Y, and Z, then the probable condition is A" to suggest possible illnesses. Although abductive reasoning does not ensure accurate conclusions, it is valuable for formulating plausible hypotheses in situations marked by uncertainty or incomplete information.
- **Analogical Reasoning:** Drawing parallels between similar situations to infer solutions. For instance, an educational tutor system might use the rule "If a student struggled with concept A and required hint B, then provide hint B for similar difficulties with concept C." Analogical reasoning helps in transferring knowledge across domains.
- **Hierarchical Reasoning:** Breaking down complex problems into subproblems, each governed by specific rules. In robotics, for instance, navigation might involve rules at multiple levels: "If the path is blocked, then replan the route" at a high level and "If the obstacle is detected within 2 meters, then slow down" at a lower level. This hierarchical approach enables agents to handle complex tasks systematically.

3.2.3 Logic Programming Languages

Logic programming languages such as Datalog [19], *Answer Set Programming (ASP)* [85], and Prolog, introduced by Alain Colmerauer and Robert Kowalski in the early 1970s (see Colmerauer [27]), have long been recognized as powerful tools for *AI*. Their declarative nature allows developers to specify what the system should achieve rather than how to achieve it, enabling the concise representation of knowledge and reasoning processes. In Cognitive AI, logic programming serves as an effective means to model high-level reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making.

Logic programming is rooted in formal logic, particularly predicate logic, it allows the representation of facts, rules, and queries in a format amenable to automated reasoning. The key feature of logic programming languages is their reliance on logical inference mechanisms, such as unification and resolution, to derive conclusions. Prolog remains the archetypal logic programming language,

its success is largely due to its simplicity and its use of backtracking and depth-first search for efficient problem-solving. It has many derived languages specific for subdomains, one of this, DALI [30] is of particular interest for our architecture as is meant to manage events happening in the environment dynamically. In Section 4.5.1 we will analyse deeper this language. Logic Programming Languages have some common characteristics that we briefly summarize in the next points:

1. Declarative Syntax: Logic programming languages focus on defining the relationships between entities using facts and rules. For example, the Prolog statement for the deductive reasoning on weather forecast example of previous section can take the form:

```
% Rule: If the weather forecast predicts rain, then take an umbrella.
take_umbrella :- forecast(rain).

% Example fact: The weather forecast predicts rain.
forecast(rain).
```

Listing 3.3: Prolog example of a deductive rule.

the program declares that if the fact "weather forecast predicts rain" the deductive rule will be "take an umbrella".

2. Automatic Reasoning: Logic programming systems inherently support reasoning through mechanisms like forward chaining and backward chaining. These processes enable systems to derive conclusions - such as determining relationships in family trees or solving logical puzzles - from given *Knowledge Base (KB)*, or a set of facts know as true.
3. Non-determinism: The ability to explore multiple potential solutions simultaneously makes logic programming suitable for tasks requiring flexibility, such as planning or hypothesis generation.

Applications of Logic programming languages have been applied across various domains within Cognitive AI:

1. Knowledge Representation and Reasoning: Logic programming is particularly suited for representing complex knowledge structures. Systems like Cyc, which aim to model common-sense reasoning, rely heavily on logical inference (Lenat, [83]). Prolog's capability to express hierarchical and relational knowledge has made it a staple for developing ontologies and reasoning engines.
2. Natural Language Processing (NLP): Prolog and similar languages have been instrumental in *NLP* tasks, such as parsing and semantic analysis. The Definite Clause Grammar (DCG) formalism in Prolog provides an elegant way to represent linguistic grammars, enabling efficient parsing and sentence generation (Pereira and Warren [111]).
3. Planning and Decision-Making: Planning tasks, such as robot navigation, benefit from the declarative nature of logic programming. Systems like Stanford Research Institute Problem Solver (STRIPS) and its derivatives use logical representations to model states, actions, and goals. *NLP*, a more recent development in logic programming, excels in planning and combinatorial problem-solving due to its capacity to handle constraints and optimization tasks (Gelfond and Lifschitz [62]).

4. Cognitive Modeling: Cognitive architectures like aforesaid *ACT-R* and Soar often integrate logic programming techniques to model human reasoning. For example, logical rules can encode decision-making processes or simulate problem-solving strategies.

Advances in Logic Programming are mainly due to the evolution of programming languages, they have addressed some of their early limitations, enhancing their applicability to cognitive AI:

- Constraint Logic Programming (CLP): CLP extends traditional logic programming by incorporating constraints into the reasoning process. This allows for efficient handling of numerical problems, such as scheduling and resource allocation (Jaffar and Lassez [76]).
- Probabilistic Logic Programming: Probabilistic extensions, such as ProbLog and P-log, integrate uncertainty into logic programming. These languages are valuable for cognitive AI applications involving incomplete or noisy data, such as diagnostic reasoning (De Raedt et al. [40]).
- Parallelism and Efficiency: Modern implementations of logic programming, such as SWI-Prolog and *ASP* solvers like Clingo, leverage advances in parallel computing and optimization to handle large-scale problems efficiently (Gebser et al. [61]).

Challenges in Logic Programming for Cognitive AI, despite its strengths, are numerous:

- Expressivity vs. Efficiency: Balancing the expressiveness of logic programming languages with computational efficiency remains a significant challenge. Highly expressive systems can become intractable for large problem domains.
- Integration with Machine Learning: While logic programming excels at symbolic reasoning, it struggles to handle the subsymbolic data typically processed by machine learning models.
- Knowledge Acquisition: Building comprehensive knowledge bases for logic programming systems is labor-intensive, often requiring domain experts.

Logic programming languages play a critical role in cognitive AI, offering powerful tools for modeling reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making. Their declarative syntax, automatic reasoning capabilities, and adaptability to diverse applications make them invaluable for advancing our understanding of intelligence. As research continues to address existing challenges and integrate logic programming with emerging technologies, its impact on cognitive AI is poised to grow further.

3.3 Knowledge Base through Constraints Definition

A *Constraints Knowledge Base (CKB)* is a formalized system designed to store, manage, and reason about constraints, conditions or restrictions that define relationships between variables. Using logic predicates as a foundation, *CKB* leverage the expressive power of formal logic to encode these relationships in a declarative manner, enabling efficient problem-solving across domains such as scheduling, optimization, and artificial intelligence. Logic predicates, which are fundamental constructs in propositional and first-order logic, provide a means to represent constraints as logical statements. For example, a constraint "X must be greater than Y" can be encoded as a predicate

$greater(X, Y)$, while domain restrictions such as $X \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ can be represented as the predicate $domain(X, \{1, 2, 3\})$. These predicates serve as building blocks to represent complex constraints and dependencies systematically; in this case the constraints may take the form of systems of constraints expressed always with formal logic notation. For example we may want to define that the possible n states S of the Agent A are:

$$S_A = \{S_0, S_1, \dots, S_n\}$$

and want to specify that the Agent can have just one state at each given time t . We can, at this point, formalise the following expressions for each value of the state variable:

$$S_A^t(0) \Leftarrow S_0 \wedge \neg S_1 \wedge \neg S_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg S_n$$

$$S_A^t(1) \Leftarrow \neg S_0 \wedge S_1 \wedge \neg S_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \neg S_n$$

...

$$S_A^t(n) \Leftarrow \neg S_0 \wedge \neg S_1 \wedge \neg S_2 \dots \wedge S_n$$

The KB constraint can be, at this point, defined as follows:

$$true \Leftarrow S_A^t(0) \vee S_A^t(1) \dots \vee S_A^t(n) \forall t$$

By organizing constraints in a KB , systems can perform logical inference to deduce new relationships or validate existing configurations. This inference often relies on constraint satisfaction techniques, which determine whether a set of constraints can be satisfied simultaneously. Advanced implementations integrate constraint propagation, where local changes to variables trigger the re-evaluation of affected predicates, ensuring consistency throughout the knowledge base. Furthermore, CKB enable modularity, reusability, and scalability by allowing the definition of reusable predicate templates, hierarchical constraint structures, and dynamic updating of knowledge as new data becomes available.

The use of logic predicates in CKB also enhances transparency and interpretability, as the declarative nature of logic allows users to understand the rationale behind constraint definitions and solutions. This capability is particularly beneficial in fields such as software verification, resource allocation, and automated reasoning, where correctness and traceability are critical. Thus, the integration of logic predicates in CKB represents a powerful approach to capturing and solving constraint-based problems with precision and flexibility.

3.4 Operational Instruments for Explainability

The innovative architecture envisioned in the previous sections require to define a new approach to software architecture able to integrate heterogeneous systems born in different context and for other purposes. The most important paradigm to model is, in our opinion, the Accountability one. Making an agent accountable means incorporate in its architecture the ability to take responsibility for its actions, decisions, and behaviors within a defined ethical, social, and operational framework.

It involves mechanisms to ensure that the system operates transparently, predictably, and reliably while providing explanations, justifications, and the means for external oversight. Accountability is thus a first order property of the Agent, in the sense that is a direct embodied peculiarity of the system.

The paradigm we propose to get such accountable Agent is *DLT*, already briefly introduced in Section 2.4. Let's examine a bit deeper the properties of *DLT* and Blockchain in relation to our needs. They are ultimately distributed databases where pieces of information are connected to form a chain (or other structures) where each block is timestamped and digitally signed through and hash. In this way a corrupted information would be easily spot having a different hash from the expected one. For our architecture we consider the *Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM)*, this is a quasi-Turing-complete computational framework that runs smart contracts on the Ethereum blockchain. Being quasi-Turing-complete [72] means that the *EVM* can execute any computational logic, or program, given enough resources (is not complete due to gas required to perform transactions on Ethereum network, this limit the number of operation that can be required to the machine). In the Blockchain environment, programs and logic instructions are implemented through Smart Contracts; they are self-executing pieces of code stored on the network, designed to automatically enforce predefined agreements without the need for intermediaries. The transactions happening within the Smart Contract are registered on the blockchain; and both the drafter of the contract and the parties involved are identified by the wallet used to access the network, while transactions are digitally signed through the private key connected to each wallet and timestamped. The activation of the Smart Contract come at a cost (gas fee) to pay validators node activity in transactions certification.

The Ethereum paradigm, leverages the *PoS* consensus protocol (See Larimer [81]) for certification of transactions, that requires a demonstration of owning a determined amount of digital assets. Another important functions of *DLT* is the capability of exchanging digital assets among nodes participating in the network. This is obtained by tokens, a digital asset that can be minted, exchanged and burned using Smart Contracts. Tokens can be described as a two-layer object: the first one contains peculiar features like ownership and proof of authenticity, and the second one represents the functionality of the token. We have two main categories of tokens:

- *Fungible Tokens (FT)*, which can transfer value among parties. *FTs* are interchangeable digital assets, like cryptocurrencies (e.g., ETH, USDT), used for payments, utility, or governance in *Distributed Applications (Dapps)*;
- *NFT*, which represent ownership rights on some assets. They can represent also a unique digital asset, such as an image, a document, or a virtual good, enabling proof of ownership and provenance. They are widely used in gaming, collectibles, and digital identity management.

Other key functionalities that are very important to foster Accountability are :

- **Timestamping:** Blockchain inherently records the exact time of every transaction or data entry, creating a reliable chronological record that can be used for audits, certifications, or historical documentation.
- **Immutability of Transactions:** Once data is added to the blockchain, it cannot be altered without consensus from the network. This immutability ensures security, trust, and transparency, making the blockchain a reliable source of truth.

By combining these functionalities, blockchain has become a cornerstone of decentralized systems, driving innovation across industries from finance to supply chain and beyond.

A second instrument we need is a second level technology based on *FT: DAOs*. Here we switch to the external world of the Agent and in particular to the implementation of the Social Ability paradigm he must have to deal with other agents (both human and non human). *DAOs* represents a new organisational model built on Blockchain technology and implementing a specialisation of *Dapps*. They rely upon a community where participants interact directly, and decisions are made through automated rules encoded in Smart Contracts on a Blockchain network. This eliminates centralised leadership and fosters a more transparent and democratic approach. *DAOs* inherit by nature core features from *DLT*, such as decentralised control, robust security through cryptographic keys, and the ability for smart contracts to self-execute code autonomously. The rise of powerful digital platforms and advancements in *DLT* architectures are fuelling interest in *DAOs*. A key element of *DAOs* philosophy is its governance structure. Decisions within the organisation are made through token-based voting. Each participant has a token amount proportional to their contribution or involvement in the organisation. This system allows for more direct decision-making, where important resolutions, such as changes to by-laws or allocation of resources, are made by the majority of participants (or weighted votes).

The third paradigm of interest focuses on the external behaviour of agents and their social capabilities, encapsulated in the concept of *MAS*. They provide a robust framework for modelling and simulating complex, decentralized architectures where human and non-human actors pursue their objectives in cooperative, competitive, or hybrid interactions. These systems serve as a natural platform for deploying distributed architectures, enabling autonomous agents— independent software entities—to interact dynamically with each other and their environment. *MAS* are particularly relevant in contexts requiring flexibility, scalability, and resilience, such as swarm robotics, supply chain optimization, and distributed energy systems.

From our perspective, coupling *MAS* with *DAOs* adds a layer of governance and decision-making transparency. Through *DAOs*, participants can collectively vote on resolutions affecting the *MAS*, such as introducing new agents or determining the strategic direction in swarm robotics. This synergy ensures that individual agent decisions align with the collective goals of the system, promoting accountability. *DAOs*, implemented through smart contracts on blockchain technology, enhance *MAS* by leveraging *DLT* properties like data immutability, transparency, and traceability. These properties ensure secure and verifiable decision-making processes, mitigating issues of trust and centralization. For example, in swarm robotics, *MAS* coupled with *DAOs* can facilitate decentralized coordination where participants vote on environmental strategies, enabling adaptive behaviours while maintaining a transparent operational history. This convergence of *MAS* and blockchain technology represents a transformative approach, empowering autonomous systems with robust governance frameworks, decentralized control, and enhanced reliability, vital for applications in critical domains like healthcare, logistics, and autonomous vehicles.

Finally a fourth paradigm of interest are frameworks to make machine learning models more interpretable by extracting symbolic knowledge from sub-symbolic predictors (e.g., neural networks, random forests). An example of such instruments is PSyKE, an innovative Python library designed for this purpose and described in Sabbatini et al. [123]. The knowledge is expressed in the form of human-readable logic rules or symbolic representations, enabling users to understand and trust com-

plex machine learning decisions. At its core, PSyKE introduces the concept of an Extractor, which acts as a bridge between sub-symbolic models (such as neural networks) and symbolic reasoning systems. Here's a detailed breakdown of its architecture (Core Components of an Extractor):

1. **Predictor as Oracle:** The trained machine learning model serves as the "oracle," answering questions about the input-output relationship. This means the predictor is used to provide predictions for synthetic or real data to guide the rule extraction process.
2. **Feature Descriptors:** These are abstractions of the input space, which help in interpreting the model's decision boundaries and in generating human-readable rules.
3. **Rule Extraction:** Rules are derived by analyzing the predictor's behavior on a set of data samples, whether real or synthetic. The extracted rules aim to maintain fidelity to the predictor while being simpler and interpretable.

The main functions of the architecture are (i) Extract and (ii) Predict. the first one produces a logic theory, which is a set of rules or symbolic representations derived from the predictor. These rules can be used in decision-making pipelines, auditing, and debugging. The second one uses the extracted rules to make predictions, offering an interpretable surrogate to the original model. The output formats of the systems are (i) Prolog theories or rules expressed as Horn clauses, which are fundamental components in logic programming; and (ii) *Ontology Web Languages (OWL)* with *Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL)* rules for applications in semantic reasoning [73]. PSyKE supports a diverse set of algorithms, each tailored to different tasks and model types:

1. **CART (Classification and Regression Trees):** Constructs decision trees that inherently generate rules from the splits in the feature space. The output rules are a direct translation of the decision tree structure [138].
2. **Classification Algorithms like REAL (Rule Extraction As Learning)** that generates rules starting from dataset samples and applies generalization techniques to combine similar patterns into more compact rules; or **Trepan** that Builds a decision tree by querying the model for predictions on synthetic samples.
3. **Regression Algorithms as ITER (Iterative Rule Extraction)** [74] which constructs hypercubes in the input space, where each cube represents a region with a constant predicted output and iteratively expands these cubes to cover the input space. It can be extended with **GridEx (Grid-based Rule Extraction)** [124] by optimizing hypercube generation to produce shorter, more generalized rule sets. Another extension is **GridREx (Grid-based Regression Rule Extraction)** which enhances GridEx by allowing each hypercube's output to be a linear combination of the input features. Furthermore optimization Algorithm like **PEDRO** automates the tuning of hyper-parameters for GridEx and GridREx algorithms, ensuring higher accuracy and shorter rule lists.

By focusing on making black-box models interpretable, PSyKE provides a powerful toolkit for deploying transparent and trustworthy AI systems in critical domains. It also can foster Integration with Advanced Reasoning Systems for a Broader compatibility with semantic web technologies and reasoning engines.

3.5 Explainable Computational Agents

Once we have defined the theoretical instruments required to foster intelligence in the Computational Cognitive Agent, we need to add the Explainability modules, situating them in the multilayer classic architecture and define the interactions among them, in respect both to the environment and other layers and paradigms involved. In Figure 3.1 we present a graphical representation of the Cognitive Explainable Computational Agent; the explainability paradigms, worth to note, are in some way embodied among the other layers. Starting from discussing the nature of the single Agent, the idea

Figure 3.1: Explainable Computational Agent architecture

is to track and save in an immutable way all the actions (or a relevant part of them) and messages happening through modules in the agents and between the agent and the environment. The second idea is to register the logic behind the intelligent layers, Decision-making and Control, in a way that is publicly readable by interested parties and immutable unless the authorized owner change it, and changes are trackable. Also time-stamping of all these activities should be available. It's also interesting to model the situation where there are more than one agent composing the Intelligent System. Here we need both an environment that can make agents interact, exchanging messages and other relevant information, and a system capable of make transparent all the decision taken by the agents and communicate them at request to a potential human controller. Let's analyse the architecture depicted in the diagram, specifying a breakdown of the components and their roles:

1. Peripheral Layer

- **Functionality:** Acts as the sensory input/output system of the agent, reading the stimuli from the Environment and performing Actions on the environment through its actu-

ators (in case of robotic agents) or software primitives. In our architecture has a minor weight as does not interact with DLT and other technologies.

- Inputs:
 - Stimuli: Environmental data captured via sensors
 - Proprioceptions: Internal state sensing (e.g., self-awareness, balance) from Control Layer must be transformed into Actions on the Environment.
- Outputs:
 - Actions: Transmits actions to the environment based on decisions.
 - Perceptions: Environmental data captured via sensors or external stimuli are elaborated and sent as metadata to the Control Layer.

2. Control Layer

- Functionality: Serves as the processing hub middleware that interprets Perceptions and manages Proprioceptions at an high level of functionalities.
- Processes:
 - Receives Perceptions and Proprioceptions.
 - Provides Interpretations to the Decision Making Layer.
 - Receives decisions and translates them into actions for the Peripheral Layer.
 - Provides Perceptions, Proprioceptions and Interpretations to the module for Rules Extractions of the Explainability Layer. This is an important function to feed data for extracting symbolic knowledge from sub-symbolic predictors.

3. Decision Making Layer

- Functionality: it is the most important layer of the architecture where intelligence of the Agent reside. In our configuration is modelled through two components: Production Rules and *CKB*. As innovative enhancement this layer integrates with *DLT*, saving on the ledger both programmes present on each module and results (decisions taken, results of logic predicates evaluation, etc.).
- Core Components:
 - Production Rules: Encodes actionable knowledge in the form of “if-then” logic for decision-making. Here we store and run Logic programs that can be implemented, to name a few, in Prolog, DALI, and Qulog/TeleoR along with (or integrated in) high-level languages programs (eg. Python).
 - *CKB*: Stores rules and constraints that guide or restrict decisions. As said early in this section we may use formal logic predicates that may be as well integrated in high-level languages programs through specific libraries.
- Outputs:
 - Elaborates constraints, propositions, and rules for action giving life to the intelligent prerogatives of the Agent.

- Integrates with the *DLT* layer for verification and immutability. Programs can be stored as Smart Contracts and *NFT* documents on the ledger while results and communication as signed and timestamped transactions between Smart Contracts.

4. Explainability Layer

- Purpose: Adds Interpretability and Transparency to the agent's decisions and actions, fostering thus Trust and Explainability to the whole system. This is the layer that orchestrate the classic function and layers of Computational Agents integrating them with the innovative paradigms of *MAS*, *DAOs* and *DLT*. This layers takes also care of presenting results in an intelligible way to potential humans in the loop.
- Modules:
 - Interpretability: Ensures decisions can be explained in human-understandable terms. This include presenting the data in a easy and immediate way (eg. well architected Graphical User Interfaces GUIs) but also avoiding to overwhelm human user with data (eg. data pruning and aggregation). Also presentation prediction of results is an important function of this module.
 - Social Ability - *MAS*: Enables interaction with other agents, facilitating cooperation or negotiation. In real world applications often scenarios requires many agents interacting among them and environment. Here eventual primitives to manage multi-agent frameworks (eg. aforesaid MESA) must be addressed.
 - Rules Extraction and Features Description: Analyzes and extracts knowledge for further use in the Prediction module. This happens, as said before, through production of a set of rules or symbolic representations of data coming from the Control Layer.
 - Prediction: Utilizes predictive modelling to anticipate outcomes and refine decisions. Here we have the production of Horn clauses and *OWL* (eg. using the aforesaid PSyKE and its featured classification algorithms).
 - *DAOs* Management: Handles autonomous governance and decision-making processes. Here every aspect of the integration with *DAOs* primitives is managed, included identification (eg. Agent is connected with a wallet on the blockchain for signing transaction and smart contract activation), voting for resolutions that influence the *MAS*.
 - *DLT* Management: Manages distributed ledger interactions to ensure secure and immutable data storage. This module orchestrate all the functions need to register and log the lifecycle of the agent and thus of the system.

5. *DLT*

- Role: The *DLT* network must ensure transparency, accountability, and immutability. The type of network must be done in order to optimize the use required; for non real time application Blockchain on public networks can be a good solution. In case of time being a factor *DLT* (eg. *Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs)* Tangles) on private networks offer faster environments.

- Functionalities:
 - Records timestamps and decisions for traceability.
 - Registers actions and creates/manages *NFT* for unique identifiers.
 - Offers Smart Contracts capabilities for automation of intelligent programs and governance in combination with *DAOs*.

6. Smart Contracts

- Purpose: Automates processes and ensures compliance with predefined rules. The execution of an agreed contract without possibility of modification fosters Trust, furthermore Smart Contracts are on a public network that is inspectable through explorers bringing Transparency (eg. verifying who activated a contract or minted an *NFT*)
- Functions:
 - Enforces the execution of programs, logic rules and knowledge base constraints.
 - Manages interactions and updates between the agent and external systems.
 - Ensures the validity and transparency of decisions based on the constraints from the Decision Making Layer.

7. Environment

- Purpose: Acts as the external domain where the agent operates and interacts with other agents, as well as with physical factors. Worth to note that humans in the loop are part of the environment.
- Inputs to the Agent: Perceptions, proprioceptions, and stimuli.
- Outputs from the Agent: Actions on the physical or software world and explanations for human in the loop.

Finally we can resume the key functional relationships emerging from our innovative architecture:

- Explainability and Accountability: Achieved through the *Explainability Layer* and integration with *DLT* for immutable decision recording.
- Autonomy and Trust: Managed through the Decision Making Layer, leveraging production rules and predictive modelling.
- Inter-Agent Interaction: Facilitated by the Social Ability module within the Explainability Layer and the Smart Contracts layer for trustless coordination.

Chapter 4

Methods to Implement Explainable Computational Agents

In the previous sections we introduced the architecture of the Explainable Computational Agent discussing theoretical instruments and paradigms used in each layer and module of the system. We also introduced a three-leg architecture composed by *MAS*, *DAOs* and *DLT* to foster Trust, Explainability and other properties like Transparency useful to make agents trustworthy by design. In this Section we want to define some methods to apply aforesaid architecture to real world scenarios, in particular we will see how to extend Trust and Explainability to *MAS* and *DAOs* and scenarios, structures to foster Interpretability like Behavioural Trees, methods for measurability, and finally languages to add intelligence to systems.

4.1 How to Define Trust in *MAS* and *DAOs*

Trust, as said in previous Section 1.5 is a foundational concept in Explainable Computational Agent paradigm, there we presented both a definition and some concepts to measure it. When coming to *MAS* and *DAOs* deployments, we must extend such concepts to fit these more complex scenarios where multiple agents interacts, potentially in a contrastive way. Among the numerous definitions of trust, the one proposed by Gambetta et al. [59] is widely accepted in the *MAS* community , furthermore it relies upon the one given before (See Section 1.5.1) for a single agent:

“Trust is the subjective probability by which an agent A expects that another agent B performs a given action on which its welfare depends.”

This definition highlights the binary nature of trust: first, it is an evaluation of another’s reliability, where agent *A* predicts the future behaviour of agent *B* based on its mental state; second, it is the actuation of decisions based on such an evaluation. To formalize and generalize Gambetta’s paradigm, we can define trust as a logical proposition. Let:

$$T_i(j) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

represent the trust evaluation agent *i* assigns to agent *j*, expressed as a degree of trustworthiness on a continuous scale. Agent *i* will take an action *a* based on its trust in *j* if the trust function *T*

exceeds a certain reputation threshold r_{i_j} . The corresponding logical proposition can be expressed as:

$$a \iff T_i(j) \geq r_{i_j}.$$

This simple yet effective formalization can be extended to more complex systems, including decentralized and distributed environments, where trust plays a crucial role in decision-making and interaction among agents.

In the context of *DAOs*, where agents composing a *MAS* may express some kind of resolution vote, trust dynamics are critical for organizational governance. A *DAOs* could employ smart contracts to estimate the trustworthiness of decisions by calculating a weighted average trust of votes cast by participating agents. Let:

- $T_i(j) \rightarrow [0, 1]$: The trust evaluation that agent i has of agent j .
- $R_j \in \mathbb{R}$: The reputation score of agent j within the DAO environment.
- n : The total number of participating agents.

The confidence level $C(V)$ of a vote V , cast by n agents, can be computed as:

$$C(V) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m R_j \cdot T_i(j)}{n}.$$

This equation represents a possible interpretation of trust in *DAOs*, leveraging the reputation of agents to influence the confidence level of decisions. However, trust evaluation can be further enriched by incorporating additional agent features, such as:

- Level of experience in the *DAOs*.
- Age of the agent in the system (i.e., how long the agent has participated in *DAOs* activities).
- Speed of response in previous interactions or tasks.
- Financial contribution or wealth in the *DAOs* ecosystem.
- Historical consistency of the agent's voting behaviour with successful outcomes.

These features can be combined to configure a multidimensional reputational system, enabling a more nuanced representation of trust. Formally, we can model the state of an agent's trustworthiness as a multidimensional vector:

$$\vec{T}_j = [T_1(j), T_2(j), \dots, T_k(j)],$$

where each component $T_k(j)$ represents a specific trust-related feature. The overall trust estimate could then be a weighted sum or function of these features, where weights are determined based on the importance of each feature in the *DAOs*'s context. To implement such a trust system we need to take care of several aspects:

1. Smart Contract Design: Smart contracts should integrate the trust evaluation formula $C(V)$ and dynamically adjust thresholds r_{i_j} based on system requirements or contextual factors.

2. Reputation Management: A distributed reputation management system can be built using a combination of on-chain and off-chain mechanisms. Reputation scores R_j can be updated in real time based on agents' actions and outcomes.
3. Multidimensional Trust Evaluation: Implement a modular architecture that computes trust as a function of multiple features. A possible solution would be to use *ML* models to determine the optimal weights for different Trust-related dimensions.
4. Transparency and Explainability: Ensure the trust evaluation process is transparent by recording all calculations and justifications on the blockchain. This enhances Explainability and builds confidence among participants.
5. Scalability: Use efficient algorithms to compute trust metrics, ensuring scalability as the number of agents and interactions grows.

In conclusion, by formalizing trust and extending its application to *DAOs*, we can build more robust and transparent systems where agents can make decisions based on measurable, explainable, and multidimensional trust evaluations. This enhances the autonomy and reliability of intelligent agents in decentralized systems, paving the way for more complex, cooperative interactions in *MAS* and *DAOs* environments.

4.2 How to Define Explainability in *MAS* and *DAOs*

We analysed how to define Explainability for a single agent in Section 1.5.2; like just done per Trust paradigm we need to extend the theoretical definition in a method for complex scenarios. An interesting framework for *XAI*, which will serve as a base for our purpose, has been proposed by Ciatto et al. [22]. This framework conceptualizes Explainability as two related activities: the objective explanation of the system and the subjective interpretation of its behaviour.

Interpretation refers to the assignment of a subjective meaning by an agent i to a system X . Formally, we define a function:

$$I_i(X) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

where $I_i(X)$ represents the degree of interpretability of the system as perceived by agent i . If:

$$I_i(X') \geq I_i(X)$$

then system X' is considered more interpretable than X

Explanation is defined as the activity performed by agent i to increase the interpretability of a system X , resulting in a new system X' . This process is captured by the function:

$$E_i(X) \rightarrow X'$$

where X' satisfies the condition:

$$I_i(X') \geq I_i(X)$$

The framework can be extended to multi-agent environments with heterogeneous behaviours and varying knowledge bases. It models an explainer-explainees paradigm, where a "mutual understand-

ing" relationship is established between agents (either human or software) on a 1-to-1 or n -to- m basis. In this paradigm, if an agent A (the explainer) wishes to explain a model to another agent B (the explainee), the following conditions must be met:

- Shared taxonomy must be established to ensure consistent interpretation of terms and concepts.
- Reconciliation mechanism must be in place to align the knowledge bases of both agents, enabling effective communication and explanation.

This framework can be extended to *DAOs*, where an agent A (the explainer) may need to explain to other agents or participants B (the explainees) why a specific decision was made in relation to a *DAOs* voting poll V on resolution R . The explanation E could be expressed as a function e :

$$E = e(A, V, R),$$

and mapped onto a minimal set of features f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m that agent A considers sufficient to justify its decision on V . The explainee has the following possible actions:

1. Accept the explanation as sufficient and take no further action.
2. Request a more granular explanation E' , which may involve additional features f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n , where $n > m$, or a historical sequence of those features.
3. Seek an alternative explanation E'' by querying another voting agent B , such that:

$$E'' = e(B, V, R).$$

Coming to technical implementation, incorporating Explainability into *DAOs* involves several technical considerations:

1. **Feature Selection and Representation:** Agents must define a minimal set of features f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m for decision-making. These features must be easily retrievable and interpretable by the *DAOs* participants.
2. **Explainability Modules:** Smart contracts can include dedicated explainability modules that generate justifications for each decision. These modules would calculate explanations E and provide dynamic adjustment for E' and E'' .
3. **Historical Traceability:** The system should maintain a blockchain-based immutable log of explanations and voting outcomes. This enables accountability and transparency, ensuring all decisions are traceable and verifiable.
4. **Granularity Control:** Mechanisms must be in place to allow agents to adjust the granularity of their explanations dynamically, depending on the explainee's requests.
5. **Performance Optimization:** Since blockchain integration can introduce delays, efficient algorithms should be used to minimize latency, ensuring that explanation requests do not bottleneck the *DAOs* operations.

While integrating Explainability into *DAOs* has significant potential, several challenges remain:

- **System Performance:** The inclusion of blockchain mechanisms, such as smart contracts and transaction validation, may slow down the overall system, particularly in real-time applications.
- **Complexity of Decision-Making:** *DAOs* mechanisms, such as voting polls, introduce delays that may not align with the requirements of time-critical systems.
- **Resource Constraints:** Explaining decisions in real time may require significant computational resources, particularly when explanations involve complex models or large amounts of historical data.
- **Scalability:** As the number of agents and interactions increases, the system must scale efficiently while maintaining interpretability and explainability.

Modelling complex organizations of interacting entities, such as *DAOs* and *MAS*, is crucial as distributed AI systems become more prevalent. Introducing Explainability and Trust mechanisms in sensitive applications (e.g., medical systems, financial platforms) fosters transparency and reliability. *DAOs*, by leveraging blockchain technology, can enable transparent and accountable orchestration of all participants in the explanation and interpretation process. However, technical challenges such as performance optimization and scalability must be addressed to ensure the practical feasibility of such systems.

4.3 Behavioural Trees

Behavioral Trees (BTs) have emerged as a versatile framework for designing, controlling, and managing complex intelligent systems, especially in the domain of robotics and autonomous agents [26]. Inspired by decision trees and hierarchical task networks, *BTs* offer a modular, intuitive, and flexible approach for representing and executing behaviour. Their adoption in robotics has facilitated advancements in autonomy, adaptability, and scalability. This section explores the principles of behavioural trees, their application in robotics, and the key benefits they bring to intelligent systems. *BTs* are directed trees that consist of nodes organized in a hierarchical structure where each node represents a specific behaviour or decision-making process. The nodes are broadly classified into (i) Root nodes that serve as the starting point of the tree, initiating the evaluation process; (ii) Control flow nodes manage the flow of execution based on specific criteria and include sequence nodes that execute child nodes sequentially until one fails, selector nodes that execute child nodes sequentially until one succeeds, and parallel nodes that execute multiple child nodes simultaneously with defined success or failure conditions; and (iii) Leaf nodes represent atomic actions or conditions and serve as the fundamental building blocks for more complex behaviours.

BTs are run through from the root node downwards, with control flow nodes dictating how child nodes are activated. The status of each node is evaluated as success, failure, or running. This dynamic framework allows them to seamlessly adapt to changing environments by reevaluating node conditions during execution.

4.3.1 Behavioural Trees in Robotics

BTs bring several advantages to robotics. They enable developers to decompose complex behaviours into smaller, reusable components, facilitating easier debugging, maintenance, and scalability. The hierarchical structure and dynamic evaluation of trees make them highly adaptable to changing conditions and unforeseen events in real-time. Additionally, their visual and hierarchical representation enhances interpretability, making them accessible to both developers and stakeholders. Trees' ability to dynamically re-evaluate conditions ensures quick responses to changes in the environment, which is crucial for robotic systems operating in uncertain settings; furthermore they can incorporate *ML* models and Rule-based logic, effectively bridging the gap between traditional AI planning and modern data-driven approaches. Applications in Robotics of the paradigm are:

- Autonomous Navigation: trees are used for path planning and obstacle avoidance. For instance, a robot navigating a warehouse may use a BT to check for obstacles, choose an alternative path if an obstacle is detected, and move towards the target.
- *Human-Robot Interaction (HRI)*: *BTs* facilitate intuitive and adaptable interactions by enabling robots to interpret human gestures or voice commands, dynamically adjusting behaviours based on user feedback, and ensuring safety while adhering to ethical guidelines.
- Swarm Robotics: *BTs* enhance coordination and communication within robotic swarms by assigning specific roles to individual robots, ensuring robust collective behaviours through redundancy and adaptability, and simplifying the implementation of distributed decision-making processes.
- Industrial Automation: In industrial automation, robots benefit from *BTs* by seamlessly switching tasks based on production requirements, employing error recovery mechanisms to minimize downtime, and integrating effectively with IoT and smart factory systems.

Several frameworks support the implementation of trees in robotics, such as BehaviorTree.CPP, a C++ library¹ designed for real-time robotic applications; ROS Behavior Trees (BT.ROSLib)², which integrates BTs with the Robot Operating System (ROS); and PyTrees³, a Python-based framework for designing and executing *BTs*.

When implementing them, it is advisable to start with a basic tree structure and incrementally add complexity. Modularity should be prioritized by designing reusable nodes, which simplifies development. Iterative testing of individual nodes and subtrees is essential before integrating them into the larger system. Additionally, incorporating logging mechanisms helps monitor node execution and diagnose issues. Let's see an example, in Figure 4.1 of a behavioural tree design for a robot performing a search and retrieval task. The Behaviour Tree structure has the following functionalities:

- Root Node
 - Task: Search and Retrieve

¹<https://github.com/BehaviorTree/BehaviorTree.CPP>, accessed on January 2025

²<https://github.com/miccol/ROS-Behavior-Tree>, accessed on January 2025

³<https://py-trees.readthedocs.io/en/devel/>, accessed on January 2025

Figure 4.1: Behavioural Tree of a robot performing a simple search and retrieval task.

- Subtasks (Child Nodes)

1. Sequence: Search Object

- Condition: Localization Ready (Check if the robot has its localization system initialized)
- Selector: Locate Object
 - * Action: Use Camera to Detect Object
 - * Action: Use Lidar to Detect Object
 - * Action: Move to Candidate Locations

2. Sequence: Retrieve Object

- Condition: Object Detected
- Action: Move to Object
- Action: Grasp Object

3. Sequence: Deliver Object

- Condition: Object Secured
- Action: Plan Path to Delivery Point
- Action: Move to Delivery Point
- Action: Release Object

As we can see from the example *BTs* are hierarchical models used to structure robot behaviours in a modular and reactive way. They allow robots to dynamically adapt to changing environments, making them ideal for search and retrieval tasks. They combine the advantages of finite-state machines and decision trees, providing clarity and scalability (See Colledanchise & Ögren [25]). Key features of the retrieval robot represented by Design 4.1 are:

- Hierarchical Modularity: The tree is divided into three main sequences: searching, retrieving, and delivering. Each is an independent module that executes its tasks sequentially.

- **Selectors:** When multiple strategies can achieve a goal (e.g., object detection via camera or LIDAR), a selector node ensures that alternative methods are tried until success.
- **Conditions:** Conditions act as checks (e.g., "Object Detected") to prevent actions from executing unnecessarily or prematurely.
- **Reactivity:** If the robot fails to locate or retrieve the object, it can loop back to re-execute parts of the tree, making it robust in dynamic environments.

Despite their advantages, *BTs* face challenges such as increased complexity in large systems, which can make them difficult to manage and debug. The lack of a universally accepted standard for *BTs* implementation often leads to compatibility issues. Furthermore, combining trees with advanced *ML* algorithms requires careful balancing of interpretability and computational complexity.

Future advancements in this paradigm include the development of hybrid architectures that combine *BTs* with Neural networks, *RL*, or Fuzzy Logic for enhanced decision-making capabilities.

This paradigm has proven to be a robust and versatile framework for managing behaviours in Intelligent Systems, particularly in robotics. Its modularity, adaptability, and transparency make it an ideal choice for addressing Trust and Explainability problems both in modern robotic applications and complex Intelligent Systems using *MAS* and *DAOs* deployments.

4.4 Fuzzy Logic to measure Trust and Explainability

Fuzzy Logic is a form of many-valued logic dealing with a type of reasoning that is approximate rather than fixed and exact. Unlike classical binary logic (or Boolean logic), which operates with clear true/false values (either 0 or 1), Fuzzy Logic allows for a continuum of truth values between 0 and 1. This makes it particularly well-suited for handling uncertain, vague, or imprecise information, emulating human decision-making processes in complex systems. Fuzzy Logic was introduced by Zadeh in 1965 [152] as a way to mathematically represent uncertainty and reasoning with imprecise information. It has since become a powerful tool in Control Systems, *AI*, and decision-making processes. Core Components of this paradigm are:

1. **Fuzzification:** The process of converting crisp inputs into fuzzy sets by applying membership functions.
2. **Fuzzy Inference:** The process of formulating mapping from a given input to an output using a set of rules and fuzzy reasoning.
3. **Defuzzification:** The process of converting fuzzy output into a crisp value.

These components interact to form the basis of Fuzzy Logic systems, allowing them to model complex behaviours in a straightforward and interpretable manner. This paradigm foster several advantages, in particular for Intelligent Systems operating in real world scenarios: (i) **Human-Like Reasoning:** reproduce human decision-making processes, making it intuitive to design and implement; (ii) **Flexibility:** can handle imprecise and noisy inputs effectively; (iii) **Simplicity:** requires less computational power compared to traditional control systems in many cases; (iv) **Wide Applications:** applied to heterogeneous fields like Industrial Automation to optimize manufacturing processes by adjusting parameters dynamically, Financial Systems to address risk assessment and

decision-making in uncertain market conditions, or Robotics where enables robots to navigate, balance, and interact with environments.

For our purpose we want to introduce an innovative use of this paradigm to evaluate Trust in *MAS* and *DAOs*; in particular we can postulate to calculate Trust of an Agent composing the *MAS* or voting in the *DAOs*, based on the following input variables envisioned in Section 4.1:

- Level of experience in the *DAOs/MAS*.
- Age of the agent in the system.
- Speed of response in previous interactions or tasks.
- Financial contribution or wealth in the *DAOs/MAS* ecosystem.
- Historical consistency of the agent's voting behaviour with successful outcomes.

We can consequently define the Fuzzy Sets and Membership Functions, each input variable is represented by sets defined as follows:

- Level of Experience (*LE*): *Low, Medium, High*
- Age in System (*AS*): *New, Moderate, Established*
- Speed of Response (*SR*): *Slow, Average, Fast*
- Financial Contribution (*FC*): *Low, Moderate, High*
- Consistency in Voting Behaviour (*CVB*): *Inconsistent, Moderate, Consistent*

The output variable, Trustworthiness T , is defined by the fuzzy sets *Low, Medium, High*. Membership functions are used to map crisp input values to fuzzy sets. Below are the membership functions diagrams for each variable:

Figure 4.2: Membership function for *Level of Experience*

Figure 4.3: Membership function for *Age in System*

Figure 4.4: Membership function for *Speed of Response*

Figure 4.5: Membership function for *Financial Contribution*

Figure 4.6: Membership function for *Consistency in Voting Behavior*

At this point we must define the Fuzzy Rules that generate the output in relation to the input variables values of interests. For each Membership Function we defined example range of values (on the x axis) that is represented in Figures 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5 and 4.6. The trustworthiness score T is computed using fuzzy inference rules. Below are sample rules, note that not all possible values of input variables must be specified:

1. If Level of Experience (LE) is High and Age in System (AS) is Established, then Trustworthiness (T) is High.

$$T = 'High' \leftarrow (LE = 'High') \wedge (AS = 'Established')$$

2. If Speed of Response (SR) is Fast and Consistency in Voting Behaviour (CVB) is Consistent, then Trustworthiness (T) is High.

$$T = 'High' \leftarrow (SR = 'High') \wedge (CVB = 'Consistent')$$

3. If Financial Contribution (FC) is Low and Consistency in Voting Behavior (CVB) is Inconsistent, then Trustworthiness (T) is Low.

$$T = 'Low' \leftarrow (FC = 'Low') \wedge (CVB = 'Inconsistent')$$

4. If Age in System (AE) is New and Level of Experience (LE) is Low, then Trustworthiness T is Low.

$$T = 'Low' \leftarrow (AS = 'New') \wedge (LE = 'Low')$$

5. If Financial Contribution (FC) is High or *Consistency in Voting Behavior* is Consistent, then *Trustworthiness* is Medium.

$$T = 'Medium' \leftarrow (FC = 'High') \wedge (CVB = 'Consistent')$$

The output *Trustworthiness* is defuzzified using the centroid method to produce a crisp score ranging from 0 to 1. A threshold of 0.5 is applied to classify agents:

- Trustable: Crisp score ≥ 0.5
- Not Trustable: Crisp score < 0.5

The centroid method, also known as the center of gravity method, calculates a crisp value for the fuzzy output set by finding the balance point of the aggregated membership function. Mathematically, the centroid C is given by:

$$C = \frac{\int x \cdot \mu(x) dx}{\int \mu(x) dx}$$

where:

- x is the output variable (in this case, trustworthiness).
- $\mu(x)$ is the membership degree of x in the aggregated fuzzy set.
- The numerator computes the weighted sum of x -values.
- The denominator calculates the total membership degree (area under the curve).

The aggregated fuzzy output is obtained by combining the individual fuzzy sets (e.g., *Low Trust*, *Medium Trust*, *High Trust*) derived from fuzzy rules. The crisp value is marked as the centroid of this aggregated curve. The diagram in Figure 4.7 shows the membership functions for the output variable *Trustworthiness T*, the aggregated fuzzy output, and the centroid indicating the crisp value:

The crisp trustworthiness score, computed using the centroid method, is of course = 0.50.

Figure 4.7: Defuzzified Trustworthiness output

This fuzzy logic system integrates multiple inputs to assess the trustworthiness of agents in a *DAOs/MAS* environment. The system is adaptable and can be refined with additional rules or inputs as needed. Fuzzy Logic bridges the gap between precise mathematical modelling and real-world uncertainty, providing a powerful framework for decision-making and control. By combining simple principles with robust flexibility, it empowers systems to operate effectively in dynamic and complex environments. The provided example demonstrates how easily Fuzzy Logic can be applied to practical problems, laying the foundation for exploring its broader applications in intelligent systems.

To conclude this section, we emphasize that the Fuzzy Logic paradigm for trust evaluation can be applied both before the Intelligent System is used, thus satisfying the ex-ante property proposed in this thesis, and after the system has produced its results, in an ex-post usage scenario. In the ex-ante case, Fuzzy Logic provides an assessment of the predicted trust level T_a (previously defined as trustworthiness T), which represents the expected trustworthiness of the system based on relevant features. This yields the ex-ante crisp value, denoted as $Crisp_a$, for the function T . In the ex-post scenario, the obtained results (e.g., the features composing the trust vector T) can be evaluated to determine both the actual trust value T_p and the ex-post crisp value $Crisp_p$. By comparing these values, we can assess the degree of predictability of the Intelligent System's results.

4.5 Languages for Intelligent Systems

This Section introduces the main features of DALI and TeleoR/Qlog, their syntax, and their theoretical foundations, alongside relevant literature illustrating its use in academic and practical settings. The development of intelligent agents necessitates a programming paradigm that combines declarative reasoning with the ability to interact with dynamic and unpredictable environments.

4.5.1 DALI: A Declarative Language for Programming Intelligent Agents

DALI is a high-level logic programming language specifically designed to develop intelligent agents capable of dynamic interaction with their environment. Extending Prolog, DALI provides features for reactivity, proactivity, reasoning, and communication, making it suitable for applications requiring robust and adaptive agent behaviour. It is a language rooted in logic programming, addresses these requirements introducing constructs for reactivity, proactivity, and agent communication. The language's foundation lies in its ability to model agents as entities capable of perceiving external events, reasoning about their internal states, and acting autonomously. The language's design aligns with logic-based agent architectures presented in Section 3.5, emphasizing modularity and expressiveness. Let's examine deeper features and extensions introduced to enhance traditional Prolog to support agent-oriented programming:

- **Reactive Rules:** this type of rules allow agents to respond dynamically to external events; they are triggered when specific conditions are met, enabling real-time interaction with the environment. Example Syntax of a rule which specifies that if an *alarm_detected* event occurs, the agent will execute the *turn_off_machine* action is the following:

```
react_to_alarm :- alarm_detected => turn_off_machine.
```

Listing 4.1: DALI example of a reactive rule.

- **Proactive Rules:** Proactive rules enable agents to perform actions autonomously based on internal goals or periodic triggers. These rules encapsulate the agent's proactive behavior. Example Syntax:

```
monitor_temperature :- every(5) => check_temperature.
```

Listing 4.2: DALI example of a proactive rule.

This rule indicates that the agent will execute *check_temperature* every five time units.

- **Internal Events:** Internal events represent the agent's reasoning processes or state changes. They enable agents to maintain a memory of past interactions and use it for decision-making.
- **Communication Capabilities:** DALI supports inter-agent communication through message passing primitives. These features allow agents to cooperate and exchange information in multi-agent systems. Example Syntax:

```
send_alert(Agent) :- critical_state => message(Agent, critical_alert).
```

Listing 4.3: DALI example of a communication rule.

This rule specifies that if a *critical_state* occurs, the agent sends a *critical_alert* message to another agent.

- **Memory Management:** DALI includes mechanisms for recording historical data, facilitating learning and temporal reasoning. This feature allows agents to adapt their behaviour based on past experiences.

The language has been applied in diverse domains requiring adaptive and intelligent behaviour, such as (i) Robotics where programming robots to react to environmental stimuli and perform autonomous tasks is a key property; (ii) Smart Environments, enabling dynamic control in smart homes and industrial automation; and (iii) Multi-Agent Systems for coordinating tasks and communication in distributed agent-based architectures.

DALI's theoretical basis lies in extending traditional logic programming with constructs that align with agent-oriented principles:

- **Event Handling:** Formalizing the notion of events (external and internal) and their effects on agent behaviour.
- **Declarative Semantics:** Providing a clear and formal semantic foundation for reactive and proactive rules.
- **Modularity:** Enabling agents to be constructed as modular components, each with specific reactive and proactive behaviours.

For our architecture DALI represent a fundamental paradigm to define both decision-making layer and the explainability layer, in order to manage dynamic events, reasoning and interaction with environment components (stimuli, actions but also *DLT* events registering). To give a simple example of how to use DALI for a robotics, consider the following program describing an agent navigating in an environment and registering on a blockchain each move taken:

```
% Load DALI library
:- use_module(library(dali)).

% Safe distance threshold
safe_distance(5). % The agent considers 5 units as the safe distance.

% Reactive rules
reactive_rule(sense(obstacle, Distance)) :-
    write('Obstacle_detected_at_distance:_'), write(Distance), nl,
    decide_action(Distance, Action),
    communicate_action(Action),
    log_decision(Action).

% Decision-making based on distance
decide_action(Distance, stop) :-
    safe_distance(Safe),
    Distance =< Safe,
    write('Decision:_STOP'), nl.

decide_action(Distance, turn_left) :-
    safe_distance(Safe),
    Distance > Safe,
    Distance =< Safe + 2, % Slightly beyond safe distance
    write('Decision:_TURN_LEFT'), nl.

decide_action(Distance, turn_right) :-
    safe_distance(Safe),
    Distance > Safe + 2,
```

```

    write('Decision: TURN_RIGHT'), nl.

% Communicating the decision to another agent
communicate_action(Action) :-
    write('Communicating decision to the partner agent: '), write(Action), nl,
    % Simulate sending a message
    send_message(partner_agent, Action).

% Simulating blockchain logging
:- dynamic blockchain/1. % Dynamic predicate to store decisions

log_decision(Action) :-
    write('Logging decision to blockchain: '), write(Action), nl,
    (blockchain(Log) => append(Log, [Action], UpdatedLog) ; UpdatedLog = [Action]),
    retractall(blockchain(_)),
    assert(blockchain(UpdatedLog)).

% Simulate receiving events
:- assert(event(sense(obstacle, 3))). % Simulate an obstacle at 3 units
:- assert(event(sense(obstacle, 6))). % Simulate an obstacle at 6 units
:- assert(event(sense(obstacle, 8))). % Simulate an obstacle at 8 units

% Partner agent reactive rule
reactive_rule(receive(partner_agent, Action)) :-
    write('Partner agent received decision: '), write(Action), nl.

```

Listing 4.4: DALI example of navigating robot interacting with a DLT/Blockchain.

The above listing, worth to note, could be written as a Smart Contract on blockchain guaranteeing users regarding immutability and predictability of agent's decisions. Let's examine the expected behaviour fostered by the program:

1. Obstacle Detection and Decision Making: when the sense event occurs, the agent checks the distance from the obstacle. If the distance is less than or equal to the safe distance, it decides to stop. If slightly greater, it decides to turn left while If significantly greater, it decides to turn right.
2. Communicating with Another Agent: the decision is sent to a partner agent using the *send_message* predicate, which simulates communication in a multi-agent environment.
3. Blockchain Logging: decisions are logged to a simulated blockchain. The *blockchain/1* predicate dynamically stores all decisions, simulating a ledger.
4. Event Simulation: three events are simulated to demonstrate different scenarios:
 - An obstacle at a close distance (3 units).
 - An obstacle slightly beyond the safe distance (6 units).
 - An obstacle far away (8 units).
5. Partner Agent's Response: a partner agent listens for messages and reacts to decisions sent by the primary agent.

In conclusion, DALI represents a significant advancement in programming languages for intelligent agents, providing a declarative framework that supports both reasoning and dynamic interaction with the environment. Its integration of reactive, proactive, and communicative capabilities makes it a powerful tool for developing intelligent systems.

Key Literature regarding this paradigm can be found in Costantini and Tocchio "The DALI Logic Programming Agent-Oriented Language" [30] while specific application of the language to Cognitive Robotic are in Costantini et. al. "DALI for Cognitive Robotics: Principles and Prototype Implementation" [29].

4.5.2 TeleoR and Qlog: two advanced logic-based languages designed for artificial intelligence and agent control

Qulog and TeleoR are high-level logic programming languages tailored for reasoning and acting in dynamic and complex environments. Both languages build upon the foundations of logic programming but address different aspects of intelligent systems:

- TeleoR: a teleo-reactive programming language for creating goal-directed, reactive agents that operate in dynamic environments.
- Qulog: a logic-based query and action language designed for multi-agent systems, focusing on reasoning, communication, and integration with real-world data.

TeleoR, or A Teleo-Reactive Language is designed for implementing Teleo-reactive (TR) programs that control agents in dynamic, real-time environments. The language extends Prolog by incorporating hierarchical condition-action rules, enabling agents to act flexibly while pursuing long-term goals. TeleoR is particularly useful in robotics and autonomous systems, where environmental unpredictability demands adaptive behaviour. The language originates from the concept of teleological-reactive logic that explains events in terms their purposes rather than their causes, and was introduced by Nilsson in the 1990s [108]. Its approach emphasized goal-directed behavior combined with reactivity to immediate environmental changes. TeleoR advances this concept by formalizing it into a practical programming language that supports reasoning and execution simultaneously, its key features are the following:

1. Hierarchical Goal Representation: rules are structured hierarchically, enabling agents to prioritize goals.
2. Continuous Monitoring: TeleoR agents continuously monitor the environment and switch actions when conditions change.
3. Modular Design: programs can be modularly defined, facilitating the reuse of behaviours across agents or scenarios.
4. Integration with External Systems: TeleoR allows integration with sensors and actuators for real-world applications

Let's examine an example program of a simple navigation Agent; the following TeleoR program defines a robot navigating a grid while avoiding obstacles:

```

% Rule 1: If at the goal location , stop .
at(goal) => stop .

% Rule 2: If an obstacle is ahead , turn left .
obstacle_ahead => turn(left) .

% Rule 3: If the path is clear , move forward .
path_clear => move(forward) .

% Rule 4: If the robot is stuck , turn right .
stuck => turn(right) .

```

Listing 4.5: TeleoR rules of a simple navigation Agent.

In this case the Execution Flow provides for the agent to evaluate the rules top-down, executing the first rule whose condition is satisfied. This approach ensures responsiveness to immediate conditions while pursuing the long-term goal ('at(goal)').

Coming to Qulog, introduced by Clark [24], it is a logic-based query and action language based on multi-paradigm logic programming language designed for reasoning, querying, and executing actions in intelligent systems. It is particularly well-suited for multi-agent environments where agents need to share knowledge, communicate, and collaborate. Core Characteristics of the languages include:

1. Declarative Queries: Qulog provides rich support for querying knowledge bases with logical inference.
2. Action Execution: agents can perform actions, including communication and manipulation of their environment.
3. Temporal Reasoning: Qulog supports reasoning about time, enabling agents to consider past, present, and future events.
4. Integration with Sensors: the language allows agents to interact with external data sources for real-time decision-making.

Qulog is very effective in Collaborative Agents Systems, the following example program defines two agents collaborating to achieve a shared goal:

1. Agent 1 (Sensor Agent):

```

% Detects the temperature and informs the Control Agent .
sense_temperature :-
    temperature(T) ,
    tell(control_agent , temperature(T)) .

```

Listing 4.6: Qulog program of Agent sensing temperature and communicating it.

2. Agent 2 (Control Agent):

```

% Reacts to the sensed temperature and takes appropriate action .
react(temperature(T)) :-
    T > 30 -> start_cooling_system ;
    T < 10 -> start_heating_system ;

```

```
true -> maintain_current_state.
```

Listing 4.7: Qulog program of Agent receiving temperature and reacting to it.

Agent 1 monitors the temperature through the *sense_temperature* predicate function and informs Agent 2 with the *sense_temperature* primitive. Agent 2 decides then the appropriate action (either *start_cooling_system* or *start_heating_system*) based on the received temperature data. Qulog allows agents to perform complex reasoning queries. For instance, an agent querying its knowledge base might use:

```
% Query all known facts about temperatures
?- temperature(T).
```

Listing 4.8: Qulog example of knowledge base query.

TeleoR and Qulog can be used together for robust agent control and reasoning:

- TeleoR handles the reactive control of agents in dynamic environments.
- Qulog provides high-level reasoning, data query primitives and inter-agent communication capabilities.

Let's consider a more complex example of a robot navigating a warehouse; robot is tasked with retrieving items from shelves and delivering them to a loading bay. The robot (i) Uses TeleoR to navigate the warehouse while avoiding obstacles; (ii) Communicates with a central Qulog system to receive tasks and report status. (iii) Queries the warehouse's database (using Qulog) for item locations. For Real-Time navigation, the TeleoR program handles low-level control of the robot as it moves in the warehouse. An example of rules definition could be the following:

```
% Rule 1: If the robot is at the destination, stop.
at(destination) => stop.

% Rule 2: If an obstacle is detected ahead, turn left.
obstacle_ahead => turn(left).

% Rule 3: If the path is clear, move forward.
path_clear => move(forward).

% Rule 4: If the robot is stuck, turn right.
stuck => turn(right).

% Rule 5: If the robot needs to recharge, go to the charging station.
battery_low => go_to(charging_station).
```

Listing 4.9: Example of rules for a robot navigating in a warehouse.

On the Qulog side instead, reasoning and communication aspects will be addressed, in particular the system manages high-level tasks such as assigning missions, querying item locations, and maintaining a central database of tasks and inventory. The Qulog *CKB* could be defined as follow:

```
% Define locations in the warehouse.
location(shelf1).
location(shelf2).
location(loading_bay).
```

```

location(charging_station).

% Item locations.
item_location(item1, shelf1).
item_location(item2, shelf2).

% Tasks queue.
task_queue([fetch(item1), fetch(item2)]).

```

Listing 4.10: Example of Qulog knowledge base for a robot navigating in a warehouse.

While the Qulog Task Manager can be written as follow:

```

% Assign tasks to the robot.
assign_task(Robot) :-
    task_queue([Task | RemainingTasks]),
    retract(task_queue(_)),
    assert(task_queue(RemainingTasks)),
    tell(Robot, task(Task)).

% Query item location.
query_item_location(Item, Location) :-
    item_location(Item, Location),
    format("Item ~w is located at ~w.~n", [Item, Location]).

% Handle status updates from the robot.
react(status(Robot, at/loading_bay))) :-
    format("~w has arrived at the loading bay.~n", [Robot]),
    assign_task(Robot).

react(status(Robot, task_complete(Item))) :-
    format("~w has completed the task for ~w.~n", [Robot, Item]).

```

Listing 4.11: Qulog example of a task manager for a robot in a warehouse.

The benefits of a mixed paradigm obtained by combining TeleoR and Qulog can be resumed in the following points:

1. High-Level Task Assignment (Qulog): the central system (using Qulog) assigns a task to the robot: fetching an item from a shelf; then it queries the database to determine the item's location (e.g., `query_item_location(item1, shelf1)`).
2. Real-Time Navigation (TeleoR): once the task is received, the warehouse robot uses TeleoR to navigate to the item's location, avoiding obstacles and managing its battery.
3. Status Updates (Qulog): the warehouse robot sends status updates to the Qulog system
 - ‘`status(at(destination))`’ when it reaches the item's location.
 - `status(task_complete(item1))` when it delivers the item to the loading bay.
4. Recharging (TeleoR): if the robot's battery is low during navigation, it automatically switches to recharging mode, navigating to the charging station using TeleoR rules.

A Workflow resembling the above example could be the following:

1. Initial Setup

- The central Qulog system holds the tasks: $[fetch(item1), fetch(item2)]$.
- The robot starts at the base station.

2. Task Assignment:

- Qulog assigns $fetch(item1)$ to the robot and determines the item's location at $shelf1$.
- The robot is informed: 'tell(robot1, task(fetch(item1)))'.

3. Navigation:

- The robot navigates to 'shelf1' using TeleoR.
- It avoids obstacles ($obstacle_ahead \Rightarrow turn(left)$).

4. Item Retrieval and Delivery:

- The robot fetches 'item1' and delivers it to the *loading_bay*.
- It reports back: $status(task_complete(item1))$.

5. Reassignment:

- The Qulog system assigns the next task ('fetch(item2)') and repeats the process.

6. Battery Management:

- If the robot's battery is low during a task, the TeleoR program directs it to the *charging_station*.

Key Benefits of Mixing TeleoR and Qulog are many, in particular we can point out: (i) Separation of Concerns: TeleoR handles low-level, time-critical navigation; while Qulog manages high-level reasoning, task allocation, and inter-agent communication. (ii) Scalability and Adaptability: where the Qulog system can coordinate multiple robots simultaneously, assigning tasks based on priority and status; while The TeleoR rules ensure that the robot can adapt to environmental changes in real time.

Chapter 5

Results

This chapter delves into the practical results derived from the theoretical frameworks and architectures presented in the earlier sections of this thesis. The aim is to bridge the gap between conceptual models and their real-world applicability by showcasing a series of practical implementations and experimental validations. Each subsection provides a comprehensive summary of individual and group research projects undertaken during the Doctoral Course, all of them have been peer-reviewed and accepted for publication.

These works represent the initial exploration of the proposed architecture’s capabilities, focusing primarily on the foundational interactions between *DLT* solutions, *DAOs* and *MAS*. By testing these interactions, the implementations lays the groundwork for more complex integrations and future enhancements. While the intelligent paradigms underpinning these systems are introduced here, they serve as a minimal component at this stage, leaving room for further exploration in subsequent research.

This chapter not only underscores the feasibility of the proposed approaches but also serves as a stepping stone toward the broader realization of intelligent, decentralized, and cooperative systems. The following sections offer detailed insights into each practical application, emphasizing the role of these initial implementations in validating and refining the architectural concepts developed throughout the course of this research.

5.1 DLT for Finance: Over-the-Counter transactions

The first *DLT* tested has been Corda¹ in an application for financial markets. The case study implemented has been based on a real problem experienced by Armundia², a software company specialized on the banking sector, and regarded the Automation of an *Over-the-Counter (OTC)* Financial Derivatives Transaction.

OTC derivatives are financial contracts negotiated directly between two parties without the involvement of an intermediary exchange. Their flexibility in terms of pricing, quantity, maturity, and upfront fees makes them an attractive option for portfolio managers. However, the manual nature of their processing has historically led to inefficiencies and errors; traditional methods in fact, often conducted over the phone or through manual systems, introduce operational risks and

¹<https://r3.com/corda/>, accessed on January 2025

²<https://armundia.com/>, accessed on January 2025

delays in verification, settlement, and compliance.

The evolution of Financial Technology (FinTech) has introduced electronic networks to improve transaction efficiency and reduce errors, and Blockchain and *DLT* offer a transformative opportunity to enhance these processes. This paper presents the design and implementation of an automated *OTC* derivatives post-trade confirmation system using the aforesaid permissioned blockchain platform Corda. By automating this traditionally manual process, the system seeks to reduce operational risks, eliminate errors, and enhance transaction speed and transparency.

Blockchain technology has garnered significant attention across financial industries for its potential to enhance transparency, security, and efficiency. In Italy, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) highlighted blockchain's potential for international trade and other sectors. Several projects, such as the "Spunta Banca DLT," have demonstrated the applicability of blockchain in banking, the project utilized Corda to streamline interbank reconciliations, proving the feasibility of blockchain solutions in financial transactions. The system's design focused on meeting general critical requirements for automating *OTC* post-trade confirmation processes:

- Immutability: transactions must be unique and unmodifiable once confirmed.
- Timestamping: each transaction must have a unique, read-only timestamp.
- Reconciliation: all transactions must be matched and confirmed by involved parties before completion.
- Privacy: transactions should only be visible to participating parties and service providers.
- Compliance: the system must align with GDPR regulations³, allowing data access for regulatory authorities when required.

Corda, developed by the R3 consortium, being an open-source DLT platform designed for financial institutions, unlike traditional blockchain architectures employs a "state" system where each state represents a contract instance. Transactions are processed and updated as states evolve; the main platform components are:

- Notary Nodes: to ensure transaction uniqueness, resolve disputes, and timestamp operations.
- Smart Contracts: enforcing business logic and data constraints.
- Flow Framework: to define multi-step protocols between parties without a central controller.

The application designed in this case study is a Corda Distributed Application (CorDapp) tailored for *OTC* post-trade confirmation, it supports critical functions like the DSMATCH and MARKIT platform ones, enabling secure and efficient transaction validation (see *OTC* trade scheme in Figure 5.1). Wu used the Corda's CorDapp Design Language (CDL) tool, that facilitates the modeling of CorDapps through:

1. Business Process Modeling Notation (BPMN): a graphical tool that illustrates workflows and interactions within the organization (see Figure 5.2).

³<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>, accessed on January 2025

Figure 5.1: The Over-the-Counter (OTC) trade scheme between a Counterparty (CTP) and a Front Office Investor (FOI). DSMATCH (Credit Default Swap) and MARKIT (Interest Rate Swap) functions of the Post Trade Confirmation (PTC) process is designed through a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) proposal. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17]

2. Smart Contract View: a method that depicts state transitions and relationships within the application.
3. Ledger View: to track the time evolution of states, reflecting transaction progress.

The CorDapp implementation involves two parties—a Front Office Investor (FOI) and a Counterparty (CTP). The post-trade confirmation process includes the following steps, that have been used to model the Smart Contract conceptualized in Figure 5.3:

1. Propose Deal: the initiator (seller) sends a transaction proposal.
2. Pre-Agree Deal: the receiver (buyer) reviews the proposal and sends a pre-agreement.
3. Agree Deal: the seller confirms the agreement.
4. Complete Deal: the buyer completes the transaction.
5. Cancel Deal: either party can cancel the transaction in case of non-compliance.

The CorDapp maintains a Post Trade Confirmation (PTC) packet containing transaction details, such as: (i) Identifiers for the buyer, seller, and trade (e.g., Legal Entity Identifier, Unique Transaction Identifier). (ii) Transaction amounts and instrument details. (iii) Rejection reasons and responsible parties (if applicable). Smart contract states transition thus, through four key statuses: (i) Proposed, (ii) Pre-Agreed, (iii) Agreed, and (iv) Rejected; while constraints are enforced at each stage to ensure data integrity and compliance with business rules. The ledger records the evolution

Figure 5.2: Business Process Modeling Notation View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17]

of a transaction's status. For example, a proposed deal transitions to "Pre-Agreed" when the buyer validates the seller's data. Upon mutual agreement, the status changes to "Agreed," and the transaction is finalized. This ledger system ensures transparency and accountability while maintaining privacy (see Figure 5.4). The system's front-end application enables seamless interaction with the CorDapp by the key actors involved that include:

- Middle Office Operators: Handle trade booking, validation, and confirmation.
- Counterparty Operators: Manage the counterparty's post-trade confirmation processes.
- Compliance Supervisors: Oversee technical and financial functions of the DLT system.
- Regulatory Authorities: Access transaction data for audits and investigations.

Coming to the Workflow and Use Case, the front-office application supports functionalities such as:

- Trade detail submission and validation.
- Execution of DSMATCH and MARKIT functions.
- Integrity checks to ensure accurate data processing.

Users authenticate through a secure VPN connection to access the system. Messaging functions facilitate communication between parties and the back office. The implementation of the Corda-based CorDapp offers several advantages:

1. Efficiency: automates manual processes, reducing time and labor.
2. Accuracy: eliminates errors associated with manual entry.

Figure 5.3: Business Process Modeling Notation View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17]

Figure 5.4: Ledger Evolution View of DSMATCH (CDS) and MARKIT (IRS) CorDapp. Courtesy of Carare et al. [17]

3. Security: provides an immutable, tamper-proof ledger.
4. Transparency: enables real-time access to transaction status for involved parties.
5. Compliance: ensures adherence to regulatory requirements.

In conclusion the study demonstrates the feasibility of automating OTC post-trade confirmation processes using Corda blockchain technology. The proposed solution reduces errors, enhances efficiency, and ensures compliance, offering a scalable foundation for further applications in the

financial sector. Future work could explore expanding the system’s capabilities to support more complex financial instruments and integrate additional intelligent features.

This research, funded by Armundia Group, validates the practical benefits of DLT in streamlining financial transactions, paving the way for broader adoption in the FinTech industry. It was presented at PAAMS 2021 international conference and published to its proceedings [17].

5.2 DAO and DLT for Tax Credit Tracking: Secure Fiscal Credit Model

This study develops a Secured Fiscal Credits Model (SFCM) to address the challenges of managing Italy’s Superbonus 110 tax credit. By integrating *AI* and blockchain technology within a *DAOs* architecture combined with a *MAS*, the system aims to prevent errors and detect fraudulent behaviors. Deploying two *DAOs*, one to represent the investors and the other to model the market of works professionals and contractors on the Algorand blockchain⁴, enhances Trust and Security ultimately supporting effective oversight of the Superbonus process and facilitating transparent value exchange among stakeholders.

Italian energy policies, influenced by European Union guidelines, focus on enhancing energy performance and reducing energy waste in residential systems. The Superbonus 110 tax credit system, introduced in 2020, enables residential owners to undertake energy efficiency upgrades and structural improvements without upfront costs through a tax credit mechanism. The study aims to develop the SFCM to address challenges such as bureaucratic delays, high demand, and potential fraud. In this scenario the Superbonus 110 program offers tax deductions for energy-efficient building renovations. The legislation stipulates that for every 100 euros spent on renovation works, the house owner is entitled to a 110 euros tax deduction over five years. The program also allows for a discount on the invoice or the transfer of accrued credit to a third party. In Figure 5.5 are shown the three Work Progress Status (WPS): (i) the first is stated at 30% of work, (ii) the second at 60%, and (iii) the remaining one after the entire work (100%). By calculating the average time to carry out the work, it is possible to project the state of the WPS and thus, the money required may be reserved over the foreseen period (on average eight months per building site for *ecobonus* and *sismabonus* (*Sisma-bonus* regards the building enhancement towards seismic vulnerabilities or six months for single *eco-bonus*).

The methodology utilized to model the intelligent part of the system involves defining a constraints knowledge base and designing agents to represent decision-makers, stakeholders, and other entities involved in the problem. The knowledge base includes six constraints designed to (i) ensure compliance with the original schedule plan, (ii) align token demand with forecasts, (iii) prevent over-spending, (iv) limit concessions per building unit, (v) certify projects, and (vi) manage the number of construction sites assigned to a General Contractor. Here we applied the theory introduced in Section 3.3; the constraint have thus been modelled as follow:

- Constraint 1. Here we want to define the possible states of the Agent representing the Workflow status of the intervention. This translates into the fact that the possible states of the

⁴<https://algorand.co/>, accessed on January 2025

Figure 5.5: Typical Work Progress Status distribution. The lower boxes represent the phases of work. The upper boxes are the actions/sub-phases requested for each principal phase of the workflow. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36]

agents are the following:

$$x_i = \{Open, Anticipation, Sal1, Sal2, Eow, Archived\},$$

or in brief $x_i = \{Op, Ant, S1, S2, Eow, Arc\}$. Each Agent of this type can occupy one of this states at one time, if we formalise the following expressions for each value of the state variable:

$$x_i(0) \Leftarrow Op \wedge \neg Ant \wedge \neg S1 \wedge \neg S2 \wedge \neg Eow \wedge \neg Arc$$

$$x_i(1) \Leftarrow \neg Op \wedge Ant \wedge \neg S1 \wedge \neg S2 \wedge \neg Eow \wedge \neg Arc$$

...

$$x_i(5) \Leftarrow \neg Op \wedge \neg Ant \wedge \neg S1 \wedge \neg S2 \wedge \neg Eow \wedge Arc$$

then the *CKB* can be, at this point, defined as follows:

$$true \Leftarrow x_i(0) \vee x_i(1) \vee x_i(2) \vee x_i(3) \vee x_i(4) \vee x_i(5)$$

- Constraint 2. We must ensure that token demand in Operator DAO aligns with Investor DAO forecasts. It is necessary to verify that the expected demand for tokens in the Operator DAO (dao_o) does not exceed that forecast in the Investor DAO (dao_i). So if d_t is the demand for the token and f_t is the forecast need for a token at time t , we must have:

$$d_t \leq f_{t-1}$$

- Constraint 3. Do not spend more than allocated for the specific project phase. So every payment made (p_s) by the agent controlling the workflow must not exceed the payments

received (p_r) as anticipation for that state. If w_t is the state of the workflow agent at time t , then

$$p_s(w_t) \leq p_r(w_{t-1})$$

- Constraint 4. Each homeowner may have at most two concessions per building unit. This translates in the condition that each client (c_i) may not have more than 2 workflow agents (w) opened:

$$|w(c_i)| \leq 2$$

- Constraint 5. Each project i must be certified by both technical and financial asseveration a raised by chartered engineers eng and accountants acc to grant the fairness of the expenses to the interventions listed in the WPS. Thus, if engineer j and accountant k are hired to asseverate project i :

$$true \Leftarrow a(eng_j)_i \wedge a(acc_k)_i$$

- Constraint 6. The General Contractor (GC) may have more than one construction site assigned. The maximum limit is determined by the tax credit that may be handled or the value set in the Attestation Organisation Certification (AOC) he has in place (e.g., 1 million euros works for private buildings renovation category). So if the GC has j works of value w_j each:

$$\sum w(GC_i)_j \leq AOC(GC_i)$$

Coming to Agents design we had to define Actors, Roles, and Actions. The agents are categorized into two main groups: investors and operators. The investors group includes actors with financial interests, while the operators group includes actors involved in the construction and design processes. Each agent has specific roles and actions, such as compliance control, construction management, and technical assessments. In Table 5.1 a scheme of Actors modelled and relative *DAOs* of reference.

Table 5.1: Relationship between the actors and their affiliation DAOs in comparison to the user actions.

DAO	Actor	Actions
Investors	Investor	Invest money to buy credits and benefits from its selling
Investors Op-operators	Financial institution	Banks that buy/sell credits and lend money to Operators
Investors Op-operators	Customer	House owner sells/transfers tax credits from works
Operators	General Contractor	Manages work, obtains credits from customers, sells to financial institutions
Operators	Sub-contractor	Hired and paid by General Contractor
Operators	Supplier	Hired and paid by General Contractor
Operators	Design Architect	Hired and paid by General Contractor
Operators	Tax Auditor	Hired and paid by General Contractor

Two main scenarios describe the information flow and actions related to the agents:

- Scenario 1: Homeowner and Technical Expert. A homeowner contacts a General Contractor to manage renovation works. A technical expert conducts a survey, prepares a project proposal, and issues a certificate of compliance after the work is completed. The General Contractor then invoices and starts the discount process to redeem the tax credit.
- Scenario 2: Financial Institution, General Contractor, and Investor. The financial institution manages the Investor DAO and Operator DAO. Tokens are minted and distributed to investors and General Contractors. The process involves freezing and minting tokens, burning and releasing tokens, and redeeming tokens against the financial institution.

Based on these premises, we developed the SFCM demonstrator relying upon three pillars: (i) providing a secure and usable environment, (ii) realizing automated and (iii) unbiased control of functionalities, and forecasting risky situations. The architecture consists of a *MAS*, two *DAOs*, and a blockchain integration.

The architecture of the software separates the investors' world from the operators' world, allowing financial institutions to raise funds and tokenise assets, and the process assumes the use of a General Contractor to manage the entire renovation process. Consequently the Secured Fiscal Credit Model implements two DAOs: (i) the Investor DAO allows investors to liaise with financial institutions, while the (ii) Operator DAO acts as a marketplace for financial institutions to distribute tokens to General Contractors. The tokens are redeemable by the financial institution, ensuring transparency and security.

The *DAOs* are developed using the Aragon framework⁵, which is based on the Ethereum network. The framework allows for the creation and governance of organizations, with smart contracts written

⁵<https://www.aragon.org/>, accessed on January 2025

in Solidity⁶.

The *MAS* Module consists of agents with specific roles and actions (see Figure 5.6). The workflow agent represents each Superbonus 110% process, while the General Contractor agent approves financial aspects. Technical agents conduct assessments, and financial agents manage funding and token operations.

Figure 5.6: Multi-agent System architecture of the demonstrator illustrates the interaction between the DAOs and MAS to Superbonus 110% simulation. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36]

The *MAS* framework employed in this study is the MESA framework⁷, a modular architecture written in Python. MESA enables the simulation of complex social systems by creating agents for each actor and designing their interactions within a specified environment. The MESA framework encompasses a variety of tools and modules essential for constructing, executing, and analyzing *MAS* models. These include built-in agent behaviours, scheduling mechanisms, and data collection primitives. The MESA web application framework incorporates visualization tools, such as 2D grid representations of agent instances, time-series graphs related to variables evolution, and tabular data displays while offering real-time interactivity. This interactivity allows users to control simulation parameters and flow (start, pause, and reset), thereby facilitating a thorough analysis and exploration of complex *MAS*. The Agent Roles and Actions modelled in the simulator are the following:

- **Workflow Agent:** Represents each Superbonus 110% process opened. It moves through different states (Open, Anticipation, WPS1, WPS2, EOW) based on the progress of the work and

⁶<https://soliditylang.org/>, accessed on January 2025

⁷<https://mesa.readthedocs.io/stable/>, accessed on January 2025

approvals from other agents. Considering the current state of the workflow agent as x_{cur} , the last asseverated state as x_{asv} , and the previous paid as x_{pay} , the propositional logic notation for such a constraint evaluation is the following:

$$x_{cur}(i+1) \Leftarrow \neg(x(i)_{cur} = x_{asv}(i)) \wedge (x_{asv}(i) = x_{pay}(i)) \wedge \neg x_{arc}(i).$$

- General Contractor Agent: Approves financial aspects and sends payments for the next state of the workflow.
- Technical Agent: Conducts assessments and approvals for the work progress. This class merges the functionalities of both Design Architects and Tax Auditors.
- Financial Agent: Manages funding and token operations, acting as a notary and banking entity.
- Client Agents: Represent homeowners activating Superbonus 110% interventions and appointing General Contractors and technicians.

The demonstrator integrates the Algorand blockchain with the MAS framework. Each agent has a wallet on the Algorand testnet, and smart contracts are written in PyTeal⁸. The integration ensures trust and traceability in transactions. Algorand is a decentralized platform known for its efficient consensus mechanism, enabling fast transaction finality and low fees. Each agent has an ALGO wallet connected to the vault in the testnet. Algorand Smart Contracts are written in Python using the PyTeal library and deployed to the blockchain using the Algorand SDK⁹; they can initiate asset creation and execute payment transactions. The PyTeal library enables these contracts to be written and integrated directly in Python; following we present an example of program implemented for the Paperwork agent.

```

"""
app_pwork_.py
A simple example of PyTeal code to implement the state update of the Paperwork agent
"""
from beaker import *
from pyteal import *

app = Application("PaperworkAgent")

@app.delete(bare=True, authorize=Authorize.only(Global.creator_address()))
def delete() -> Expr:
    return Approve()

@app.external
def update_state(
    actual: abi.String, assevered: abi.String, payed: abi.String, *, output: abi.
    String
) -> Expr:
    return (
        If((actual.get() != assevered.get()) and (actual.get() == payed.get()))

```

⁸<https://pyteal.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>, accessed on January 2025

⁹<https://developer.algorand.org/docs/get-started/algorand/>, accessed on January 2025

```

        .Then(output.set("True"))
        .Else(output.set("False"))
    )

if __name__ == "__main__":
    app.build().export("./artifacts")

```

Listing 5.1: PyTeal program implementing the Paperwork Agent.

We set up and run simulations, as said before, with MESA. The MESA model implemented, named SB110Model, incorporates a grid environment where agents are instantiated with attributes such as unique ID, name, data manager, wallet, *tech_threshold*, and private key. Agent behaviours are specified within the "step" function, which reviews active paperwork, retrieves the current status, verifies assignment to the current technician, and sets an approval probability to simulate real-world scenarios. In Figure 5.7 is presented a screenshot of the emulator, the results of simulation is available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/13742335>) [37]. The code is available on AAAI Github repository (https://github.com/AAAI-DISIM-UnivAQ/Secure_Fiscal_Credit_Model)

Figure 5.7: On the left side, the demonstrator dashboard for setting the parameters is varied by moving each slider, thus modifying the success threshold of each scenario. To the right side is the agent's status during the simulation. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [36]

Agent-Blockchain Connectivity is implemented assigning to each agent a wallet address and a private key. Transaction handling for agents is executed via the *send_transaction* function provided by the Algorand SDK, which verifies transactions using the sender's private key. The MESA MAS environment is integrated with the Algorand blockchain to extend the system-wide benefits of blockchain technology, particularly in terms of trust and traceability.

In conclusions, the study introduces the SFCM, which integrates *MAS* and *DAOs* to enhance the management of the Superbonus 110 tax credit program. The model addresses challenges such as transparency, fraud prevention, and automation, providing a replicable framework for similar tax relief systems worldwide. Future research could explore different fiscal environments, alternative blockchain platforms, and real-time AI-based auditing.

This work lead to the journal publications "Leveraging Multi-Agent Systems and Decentralised Autonomous Organisations for Tax Credit Tracking: A Case Study of the Superbonus 110% in Italy" [36].

5.3 Digital Twin and BC for seismic prevention: the Building Ledger Dossier

In this application we propose an innovative system, called the Building Ledger Dossier, designed to solve pressing issues of traceability, certification, and accountability in seismic prevention. It's a technical framework designed as a mix of technologies, such as Digital Twins, blockchain, and Tokenization of assets.

Earthquakes have long been a significant concern in Italy, a country where the historical buildings along with old housing constructions are know for their vulnerability to seismic activity. Over the past few decades, devastating earthquakes in regions like Abruzzo and Central Italy have highlighted the precarious state of many buildings. These events exposed a high risk situation: many structures were constructed long before seismic codes became a norm, leaving them vulnerable to earthquakes. Building Ledger Dossier takes on the challenge of improving how seismic interventions on buildings are tracked and managed.

The key technologies and concepts that underlay the system are (i) *NFT* that provides a virtual representation of a building, incorporating its geometry, physics, and behaviour to simulate real-world responses to seismic events; (ii) Tokenization which converts real-world building data and documentation into digital assets (*NFT*) stored on a blockchain. (iii) *DAOs* to facilitate decentralized governance, enabling efficient decision-making and validation processes for seismic interventions. These three paradigms are integrated and orchestrated in a *MAS* where special agents superintend to functions such as Interpretability, blockchain and *DAOs* management; while each building is modelled through a Building Dossier Agent. Let's examine deeper such paradigms and how them interact, in Figure 5.8 is proposed a diagram of interaction of the whole Building Ledger Dossier system. A *Digital Twin (DT)* is a virtual model of a physical structure that mirrors its geometry, behaviour, and historical data. By using digital twins, the system ensures that every aspect of the building, from its initial construction plans to its most recent seismic upgrade, is accurately represented in a virtual environment. The system operates through a multi-level architecture involving several components:

1. *DT* Representation: a comprehensive model of the building is created using Open Sees¹⁰, a framework that simulates how the structure would respond to seismic events. This helps in both designing and validating interventions.
2. Blockchain for Accountability: all data related to a building's interventions are stored on a blockchain. This makes it virtually impossible to falsify records or hide information.
3. Tokenization: *NFT* are used to represent individual components of the building's documentation. Each token corresponds to a specific piece of data, such as a set of photographs, a project report, or certification of compliance.

¹⁰<https://opensees.berkeley.edu/>, accessed on January 2025

Figure 5.8: MAS architecture of Building Ledger Dossier. Three types of agents allow accountability, DAOs management, and interaction with smart contracts. DLT blocks are also presented to provide a more precise understanding of MAS functions. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [34]

4. *DAOs*: the governance of the system is decentralized. Using *DAOs*, key stakeholders—like contractors, inspectors, and owners—can participate in approving and validating interventions. This ensures transparency and reduces the risk of fraud or bias.

The aim is to track all seismic interventions made to a building, whether it’s installing reinforcement plates, applying ant, seismic mesh, or fortifying the foundation — and record them in a way that cannot be altered, manipulated, or lost. The Building Ledger Dossier, leveraging these theoretical concepts; implements practical solution with far-reaching implications, offering several benefits:

- **Enhanced Transparency:** All stakeholders can view a building’s seismic intervention history, fostering trust and accountability.
- **Improved Traceability:** With *NFT* linked to every intervention, tracking the lifecycle of a building becomes straightforward.

- **Data Integrity:** Blockchain ensures that records are secure, unalterable, and easy to verify.

These features are meant to solve a problem in building sector: seismic repairs and upgrades often leave behind incomplete or unreliable documentation. Over time, critical information about what interventions were performed, when, and by whom gets lost. Even when records exist, verifying their authenticity can be tricky. For instance, a photograph of a completed project could be edited or misrepresented, leaving no way to guarantee its accuracy and geographical position.

This lack of traceability can be an important issue in legal disputes, inspections, or even future restoration projects. The Building Ledger Dossier aims to address this by creating a secure, transparent, and tamper-proof digital record of a building's lifecycle.

We implemented a real-world scenario demonstrator, focused on blockchain interaction, that allows to manage the installation of plates on joints of an existing building. Every step of the process is recorded on the blockchain, making the data impossible to tamper with. The documentation, including photographs, project details, and certifications, is tokenized using *NFT*.

Usually, after modelling the structure of a building, the designer engineer produce a project to restore a building using steel plates and steel nets to reinforce a building's facade. The work and its accompanying documentation (photos, GPS coordinates, project approvals) are implemented by a Contractor and directed and certified by a Director of Works (DoW). We can model such process of installing anti-seismic plates on a building in the following steps:

1. **Planning:** The building owner initiates a new intervention by creating a digital record in the system hiring an Engineer to operate in his behalf. This includes uploading project details and assigning roles to stakeholders like contractors and inspectors.
2. **Execution:** During the work, the Contractor Installer uses a mobile application to document every step—taking photos, tagging GPS coordinates, and uploading relevant certifications.
3. **Validation:** The project supervisor or Director of Works (DoW) reviews the uploaded data, ensures compliance with the approved plans, and verifies the work's quality.
4. **Blockchain Integration:** Once approved, the entire record, complete with time stamps and signatures, is stored on the blockchain as a series of *NFT*. From this point on, the data cannot be altered or deleted.

This process, modelled in the sequence diagram of Figure 5.9, is not just about documentation. It also enhances trust and transparency in fact whether an inspector, a building owner, or a regulatory authority, can access at any time a tamper-proof record of the building's history with just a few clicks. This work has been presented to PAAMS 2024 along with the demonstrator and published to Conference proceedings [34]. The software has been developed in collaboration with the engineering company Studio Berkana Srl and innovative startup BCC Studio Srl: the demo is available at the following address: <http://bccstudio.biz/plates/> while code is reserved due to copyright reasons.

5.4 DLT, MAS and DAOs for Cognitive Robotics

The field of cognitive robotics integrates artificial intelligence and robotics to create autonomous agents capable of complex decision-making. These agents interact with their environment via structured layers:

Figure 5.9: Sequence diagram of Plates installation. Two actors, DoW and Installer, interact to install, produce proof documentation and certify works on BC. Courtesy of De Gasperis et al. [34]

1. Decision-Making Layer: Analyzes perceptions and sets goals.
2. Central Layer: Processes perceptions and feedback.
3. Peripheral Layer: Manages hardware, sensors, and actuators.

In this section we present two works focussed on integration of intelligent systems in robotics with DLT both on single robot and swarm robots scenarios.

5.4.1 Enhancing Robotics with Advanced Reasoning Capabilities: SkRobot with TeleoR/QuLog

The complexity of designing cognitive robots requires efficient platforms and middleware. In this section we introduce SkRobot, a robust framework based on the SpecialK C++ platform (see De Gasperis et al. [33]), extended with TeleoR and QuLog to enable reasoning capabilities. The system

allows for real-time decision-making and behaviour modelling in robotic applications. A demonstration of the integration is provided through a virtual simulation on Coppelia Sim¹¹, involving a NAO humanoid robot [67] completing a target retrieval task. A key challenge in cognitive robotics is achieving real-time performance while handling distributed systems and integrating advanced reasoning mechanisms. The SkRobot framework was developed to address these needs, employing the FlowProtocol communication model for robust data exchange. This paper expands the SkRobot framework, with reasoning systems based on TeleoR and QuLog, presented in Section 4.5.2, to enhance decision-making.

Middleware simplifies robotic development by abstracting complex tasks such as data brokering and hardware control. Prominent examples include:

- ROS (Robot Operating System): A versatile middleware offering modular tools for navigation, perception, and control; However, ROS has limitations, such as high setup complexity and OS dependency [116];
- Redis: Widely used for real-time data management in distributed systems [18].

The SkRobot application leverages the SpecialK C++ framework, which supports distributed processing and pseudo-real-time synchronization. Features include (i) Active data brokering, (ii) Event-driven programming with Signal/Slot mechanisms and (iii) Lightweight dependency management for flexibility across platforms.

On this architecture we added Rule-Based Languages for Reasoning, in particular we integrated TeleoR/QuLog to provide a logical reasoning layer for robotic agents. We briefly recall that: (i) TeleoR is a teleological programming language with typed, parameterized procedures; while (ii) QuLog is a higher-order logic language for querying and decision-making. These tools enable robots to interpret sensory data and adapt behavior to achieve specific goals. The integration of these paradigms into SkRobot required modifications to the FlowNetwork architecture, facilitating reasoning and decision-making within robotic systems. The approach enhances SkRobot's ability to:

1. Collect and process perceptions from sensors;
2. Execute logical reasoning using production rules;
3. Communicate decisions effectively to other system components.

In Figure 5.10 is represented a simple scheme of the TeleoR Agent.

On the communication and data flow side, the FlowProtocol ensures efficient inter-process communication via structured binary frames. Key features include: Parallelism and functional asynchrony, Support for synchronous (blocking) and asynchronous (non-blocking) commands, and modular FlowNetwork channels for data distribution (see Figure 5.11a and 5.11b for an architectural example). The Signal/Slot mechanism in SkRobot, instead enables flexible inter-object communication without mutexes or semaphores. Signals trigger Slots, which execute predefined actions. Connection modes include:

- Direct invocation;
- Queued execution for asynchronous operations; -

¹¹<https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/>, accessed on December 2024

Figure 5.10: Simple Two Thread TeleoR Agent Architecture. Courtesy of D’Ottavio et al. [32]

- OneShot connections for single-use tasks.

The integration with TeleoR/QuLog was achieved using a Python-based satellite, combining Flow-Protocol (from SkRobot) with the Pedro message broker (for TeleoR). This satellite implement specific tasks:

1. Captures perceptions from sensors
2. Forwards data to TeleoR for reasoning
3. Receives and executes action decisions

The architecture ensures seamless communication between distributed components while leveraging TeleoR’s logical reasoning capabilities.

The work was tested on a Proof of Concept of a NAO Robot Simulation to demonstrate the possibility of integration of aforesaid paradigms; in particular the task involved retrieving a red ball placed on a table. Key components of the simulation are the following:

- Sensors: Sonar and camera for detecting objects.
- Perceptions: Represented as logical facts (e.g., ‘see(ball, left)’).
- Decision-Making: Controlled by a TeleoR program (see Listing 5.2) that planned and executed actions to approach and retrieve the ball.

```

def dir ::= left | centre | right
def object ::= ball | duck
  
```


Figure 5.11: (a) Satellites in a Mono-centralized FlowNetwork. They are applications that manage sensors and actuators exchanging data with SkRobots. (b) Multi-centralized FlowNetwork/DipoleNetwork where multiple hubs have their own satellites, arrows are P2P connections. Courtesy of D’Ottavio et al. [32]

```
percept holding(), see(num, dir)
```

Listing 5.2: TeleoR example program for object recognition

The robot successfully executed the task, validating the integration of TeleoR/QuLog into SkRobot. The simulation highlighted the system’s ability to both respond to sensory inputs in real time and adapt actions dynamically based on feedback. The NAO robot [67] has been simulated with the Coppelia robot simulator¹², in a simple scene with a table where on top lays a red ball. The NAO sensors are the two torso sonars, left and right, and the frontal camera. The NaoSat from the sensor readings creates the perceptions to determine where the red ball is seen in the visual range of the camera. It then subscribes to the PedroSat/TeleoR notify channel to receive motion commands. The QuLog/TeleoR agent program receives perceptions as QuLog-subscribe string, through a service-channel, and plans accordingly the motion command to engage, with the main TeleoR program in Listing 5.3:

```
tel collect_object()
collect_object(){
    taken()
    ~> ()
    too_close()
    ~> get_next_to()
```

¹²<https://www.coppeliarobotics.com>, last accessed July 2024

Figure 5.12: Simulation of the NAO humanoid robot after running the QuLog/TeleoR control program, getting close to its target. Courtesy of D’Ottavio et al. [32]

```

next_to(centre)
  ~> grab()
next_to(Dir)
  ~> turn(Dir, 0.2)
holding()
  ~> release()
true
  ~> get_next_to()
}

```

Listing 5.3: TeleoR example program for object recognition

Fig.5.12 shows the simulation with the NAO humanoid robot right before accomplishing the task of finding and grabbing the target red ball, after the exploration of the environment. With SkRobot we introduced a reasoning-enabled middleware for distributed robotic systems, Demonstrating pseudo-real-time decision-making capabilities and scalability for multi-robot scenarios. The framework offers thus potential benefits for:

- Swarm robotics in industrial automation;
- Autonomous exploration in unstructured environments;
- Cognitive systems requiring reasoning under resource constraints.

The integration of TeleoR/QuLog into SkRobot marks a significant step toward intelligent robotic systems capable of reasoning and dynamic planning. By enabling robust communication, distributed processing, and logical decision-making, this framework lays the groundwork for advancements in cognitive and swarm robotics. This work has been presented to ICINCO2024 International Conference and published to its Proceedings [32].

5.4.2 Increasing Accountability in Swarm Robotics: HST-4 Architecture

With this work we want to explore how integrating *XAI* and *DLT* into Swarm Robotics (SR) to enhance trust, explainability, and accountability in *Human-swarm teaming (HST)*. Addressing ethical concerns and decision-making complexities in SR, we ultimately propose the HST-4 architecture, an extension of the HST-3 model of Endsley [49], introducing Accountability and leveraging technologies like *DAOs*.

Endsley's *SA* is vital for human-in-the-loop decision-making and relies on three core tenets for transparency:

1. Interpretability, which involves understanding the algorithm's internal structure and mapping input-output relationships;
2. Explainability, focusing on comprehending individual parameters and the causal relationships between inputs and outputs, while also aiming for global transparency in the decision process;
3. Predictability, referring to the ability to foresee an agent's future behaviour.

In swarm robotics, challenges such as non-cooperative behaviours and communication delays are common. Hepworth et al. [71] proposed the HST-3 architecture, a three-tier model of *HST* encompassing agent knowledge, an inference engine, and communication. We extend this architecture to improve Transparency, Explainability, Accountability, and Communication security.

Two key challenges in human-swarm interaction are (i) conveying the global goal to robots and (ii) issuing collaborative instructions. The Smart Shepherding approach addresses these issues by considering the swarm's well-being while guiding them. The human controller, or "shepherd," must understand the agents' cognitive structure. A shepherding swarm ontology can explain agent decisions, integrating elements of *XAI*. Abbas et al. [1] highlight the use of a contextual *SA* architecture and Reynolds' three-level model in Swarm Shepherding.

These paradigms are meant to improve the hot topics of research that at the moment are

- Transparency in HST: Internal and external transparency is critical for interpreting swarm and individual robot behaviours. Simplified information systems mitigate operator overload.
- Non-cooperative Scenarios: Ensuring secure communication and handling disruptive agents through tokenized incentives and blockchain-based verification.
- Hardware Reliability: Addressing limitations in sensors and computational power to prevent failures in path planning and communication.

In this context the proposed HST-4 model, represented in the block scheme of Figure 5.13 introduces an Accountability Module within the HST-3 architecture, leveraging *DLT* for robust tracking and transparency of agent actions. It includes a Publish/Subscribe communication bus for efficient data transmission and modular interaction among system components. Three levels of blockchain integration are proposed, this to differentiate scenarios based on timing requirements:

- Full-Blockchain: Each robot is a blockchain node, ensuring high transparency but with latency challenges.
- Semi-Blockchain: Select nodes operate on the blockchain, balancing speed and security.

- Non-Blockchain: Uses alternative *DLT* like *DAGs* for real-time scalability.

Figure 5.13: The HST-4 Block Diagram. It is derived from a modification of the one in [71]. We enhanced it by adding a Publish/Subscribe channel and DLT functions. In white are represented novel elements that extend the original blocks in gray.

We implemented, to test integration of *DLT* with Swarm Robots in a near real time-environment, a simulation using CoppeliaSim and relying on the the IOTA Tangle¹³. This is a *DLT* a solution based on a *DAGs* network that implement transactions and certifications on each node while executes a very light proof-of-work when adding a new transaction in order to prevent spam and Sybil attacks. New Transactions are at the border of the graph and are unconfirmed while connections to other nodes are Edges and represent a certification performed by a certification node of the net (see Figure 5.14 for a visualization of these concepts). To append a new transaction a node needs to confirm another two transactions, in this way, the network speeds up when transactions rise (more nodes elaborate transactions) fostering also more scalability. As the graph rises in dimension, transactions have a cumulative weight calculated by summing the weight of entering sites, the higher the weight the higher the trust of transactions.

nft

The interaction environment for the *DLT* was configured using a Docker container running on Docker Desktop. This setup utilized the IOTA Sandbox¹⁴, a suite of tools offering essential primitives to connect with the IOTA network. For this project, the IOTA Testnet served as the connection point. Integration with CoppeliaSim was achieved through the Coppelia Remote API Client, enabling direct simulation management via a Python-based program. Each robot logs pertinent information—such as its selected actions—by encoding this data as a string within a *NFT* and transmitting it to the accountability agent’s wallet. All transactions are publicly accessible

¹³<https://www.iota.org> last access January 2025

¹⁴<https://wiki.iota.org/iota-sandbox/welcome> last access January 2025

Figure 5.14: IOTA transactions happen in 3 steps. The node creates the transaction (violet) and signs it with a private key, then chooses two unconfirmed transactions (green) using a random algorithm and finally solves a hash to finalize the operation. In blue existing confirmed transactions.

Figure 5.15: Coppelia Simulation environment. The swarm of three Pioneer P3DX robots moves inside a fence trying to avoid obstacles. The simulation is connected to IOTA Sandbox through a Python module that starts it and reads the decisions taken by robots.

and visible on the IOTA Explorer ¹⁵, This ensures that the data remains inspectable, immutable, and timestamped, providing a transparent record of activity (refer to Figure 5.16). From a computational perspective, the simulation employs a multi-threaded architecture. Seventeen threads are allocated to Docker containers for setting up the local IOTA Sandbox, while each Pioneer robot instance operates four dedicated threads for perception, assertion, planning, and actuation. The

¹⁵<https://explorer.iota.org/iota-testnet> last access January 2025

DLT's performance, particularly in the context of minting and transmitting *NFT*, is highly efficient. On average, the production and delivery of *NFT* are completed within a few tenths of a second, highlighting *IOTA*'s suitability as a platform for supporting near real-time applications.

Figure 5.16: Transactions on IOTA Testnet Explorer. Each action executed by the robots (in this case "turn left") is minted as an *NFT* along with relevant information and timestamping. The *NFT* is then sent to the Accountability agent wallet. Each transaction is public and visible on IOTA Testnet.

This research establishes a foundation for integrating accountability in swarm systems via *DLT*. Future directions include:

- Testing HST-4 in real-world applications.
- *DAOs* integration for collective decision-making.
- Evaluating system performance under complex and dynamic scenarios.

The HST-4 architecture represents a significant step in SR by addressing transparency, security, and scalability challenges. By combining *XAI*, *DLT*, and *DAOs* principles, the paper provides a pathway for enhancing trust and operational reliability in human-swarm teaming systems.

This work has been presented at FAIEMA 2024 International Conference, proceedings are in course of publication.

5.5 Connecting and Using DAO via Scripting

To conclude the presentation of the applications implemented, we briefly introduce a test-bed developed to try integration among Intelligent Agents and *DAOs*. This activity was performed in collaboration with an innovative startup BCC Studio, with the aim of developing a system to create and manage *DAOs* and connected assets (*FT* and *NFT*). In the example presented here, we simulate

Figure 5.17: Decision block scheme to model a robot trying to enter an already formed swarm.

a robot trying to enter an already formed swarm. The logic of the process is synthetized in Figure 5.17: when a request from an external robot n arrives, the receiving robot m connects to the *DAOs* representing the swarm and set up a vote proposal. Each robot belonging to the swarm votes then yes or not to the resolution based on it's own logic. For example may evaluate the trustfulness of the robot 'n' relying on the formula presented in Section 4.1

$$vote_yes \iff T_m(n) \geq r_{m_n}.$$

In case the majority of the participants vote 'yes', the new robot n is added to the *DAOs* swarm by sending him a membership token; each robot has its own wallet on the selected blockchain (in this case Polygon¹⁶). Trough a typescript program, which in real scenario could be integrated in

¹⁶<https://polygon.technology/>, accessed on January 2025

the *DAOs* Management module of Agent architecture (See Figure 3.1), the agent installs a admin plugin to set up the wallet based *DAOs* (at the first execution) and through its wallet set up also the vote proposal. As we can see from Figure 5.18, the script `add – robot – proposal.ts` is executed in an Hardhat¹⁷ environment; it generates a vote proposal named 'NEW SWARM ROBOT' and set its parameters (eg. approval threshold to 0.5). Relative digital signatures and wallets of agent, *DAOs* and newly created vote proposal are generated on the Aragon *DAO* related to the swarm robot and thus on the Polygon network hosting Aragon system. At this point other agents may cast their vote based on the intelligent logic as aforesaid described. On the Aragon side, we can see on

```
nix@dev:~/BCC-aragon/BCC-DAO-dec_2024/sandi$ npx hardhat run scripts/deploy/add-robot-proposal.ts --network sepolia
Compiled 36 Solidity files successfully (evm target: paris).
## Add new robot proposal
Init Params: {
  subdomain: 'new-robot-003',
  name: 'NEW SWARM ROBOT',
  description: 'Generate proposal on token based DAO',
  votingSetting: {
    votingMode: 1,
    supportThreshold: 0.5,
    minParticipation: 0.25,
    minDuration: 3600
  },
  tokenSetting: { name: 'Swarm', symbol: 'SWM', decimal: 18, initValue: 1000 }
},
{
  key: 'creating',
  txHash: '0x35fe51c82e56ce8370f84a5de325f94560e8b928a0ea1ebfe49810204b68580d'
}
{
  key: 'done',
  address: '0x809d5cC5a115071ABfb1071FACC27e5807c975dF',
  pluginAddresses: [ '0x087b7306d0B2fCA043396Af55Cbb066DF1d35F80' ]
}
DAO addresses {
  daoAddress: '0x809d5cC5a115071ABfb1071FACC27e5807c975dF',
  tokenVotingAddress: '0x087b7306d0B2fCA043396Af55Cbb066DF1d35F80'
}
Waiting 30 second
Installing new robot proposal
START GRANT PERMISSIONS FOR DAO
Permission for new robot proposal
Proposal created: 0
```

Figure 5.18: Typescript execution results of a robot in a swarm setting up a *DAO* and a Voting Poll.

the *DAOs* console (See Figure 5.19) the result of the correspondent operations undertaken by the agents. This demonstrator is the base for a wider project that aims to develop specific *Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)* for interacting with Blockchain technology, primarily for managing *DAOs* and *NFT*. Those *APIs* will activate a range of functions for managing *DAOs* and interacting with various blockchain-based assets, with a focus on user wallets, reputation systems, *NFT*, and community governance. Here's a summary of the key functions:

1. User Wallet Management: The *APIs* allows for the addition or removal of user wallets in each *DAOs* by managing the unique membership tokens. This validates user wallets within the system. It checks if a user's Metamask ERC20 wallet is enabled by verifying the presence of a specific membership token.
2. Internal Payment Tokens: The *APIs* manages internal payment tokens specific to each *DAOs*, which are used exclusively for services within that community. The system verifies that these tokens enable the user's Metamask ERC20 wallet.

¹⁷<https://hardhat.org/>, accessed on January 2025

NEW SWARM ROBOT
Published by you
Generate proposal on token based DAO

Read full proposal

SwarmRo... Governance > Proposal Executed Give feedback 0x453...4271

Voting
Proposal executed

Option	Count	Percentage
Yes	1000 SWM	100%
No	0 SWM	0%
Abstain	0 SWM	0%

Vote over

Actions
These actions can be executed only once the governance parameters are met.

grant 0x809d...75df DAO

Grants permission to an address to call methods in a contract guarded by an auth modifier with the specified permission identifier.

_where
The address of the target contract for which `^_who` receives permission.
0xc24188a73dc09aa7c721f96ad8857b469c01dc9f Copy

_who
The address (EOA or contract) receiving the permission.
0x453c2aa2716310306b96a8c1d750f7a1748f4271 Copy

_permissionId
The permission identifier.
0xf796b89427c6552c1ac705d833fb7909f8eb5ce502c1db97185abc6ad...

Status

- Published 2025/01/23 11:06 AM UTC+1 7,553,275
- Running 2025/01/23 11:06 AM UTC+1
- Succeeded 2025/01/23 11:06 AM UTC+1
- Executed 2025/01/23 11:06 AM UTC+1 7,553,275

Figure 5.19: Aragon DAO Console illustrating wallets and a voting poll details.

3. **Token and Asset Verification:** The API reads token data across different *DAOs* to check security ACLs and update the user's control dashboard. It also facilitates the issuance of new "like" tokens within user wallets, which can later be converted into "reputation-like" tokens after being used by the user to appreciate something.
4. **NFT Minting and Management:** Users can mint NFTs (e.g., robots decisions to turn left or right), interact with IPFS for storage, and manage these *NFT* within their wallets. The API includes typical NFT minting options, such as adding royalties on future sales. It also enables interaction with a marketplace for buying or selling NFTs and checks the originality and validity of NFTs
5. **Legal Validity and *DAOs* Creation:** The *APIs* integrates with a patented IAC system to ensure legal validity for digital transactions. It also includes API calls for the dynamic creation of *DAOs* using the Aragon system.

Chapter 6

Discussion, Conclusions and Future Works

In this Section, to conclude our thesis, we resume the innovative contributions given to the field of Cognitive Intelligent Agents and try to respond to the Research Questions enunciated in Section 1.6 that we briefly recall:

- RQ1: How to define Explainability and Trust by design?
- RQ2: How to add Explainability and Trust by design in Intelligent Systems fostering its ex-ante application?
- RQ3: What are the application fields of Explainable Intelligent Systems?

We also discuss weak points of the architectures and solutions proposed, and finally envision possible future works and stem of research in the field. We remember that, the main problem addressed by the Doctoral work, is a solution to cope with the lack of general paradigms to foster ex-ante Explainability and Trust in the area of Cognitive Intelligent Systems. This problem, as explained in Section 2.1, is more and more important especially in Europe where regulatory framework on AI require mandatory Explainability.

Let's then examine in the next points the single questions and possible future developments of the research in this sector, while finally a resume of papers and articles published during the PhD Course is reported in Appendix A.

6.1 Definition of Trust and Explainability

We answered to the first Research Question (RQ1) giving initially a picture of Trust in Cognitive single Agents. In Section 1.5.1 we modelled it as a function measuring in the range domain $[0..1]$, based on the capability to maintain contractual agreements and accept some level of risk of not fulfilling them. Both of these properties are defined ex-ante, or before the use of the agent. We introduced also the warranted trust concept for agents and the Intrinsic and Extrinsic trust. Explainability on the other side has been considered (See Section 1.5.2) as a property deriving from ethical frameworks, described as empirical needs coming from experience, and connecting the Situation Awareness model for practical agents application. The definitions are given, like per Trust,

as ex-ante properties of the Agents and thus must be encoded in the intelligent part of the Agent. On this regard we proposed a modification of the Cognitive Agent introducing a specific module as per Figure 1.2.

In Section 4.1 and 4.2 we extended the concept of ex-ante Trust and Explainability to *MAS* environments possibly interacting through a *DAOs*. We introduced an innovative perspective on Trust, defining it as a multidimensional vector that every agent builds up to evaluate each other agent composing the *MAS*. Each component of the vector is a property defined ex-ante and well clear to the whole system (eg. Age of the agent in the system, Speed of response in previous interactions or tasks, etc.). We also modelled a second type of Trust definition related to the confidence of voting in *DAOs* as a weighted sum combining Reputation of agents and Trust. These descriptions clearly define Trust and Explainability both in a single agent configuration and for Intelligent System potentially composed of many interacting agents. Finally we also envisioned a method to measure the level of trust in multi-agent environments, modelling trustworthy system through Fuzzy Logic in Section 4.4.

6.2 Adding Trust and Explainability

In order to answer RQ2, we had to introduce an innovative architecture relying upon an innovative combination of existing paradigms and new technologies. After reviewing the classic architecture of multi-layer agents and the *BDI* paradigm, the solution envisioned was the extension of the Computational Agent introduced by Poole and Macworth (See Figure 1.1) to foster Explainability and Trust by design, we called this new extended model the Explainable Computational Agent (See Figure 3.1). This new instrument introduces a new layer to manage all the technologies and paradigm need to foster Explainability in intelligent systems, but also sees the Decision-making layer under a different perspective.

In the Explainability layer (See Section 3.1.4), we deployed the management core functions to consent use the three leg architecture composed by *DLT*, *MAS* and *DAOs*. This to add trackability, accountability, transparency and ultimately explainability to the whole system. This methods allow thus to design an ex-ante system containing the wanted properties and the searched level of Explainability, allowing to modulate the Intelligent System in function of user's request (higher or lower level of Trust expected), environment nature (eg. need of real-time acquisition and actions) and other constraints like costs.

For the Decision-making layer we proposed several framework combinations to enhance the ex-ante intelligence in agents in Section 3.2: Production Rules, Reasoning and Constraints Knowledge Base. To implement them we selected three logic-based programming languages DALI, tailored for multi-agents with proactive and reactive behaviour, and TeleoR/QuLog very effective in robotics as, in combination, solve the need of goal-directed behaviour mixed with data management.

Solution proposed where Explainability and Decision-making layers cooperate for Trust and Explainability are:

- Implementing Intelligent functions and programs on Smart Contracts to guarantee behaviour is predictable and uniform before the system is running and ex-post.
- Register messaging and decisions between layers and environments on *DLT* to make them

inspectable, immutable and time-stamped at run-time.

- Use *MAS* and *DAOs* to make decisions in complex environments, fostering thus transparency and clarity both since before the system is running and at run-time.

To sum up, the known paradigms in combination with new and innovative solutions are able to define an organic architecture and a set of methods to add Trust and Explainability by design in Cognitive Intelligent Systems.

6.3 Applications to Real World Scenarios

Following the definition of new paradigms and the innovative combination of established techniques, we have sought to apply these approaches to real-world scenarios in order to test the applicability of the proposed architectures and methods to practical problems. In the final section of this thesis, we summarize the applications and demonstrators that have been developed, focusing primarily on the lower levels of the architecture and the integration of *DLT*/Blockchain environments with multi-agent intelligent systems.

In particular, we conducted a survey of various *DLT* deployments, including permissionless blockchains such as Algorand, permissioned *DLT* like Corda, and *DLT* based on *DAGs* such as IOTA. These technologies were tested across diverse scenarios, ranging from economics (Section 5.1) and tax credits (Section 5.2) to construction (Section 5.3) and robotics (Sections 5.4.1 and 5.4.2). The tested scenarios provide a foundational case history in this emerging area of application research. The results obtained are promising and demonstrate the potential for real-world deployment of Explainable Computational Agents.

However, the usability of the system is currently highly dependent on the temporal requirements of the scenarios. Non-real-time use cases involving a small number of transactions can be successfully addressed using commercial blockchains, despite their low response times and potentially high transaction fees. This is particularly suitable for applications such as construction, document management systems, and financial scenarios that we have tested.

For robotics, where quasi-real-time scenarios are typically required, our experiments successfully tested the IOTA public test-net with software simulations of swarm robots. However, when real robots are involved, it may be necessary to explore the use of localized *DLT* networks to meet the stringent real-time requirements.

6.4 Future Works

The future development of the proposed framework should address two main research directions, each targeting critical advancements in the fields of *DLT*, *MAS*, and *DAOs*. These developments aim to improve scalability, autonomy, and efficiency in the application of these technologies to practical and real-world scenarios.

6.4.1 Real-Time *DLT* Deployment in Swarm Robotics

The first research direction involves advancing the integration of *DLT* within swarm robotics, focusing on real-time deployments using physical robots. While initial experiments have validated the

feasibility of integrating *DLT* into simulated swarm robotic systems, significant challenges remain in extending these findings to real-world robotic platforms; let's explore some important ones:

- **Challenges in Real-Time Integration:** Swarm robotics inherently involves the coordination of multiple agents operating in dynamic and often unpredictable environments. Traditional *DLT* architectures, particularly those employing *PoW* or *PoS* consensus mechanisms, are often unsuitable for real-time applications due to high latency and transaction costs. Deploying *DLT* directly on robotic platforms represents a promising approach to mitigate these challenges. By transforming each robot into a node within a decentralized network, the system can achieve low-latency communication, localized consensus, and virtually cost-free transactions. One of the primary challenges in this area is optimizing resource usage on resource-constrained robotic platforms. Robots, especially those designed for swarm behavior, often have limited computational power, memory, and energy reserves. Implementing a lightweight, resource-efficient *DLT* protocol is critical to ensure that the added computational overhead does not hinder the robot's primary functions, such as navigation, sensing, and task execution.
- **Promising Technologies: IOTA and Sui:** Two *DLT* technologies stand out as promising candidates for this application: IOTA and Sui¹. (i) IOTA employs a *DLT* structure rather than a traditional blockchain. This architecture eliminates the need for miners and transaction fees, enabling low-cost, high-speed transactions. IOTA's Tangle architecture allows for parallelized transaction validation, making it particularly well-suited for scenarios where multiple nodes (robots) simultaneously interact within a localized network. Additionally, its energy-efficient nature aligns with the constraints of robotic platforms. (ii) Sui, on the other hand, is a novel *DLT* platform that utilizes a delegated proof-of-stake (dPoS) consensus mechanism combined with an object-centric data model. Sui's approach to parallel transaction processing and low-latency consensus mechanisms makes it an attractive candidate for real-time robotic applications. Its ability to manage state transitions efficiently aligns well with the dynamic state changes that characterize swarm robotic systems.
- **Proposed Implementation and Evaluation:** Future research should focus on the deployment of these technologies in real robotic environments. This involves: (i) *DLT* Node Deployment: Each robot should be equipped with the necessary hardware and software to function as a node in the *DLT* network. This includes implementing lightweight client libraries compatible with IOTA or Sui. (ii) Performance Metrics: The system should be evaluated based on metrics such as transaction latency, energy consumption, and the impact on robotic tasks. Stress-testing the network under high transaction loads will provide valuable insights into scalability.

6.4.2 Enhanced Integration of DAOs

The second research direction focuses on enhancing the role of *DAOs* within the decision-making framework. While the current implementation utilizes the Aragon DAO platform for demonstration purposes, future developments should aim to integrate *DAOs* more deeply into the architecture, leveraging private and localized *DLT* to improve efficiency and reduce costs.

¹<https://sui.io/>, accessed on January 2025

The existing DAO implementation relies on public platforms, such as Aragon, which introduce several limitations. Public *DLT* often incur high transaction fees and exhibit slower response times due to network congestion and the global scale of the consensus process. These drawbacks hinder the adoption of *DAOs* in scenarios requiring rapid decision-making and high transaction throughput, such as swarm robotics or financial markets. Moreover, the current integration of *DAOs* does not fully exploit their potential for autonomous decision-making in multi-agent systems. *DAOs* can serve as a powerful tool for orchestrating decentralized decision-making processes, enabling agents to vote on critical decisions, allocate resources, and resolve conflicts without centralized oversight.

1. **Private *DLT* and Smart Contract Optimization:** To overcome these limitations, future research should explore the deployment of *DAOs* on private or consortium-based *DLT*. Private *DLT* offer several advantages: (i) **Low Latency:** By limiting the network to a predefined set of nodes, private *DLTs* can achieve significantly faster consensus times. (ii) **Cost Efficiency:** Transaction costs are minimized as there is no need to incentivize a global network of validators. (iii) **Customizability:** Private *DLTs* can be tailored to meet specific application requirements, such as integrating domain-specific voting mechanisms or resource allocation algorithms.
2. **Smart Contracts for Localized Decision-Making:** Future work should focus on designing and implementing smart contracts that facilitate localized decision-making. These contracts can encode rules for voting, resource allocation, and task assignment, enabling agents to collaborate autonomously within a decentralized framework.

The enhanced DAO integration proposed should be evaluated through a series of experimental scenarios, including:

- **Decision-Making Efficiency:** Measure the time required to reach consensus on critical decisions in both public and private *DLT* environments.
- **Transaction Throughput:** Evaluate the system's ability to handle a high volume of transactions under varying network conditions.
- **Scalability:** Test the scalability of the DAO framework by increasing the number of participating agents and the complexity of decision-making tasks.
- **Resilience:** Assess the system's ability to maintain functionality under adverse conditions, such as node failures or malicious attacks.

6.4.3 Integration of Cognitive and Generative AI: LLM as Perception Tools for Facts Grounding

The last promising research direction we propose is the integration of the two key paradigms of *AI* examined in the previous sections: Cognitive and Generative AI. The idea is to leverage the strengths and specializations of each paradigm to enhance both the performance and trustworthiness of the entire computational system.

A potential implementation of this approach involves using *LLMs* to analyze vast amounts of data available in the environment where Intelligent Agents operate. If we consider the possible stimuli present in the environment as a dataset, we can train a Transformer on this data and

employ a *LLMs* to process and extract meaningful patterns and insights. In this way, the *LLMs* layer can be seen as a generator of perceptions transforming raw stimuli into structured, enriched information—to be used for Facts Grounding. In logic, Facts Grounding refers to the process of linking abstract logical statements or propositions to concrete, real-world facts or data, ensuring that logical reasoning is not only syntactically correct but also corresponds to actual truths within a given domain. The use of *LLMs* as a perception tool can facilitate the following:

- Connecting to the real environment: logical statements must be verifiable against real-world observations or empirical data. Mapping symbols to data is crucial for aligning abstract concepts (e.g., "Colosseum amphitheater") with factual descriptions (e.g., "located in Rome, Italy").
- Enhancing semantic interpretation: symbols and predicates in a formal system gain meaning based on real-world facts, improving contextual understanding.
- Enriching the ontological basis and *KB* of the Intelligent Agent: a logical system often requires an ontology or a structured representation of entities and their relationships within a domain. This is particularly relevant for Natural Language Understanding (NLU), where *LLMs* can interpret ambiguous user inputs and relate them to structured data.
- Verifying and validating rule applications: logical inferences must be checked against a ground truth to ensure their correctness, reducing the risk of erroneous reasoning.

However, using *LLMs* for Facts Grounding presents several limitations: (i) Hallucination problems, as *LLMs* may generate plausible but incorrect facts. (ii) Lack of real-world interaction, since they lack direct sensory perception or empirical verification capabilities. (iii) Static knowledge, as most *LLMs* are trained on historical data and may not reflect recent changes in the world. In real-time environments, this could pose a significant limitation.

To address these challenges, a Hybrid AI approach integrating *LLMs* with structured knowledge sources (e.g., knowledge graphs, databases) could significantly improve Facts Grounding. Promising configurations include:

- Neuro-Symbolic AI: combining *LLMs* with formal reasoning systems.
- *LLMs* with external *APIs*: querying real-time databases for fact verification.
- Multi-Modal Learning: utilizing images, sensor data, and text to achieve richer grounding.

6.4.4 Conclusions

This proposed future research directions represent a roadmap for advancing the state of the art in *DLT*, *MAS*, and *DAOs* integration. By addressing the challenges of real-time *DLT* deployment in swarm robotics and enhancing the integration of *DAOs* within decentralized decision-making frameworks, this research has the potential to unlock new applications and capabilities across a wide range of domains. Furthermore, exploring the synergies between these technologies and Neuro-Symbolic AI will pave the way for innovative solutions to complex, multidisciplinary problems, driving progress in both research and industry.

Bibliography

- [1] H. A. Abbass and R. A. Hunjet. Smart shepherding: Towards transparent artificial intelligence enabled human-swarm teams. *Shepherding UxVs for human-swarm teaming: An artificial intelligence approach to unmanned X vehicles*, pages 1–28, 2021.
- [2] I. Afanasyev, A. Kolotov, R. Rezin, K. Danilov, M. Mazzara, S. Chakraborty, A. Kashevnik, A. Chechulin, A. Kapitonov, V. Jotsov, et al. Towards blockchain-based multi-agent robotic systems: Analysis, classification and applications. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.07433*, 2019.
- [3] D. Alic. The role of data protection and cybersecurity regulations in artificial intelligence global governance: a comparative analysis of the european union, the united states, and china regulatory framework. *Search in*, 2021.
- [4] J. R. Anderson, D. Bothell, M. D. Byrne, S. Douglass, C. Lebiere, and Y. Qin. An integrated theory of the mind. *Psychological review*, 111(4):1036, 2004.
- [5] J. R. Anderson, M. Matessa, and C. Lebiere. Act-r: A theory of higher level cognition and its relation to visual attention. *Human-Computer Interaction*, 12(4):439–462, 1997.
- [6] R. Bal and I. S. Gill. Policy approaches to artificial intelligence based technologies in china, european union and the united states. 2020.
- [7] R. Behringer. The darpa grand challenge-autonomous ground vehicles in the desert. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 37(8):904–909, 2004.
- [8] R. J. Brachman. Ai more than the sum of its parts. *AI Magazine*, 27(4):19–19, 2006.
- [9] M. Bratman. Intention, plans, and practical reason, 1987.
- [10] L. Breiman. Random forests. *Machine learning*, 45:5–32, 2001.
- [11] A. G. Bromley. Charles babbage’s analytical engine, 1838. *Annals of the History of Computing*, 4(3):196–217, 1982.
- [12] B. G. Buchanan and E. A. Feigenbaum. Dendral and meta-dendral: Their applications dimension. In *Readings in artificial intelligence*, pages 313–322. Elsevier, 1981.
- [13] V. Buterin. Daos, dacs, das and more: An incomplete terminology guide. *Ethereum Blog*, 6:2014, 2014.
- [14] V. Buterin et al. Ethereum white paper. *GitHub repository*, 1:22–23, 2013.

- [15] D. Calvaresi, A. Dubovitskaya, J. P. Calbimonte, K. Taveter, and M. Schumacher. Multi-agent systems and blockchain: Results from a systematic literature review. In *Advances in Practical Applications of Agents, Multi-Agent Systems, and Complexity: The PAAMS Collection: 16th International Conference, PAAMS 2018, Toledo, Spain, June 20–22, 2018, Proceedings 16*, pages 110–126. Springer, 2018.
- [16] M. Campbell, A. J. Hoane Jr, and F.-h. Hsu. Deep blue. *Artificial intelligence*, 134(1-2):57–83, 2002.
- [17] A. Carare, M. Ciampoli, G. De Gasperis, and S. D. Facchini. Case study: The automation of an over the counter financial derivatives transaction using the corda blockchain. In *International congress on blockchain and applications*, pages 128–137. Springer, 2021.
- [18] J. Carlson. *Redis in Action*. Manning, 2013.
- [19] S. Ceri, G. Gottlob, L. Tanca, et al. What you always wanted to know about datalog(and never dared to ask). *IEEE transactions on knowledge and data engineering*, 1(1):146–166, 1989.
- [20] T. J. Chaffer, I. Charles von Goins, D. Cotlage, B. Okusanya, and J. Goldston. Decentralized governance of ai agents. 2024.
- [21] R. Chrisley. Embodied artificial intelligence. *Artificial intelligence*, 149(1):131–150, 2003.
- [22] G. Ciatto, M. I. Schumacher, A. Omicini, and D. Calvaresi. Agent-based explanations in ai: Towards an abstract framework. In *International workshop on explainable, transparent autonomous agents and multi-agent systems*, pages 3–20. Springer, 2020.
- [23] D. Ciregan, U. Meier, and J. Schmidhuber. Multi-column deep neural networks for image classification. In *2012 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 3642–3649. IEEE, 2012.
- [24] K. Clark and P. Robinson. Qulog: A flexibly typed logic based language with function and action rules. Technical report, Technical report, Imperial College London, 2003.
- [25] M. Colledanchise and P. Ögren. *Behavior trees in robotics and AI: An introduction*. CRC Press, 2018.
- [26] M. Colledanchise, R. Parasuraman, and P. Ögren. Learning of behavior trees for autonomous agents. *IEEE Transactions on Games*, 11(2):183–189, 2018.
- [27] A. Colmerauer. An introduction to prolog iii. *Communications of the ACM*, 33(7):69–90, 1990.
- [28] A. Colmerauer and P. Roussel. The birth of prolog. In *History of programming languages—II*, pages 331–367. 1996.
- [29] S. Costantini, G. De Gasperis, and G. Nazzicone. Dali for cognitive robotics: Principles and prototype implementation. In *Practical Aspects of Declarative Languages: 19th International Symposium, PADL 2017, Paris, France, January 16-17, 2017, Proceedings 19*, pages 152–162. Springer, 2017.

- [30] S. Costantini and A. Tocchio. The dali logic programming agent-oriented language. In *European workshop on logics in artificial intelligence*, pages 685–688. Springer, 2004.
- [31] G. De Gasperis, G. Della Penna, and S. D. Facchini. A microservices architecture for machine learning assisted decision support in a real-time field sensors environment. In *presentado en CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2021.
- [32] G. De Gasperis, D. Di Ottavio, and S. D. Facchini. Skrobot with teleor/qulog: A pseudo-realtime robotics data distribution service extended with production rules and reasoning.
- [33] G. De Gasperis, D. Di Ottavio, P. Migliarini, and S. Costantini. Skrobot: a pseudo-realtime multiplatform framework for robotics agents development. 2024.
- [34] G. De Gasperis and S. D. Facchini. A digital twin approach to building’s dossier for seismic prevention. In *International Conference on Practical Applications of Agents and Multi-Agent Systems*, pages 84–96. Springer, 2024.
- [35] G. De Gasperis, S. D. Facchini, and I. Letteri. Secured fiscal credit model: Multi-agent systems and decentralized autonomous organisations for tax credit’s tracking. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.01584*, 2023.
- [36] G. De Gasperis, S. D. Facchini, and I. Letteri. Leveraging multi-agent systems and decentralised autonomous organisations for tax credit tracking: A case study of the superbonus 110% in italy. *Applied Sciences*, 14(22):10622, 2024.
- [37] G. De Gasperis, S. D. Facchini, and I. Letteri. Leveraging multi-agent systems and decentralised autonomous organisations for tax credit tracking: A case study of the superbonus 110% in italy, September 2024 2024.
- [38] G. De Gasperis, S. D. Facchini, and M. Michilli. Distributed autonomous organizations as public services supplying platform. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.05189*, 2023.
- [39] G. De Gasperis, S. D. Facchini, and A. Susco. Decentralized autonomous organizations for tax credit’s tracking. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.10075*, 2022.
- [40] L. De Raedt, A. Kimmig, and H. Toivonen. Problog: A probabilistic prolog and its application in link discovery. In *IJCAI*, volume 7, pages 2462–2467. Hyderabad, 2007.
- [41] V. Dhillon, D. Metcalf, M. Hooper, V. Dhillon, D. Metcalf, and M. Hooper. The dao hacked. *blockchain enabled applications: Understand the blockchain Ecosystem and How to Make it work for you*, pages 67–78, 2017.
- [42] C. Di Ciccio. 1 blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. *The Role of Distributed Ledger Technology in Banking: From Theory to Practice*, page 11, 2023.
- [43] G. Diez-Valencia, T. Ohashi, P. Lanillos, and G. Cheng. Sensorimotor learning for artificial body perception. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.09792*, 2019.
- [44] M. Dikmen and C. M. Burns. Autonomous driving in the real world: Experiences with tesla autopilot and summon. In *Proceedings of the 8th international conference on automotive user interfaces and interactive vehicular applications*, pages 225–228, 2016.

- [45] R. B. L. Dixon. A principled governance for emerging ai regimes: lessons from china, the european union, and the united states. *AI and Ethics*, 3(3):793–810, 2023.
- [46] A. Dorri, S. S. Kanhere, and R. Jurdak. Multi-agent systems: A survey. *Ieee Access*, 6:28573–28593, 2018.
- [47] F. Doshi-Velez and B. Kim. Towards a rigorous science of interpretable machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.08608*, 2017.
- [48] H. Drucker, D. Wu, and V. N. Vapnik. Support vector machines for spam categorization. *IEEE Transactions on Neural networks*, 10(5):1048–1054, 1999.
- [49] M. R. Endsley. Toward a theory of situation awareness in dynamic systems. *Human factors*, 37(1):32–64, 1995.
- [50] S. D. Facchini. Decentralized autonomous organizations and multi-agent systems for artificial intelligence applications and data analysis. In *IJCAI*, pages 5851–5852, 2022.
- [51] S. D. Facchini. Xai-daos: Decentralised autonomous organisations with explainable intelligence. 2023.
- [52] L. M. Fagan, E. H. Shortliffe, and B. G. Buchanan. Computer-based medical decision making: from mycin to vm. *Automedica*, 3(2):97–108, 1980.
- [53] J. Fan, Z. Wang, Y. Xie, and Z. Yang. A theoretical analysis of deep q-learning. In *Learning for dynamics and control*, pages 486–489. PMLR, 2020.
- [54] Y. Faqir-Rhazoui, J. Arroyo, and S. Hassan. A comparative analysis of the platforms for decentralized autonomous organizations in the ethereum blockchain. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 12:1–20, 2021.
- [55] I. A. Filipova. Legal regulation of artificial intelligence: Experience of china. *Journal of Digital Technologies and Law*, 2(1):46–73, 2024.
- [56] L. Floridi. The ethics of artificial intelligence: Principles, challenges, and opportunities. 2023.
- [57] L. Floridi and J. Cows. A unified framework of five principles for ai in society. *Machine learning and the city: Applications in architecture and urban design*, pages 535–545, 2022.
- [58] Y. Freund and R. E. Schapire. A decision-theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting. In *European conference on computational learning theory*, pages 23–37. Springer, 1995.
- [59] D. Gambetta. Trust: Making and breaking cooperative relations. *Basic Blackwell*, 1988.
- [60] A. Gawesha, B. Hettige, and M. Goonatilleke. Implementation of autonomous robotic arm for nerenchi board game. 2022.
- [61] M. Gebser, B. Kaufmann, and T. Schaub. Conflict-driven answer set solving: From theory to practice. *Artificial Intelligence*, 187:52–89, 2012.

- [62] M. Gelfond and V. Lifschitz. The stable model semantics for logic programming. In *ICLP/SLP*, volume 88, pages 1070–1080. Cambridge, MA, 1988.
- [63] M. P. Georgeff and F. F. Ingrand. *Decision-making in an embedded reasoning system*. Australian Artificial Intelligence Institute, 1989.
- [64] C. A. Gomez-Uribe and N. Hunt. The netflix recommender system: Algorithms, business value, and innovation. *ACM Transactions on Management Information Systems (TMIS)*, 6(4):1–19, 2015.
- [65] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio. Generative adversarial nets. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 27, 2014.
- [66] M. Gorbunova, P. Masek, M. Komarov, and A. Ometov. Distributed ledger technology: State-of-the-art and current challenges. *Computer Science and Information Systems*, 19(1):65–85, 2022.
- [67] D. Gouaillier, V. Hugel, P. Blazevic, C. Kilner, J. Monceaux, P. Lafourcade, B. Marnier, J. Serre, and B. Maisonnier. Mechatronic design of nao humanoid. In *2009 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation*, pages 769–774. IEEE, 2009.
- [68] L. Gugerty. Newell and simon’s logic theorist: Historical background and impact on cognitive modeling. In *Proceedings of the human factors and ergonomics society annual meeting*, volume 50, pages 880–884. SAGE Publications Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA, 2006.
- [69] D. Gunning. Explainable artificial intelligence (xai). *Defense advanced research projects agency (DARPA), nd Web*, 2(2):1, 2017.
- [70] J. Haugeland. *Artificial intelligence: The very idea*. MIT press, 1989.
- [71] A. J. Hepworth, D. P. Baxter, A. Hussein, K. J. Yaxley, E. Debie, and H. A. Abbass. Human-swarm-teaming transparency and trust architecture. *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, 8(7):1281–1295, 2020.
- [72] E. Hildenbrandt, M. Saxena, N. Rodrigues, X. Zhu, P. Daian, D. Guth, B. Moore, D. Park, Y. Zhang, A. Stefanescu, et al. Kevm: A complete formal semantics of the ethereum virtual machine. In *2018 IEEE 31st Computer Security Foundations Symposium (CSF)*, pages 204–217. IEEE, 2018.
- [73] I. Horrocks, P. F. Patel-Schneider, H. Boley, S. Tabet, B. Groszof, M. Dean, et al. Swrl: A semantic web rule language combining owl and ruleml. *W3C Member submission*, 21(79):1–31, 2004.
- [74] J. Huysmans, B. Baesens, and J. Vanthienen. Iter: an algorithm for predictive regression rule extraction. In *Data Warehousing and Knowledge Discovery: 8th International Conference, DaWaK 2006, Krakow, Poland, September 4-8, 2006. Proceedings 8*, pages 270–279. Springer, 2006.

-
- [75] A. Jacovi, A. Marasović, T. Miller, and Y. Goldberg. Formalizing trust in artificial intelligence: Prerequisites, causes and goals of human trust in ai. In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency*, pages 624–635, 2021.
- [76] J. Jaffar and J.-L. Lassez. Constraint logic programming. In *Proceedings of the 14th ACM SIGACT-SIGPLAN symposium on Principles of programming languages*, pages 111–119, 1987.
- [77] M. Jakobsson and A. Juels. Proofs of work and bread pudding protocols. In *Secure Information Networks: Communications and Multimedia Security IFIP TC6/TC11 Joint Working Conference on Communications and Multimedia Security (CMS'99) September 20–21, 1999, Leuven, Belgium*, pages 258–272. Springer, 1999.
- [78] L. P. Kaelbling, M. L. Littman, and A. W. Moore. Reinforcement learning: A survey. *Journal of artificial intelligence research*, 4:237–285, 1996.
- [79] N. Kokhlikyan, V. Miglani, M. Martin, E. Wang, B. Alsallakh, J. Reynolds, A. Melnikov, N. Kliushkina, C. Araya, S. Yan, et al. Captum: A unified and generic model interpretability library for pytorch. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.07896*, 2020.
- [80] J. E. Laird, A. Newell, and P. S. Rosenbloom. Soar: An architecture for general intelligence. *Artificial intelligence*, 33(1):1–64, 1987.
- [81] D. Larimer. Transactions as proof-of-stake. *Nov-2013*, 909, 2013.
- [82] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton. Deep learning. *nature*, 521(7553):436–444, 2015.
- [83] D. B. Lenat. Cyc: A large-scale investment in knowledge infrastructure. *Communications of the ACM*, 38(11):33–38, 1995.
- [84] J. Li, R. Qin, and F.-Y. Wang. The future of management: Dao to smart organizations and intelligent operations. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, 53(6):3389–3399, 2022.
- [85] V. Lifschitz. *Answer set programming*, volume 3. Springer Heidelberg, 2019.
- [86] Z. C. Lipton. The mythos of model interpretability: In machine learning, the concept of interpretability is both important and slippery. *Queue*, 16(3):31–57, 2018.
- [87] L. Liu, S. Zhou, H. Huang, and Z. Zheng. From technology to society: An overview of blockchain-based dao. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 2:204–215, 2021.
- [88] D. W. Loveland. *Automated theorem proving: A logical basis*. Elsevier, 2016.
- [89] S. Lundberg. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.07874*, 2017.
- [90] S. M. Lundberg, G. Erion, H. Chen, A. DeGrave, J. M. Prutkin, B. Nair, R. Katz, J. Himmelfarb, N. Bansal, and S.-I. Lee. From local explanations to global understanding with explainable ai for trees. *Nature machine intelligence*, 2(1):56–67, 2020.

- [91] M. Lustenberger, F. Spsychiger, L. Küng, and P. Cuadra. Mastering daos: a practical guide-book for building and managing decentralized autonomous organizations. *Available at SSRN 5001424*, 2024.
- [92] H. Ma, L. Li, Y. Wu, and J. Wang. Bringing web 3.0 and dao into democratic class: A study of pedagogy in higher education. In *International Conference on Blockchain*, pages 21–37. Springer, 2023.
- [93] A. I. A. Mahmoud. Exploring the potential of daos: a comprehensive study of decentralized autonomous organizations. 2022.
- [94] R. Mayer. An integrative model of organizational trust. *Academy of Management Review*, 1995.
- [95] J. McCarthy, M. L. Minsky, N. Rochester, and C. E. Shannon. A proposal for the dartmouth summer research project on artificial intelligence, august 31, 1955. *AI magazine*, 27(4):12–12, 2006.
- [96] W. S. McCulloch and W. Pitts. A logical calculus of the ideas immanent in nervous activity. *The bulletin of mathematical biophysics*, 5:115–133, 1943.
- [97] A. McGovern, R. Lagerquist, D. J. Gagne, G. E. Jergensen, K. L. Elmore, C. R. Homeyer, and T. Smith. Making the black box more transparent: Understanding the physical implications of machine learning. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 100(11):2175–2199, 2019.
- [98] T. Miller. Explanation in artificial intelligence: Insights from the social sciences. *Artificial intelligence*, 267:1–38, 2019.
- [99] M. Minsky. A neural-analogue calculator based upon a probability model of reinforcement. *Harvard University Psychological Laboratories, Cambridge, Massachusetts*, page 7, 1952.
- [100] F. Morandín-Ahuerma. Montreal declaration for responsible ai: 10 principles and 59 recommendations. 2023.
- [101] F. Morandín-Ahuerma. Twenty-three asilomar principles for artificial intelligence and the future of life. 2023.
- [102] C. Moulin-Frier, T. Fischer, M. Petit, G. Pointeau, J.-Y. Puigbo, U. Pattacini, S. C. Low, D. Camilleri, P. Nguyen, M. Hoffmann, et al. Dac-h3: a proactive robot cognitive architecture to acquire and express knowledge about the world and the self. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and Developmental Systems*, 10(4):1005–1022, 2017.
- [103] S. Nakamoto. Bitcoin whitepaper. *URL: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>-(: 17.07. 2019)*, 9:15, 2008.
- [104] H. Naveed, A. U. Khan, S. Qiu, M. Saqib, S. Anwar, M. Usman, N. Akhtar, N. Barnes, and A. Mian. A comprehensive overview of large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.06435*, 2023.
- [105] A. Newell. Human problem solving. *Upper Saddle River/Prentive Hall*, 1972.

-
- [106] A. Newell and H. Simon. The logic theory machine—a complex information processing system. *IRE Transactions on information theory*, 2(3):61–79, 1956.
- [107] A. Newell and H. A. Simon. Gps, a program that simulates human thought. 1961.
- [108] N. Nilsson. Teleo-reactive programs for agent control. *Journal of artificial intelligence research*, 1:139–158, 1993.
- [109] G. M. O’Hare and N. R. Jennings. *Foundations of distributed artificial intelligence*, volume 9. John Wiley & Sons, 1996.
- [110] A. Peña-Calvin, J. Saldivar, J. Arroyo, and S. Hassan. A categorization of decentralized autonomous organizations: the case of the aragon platform. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, 2023.
- [111] F. C. Pereira and D. H. Warren. Definite clause grammars for language analysis—a survey of the formalism and a comparison with augmented transition networks. *Artificial intelligence*, 13(3):231–278, 1980.
- [112] F. Pesapane, D. A. Bracchi, J. F. Mulligan, A. Linnikov, O. Maslennikov, M. B. Lanzavecchia, P. Tantrige, A. Stasolla, P. Biondetti, P. F. Giuggioli, et al. Legal and regulatory framework for ai solutions in healthcare in eu, us, china, and russia: new scenarios after a pandemic. *Radiation*, 1(4):261–276, 2021.
- [113] A. Pokahr, L. Braubach, and W. Lamersdorf. Jadex: A bdi reasoning engine. *Multi-agent programming: Languages, platforms and applications*, pages 149–174, 2005.
- [114] D. L. Poole and A. K. Mackworth. *Artificial Intelligence: foundations of computational agents*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [115] M. L. Puterman. Markov decision processes. *Handbooks in operations research and management science*, 2:331–434, 1990.
- [116] M. Quigley, K. Conley, B. Gerkey, J. Faust, T. Foote, J. Leibs, R. Wheeler, A. Y. Ng, et al. Ros: an open-source robot operating system. In *ICRA workshop on open source software*, volume 3, page 5. Kobe, Japan, 2009.
- [117] R. Ramadoss. Blockchain technology: An overview. *IEEE Potentials*, 41(6):6–12, 2022.
- [118] A. S. Rao and M. P. Georgeff. Deliberation and its role in the formation of intentions. In *Uncertainty Proceedings 1991*, pages 300–307. Elsevier, 1991.
- [119] A. S. Rao, M. P. Georgeff, et al. Bdi agents: from theory to practice. In *Icmas*, volume 95, pages 312–319, 1995.
- [120] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, and C. Guestrin. Model-agnostic interpretability of machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.05386*, 2016.
- [121] H. Roberts, J. Cows, J. Morley, M. Taddeo, V. Wang, and L. Floridi. *The Chinese approach to artificial intelligence: an analysis of policy, ethics, and regulation*. Springer, 2021.

- [122] F. Rosenblatt. The perceptron: a probabilistic model for information storage and organization in the brain. *Psychological review*, 65(6):386, 1958.
- [123] F. Sabbatini, G. Ciatto, R. Calegari, A. Omicini, et al. On the design of psyke: a platform for symbolic knowledge extraction. In *CEUR WORKSHOP PROCEEDINGS*, volume 2963, pages 29–48. Sun SITE Central Europe, RWTH Aachen University, 2021.
- [124] F. Sabbatini, G. Ciatto, and A. Omicini. Gridex: an algorithm for knowledge extraction from black-box regressors. In *Explainable and Transparent AI and Multi-Agent Systems: Third International Workshop, EXTRAAMAS 2021, Virtual Event, May 3–7, 2021, Revised Selected Papers 3*, pages 18–38. Springer, 2021.
- [125] S. Salimpour, F. Keramat, J. P. Queralta, and T. Westerlund. Decentralized vision-based byzantine agent detection in multi-robot systems with iota smart contracts. In *International Symposium on Foundations and Practice of Security*, pages 322–337. Springer, 2022.
- [126] C. Santana and L. Albareda. Blockchain and the emergence of decentralized autonomous organizations (daos): An integrative model and research agenda. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 182:121806, 2022.
- [127] A. C. Scott, W. J. Clancey, R. Davis, and E. H. Shortliffe. Explanation capabilities of production-based consultation systems. *American Journal of Computational Linguistics*, pages 1–50, 1977.
- [128] S. C. Shapiro. Artificial intelligence (ai). In *Encyclopedia of Computer Science*, pages 89–93. 2003.
- [129] L. Shen, H. Tao, Y. Ni, Y. Wang, and V. Stojanovic. Improved yolov3 model with feature map cropping for multi-scale road object detection. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 34(4):045406, 2023.
- [130] E. H. Shortliffe and B. G. Buchanan. A model of inexact reasoning in medicine. *Mathematical biosciences*, 23(3-4):351–379, 1975.
- [131] K. Simonyan, A. Vedaldi, and A. Zisserman. Deep inside convolutional networks: Visualising image classification models and saliency maps. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6034*, 2013.
- [132] R. G. Smith. The contract net protocol: High-level communication and control in a distributed problem solver. *IEEE Transactions on computers*, 29(12):1104–1113, 1980.
- [133] J. R. Sublette. The dartmouth conference: Its reports and results. *College English*, 35(3):348–357, 1973.
- [134] M. Sundararajan, A. Taly, and Q. Yan. Axiomatic attribution for deep networks. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 3319–3328. PMLR, 2017.
- [135] V. Sze, Y.-H. Chen, T.-J. Yang, and J. S. Emer. Efficient processing of deep neural networks: A tutorial and survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 105(12):2295–2329, 2017.

- [136] B. Tang, Z. Pan, K. Yin, and A. Khateeb. Recent advances of deep learning in bioinformatics and computational biology. *Frontiers in genetics*, 10:214, 2019.
- [137] A. Tigadi, R. Gujanatti, A. Gonchi, and B. Klemsscet. Advanced driver assistance systems. *International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science*, 4(3):151–158, 2016.
- [138] R. Timofeev. Classification and regression trees (cart) theory and applications. *Humboldt University, Berlin*, 54:48, 2004.
- [139] M. N. Tunio and A. B. Memon. *Frugal Innovation and Social Transitions in the Digital Era*. IGI Global, 2022.
- [140] A. M. Turing. Mind. *Mind*, 59(236):433–460, 1950.
- [141] M.-C. Valiente Blázquez, S. Hassan, and J. Pavón Mestras. Evaluating the software frameworks for developing decentralized autonomous organizations. 2021.
- [142] S. Wachter, B. Mittelstadt, and C. Russell. Counterfactual explanations without opening the black box: Automated decisions and the gdpr. *Harv. JL & Tech.*, 31:841, 2017.
- [143] K. Wang, M. Liu, and Z. Ye. An advanced yolov3 method for small-scale road object detection. *Applied Soft Computing*, 112:107846, 2021.
- [144] P. Wang. On defining artificial intelligence. *Journal of Artificial General Intelligence*, 10(2):1–37, 2019.
- [145] T. Winograd. Understanding natural language. *Cognitive psychology*, 3(1):1–191, 1972.
- [146] M. Wooldridge. *An introduction to multiagent systems*. John wiley & sons, 2009.
- [147] Y. Xu, X. Liu, X. Cao, C. Huang, E. Liu, S. Qian, X. Liu, Y. Wu, F. Dong, C.-W. Qiu, et al. Artificial intelligence: A powerful paradigm for scientific research. *The Innovation*, 2(4), 2021.
- [148] A. Yakovenko. Solana: A new architecture for a high performance blockchain v0. 8.13. *Whitepaper*, 2018.
- [149] C.-K. Yeh, B. Kim, S. Arik, C.-L. Li, T. Pfister, and P. Ravikumar. On completeness-aware concept-based explanations in deep neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 33:20554–20565, 2020.
- [150] G. Yenduri, M. Ramalingam, G. C. Selvi, Y. Supriya, G. Srivastava, P. K. R. Maddikunta, G. D. Raj, R. H. Jhaveri, B. Prabadevi, W. Wang, et al. Gpt (generative pre-trained transformer)—a comprehensive review on enabling technologies, potential applications, emerging challenges, and future directions. *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [151] L. Zadeh and C. Desoer. *Linear system theory: the state space approach*. Courier Dover Publications, 2008.
- [152] L. A. Zadeh, G. J. Klir, and B. Yuan. *Fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, and fuzzy systems: selected papers*, volume 6. World scientific, 1996.

Appendix A

List of Publications

In this Section are listed the publications realized during the PhD Course undertaken at University of L'Aquila from December 2021 to December 2024. The list includes journal articles, conference papers and workshops proceedings.

A.0.1 Journals and International Conference Proceedings

1. De Gasperis, G., Della Penna, G., & Facchini, S. D. (2021). A Microservices Architecture for Machine Learning Assisted Decision Support in a Real-Time Field Sensors Environment. In: Heinrich R., Mirandola R., Weyns D., Weyns D. (eds) 15th European Conference on Software Architecture - Companion, ECSA-C 2021; Code 172547. CEUR Workshop Proceedings Volume 2978, 2021 [31] <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2978/saml-paper3.pdf>
2. Carare, A., Ciampoli, M., De Gasperis, G., & Facchini, S.D. (2022). Case Study: The Automation of an over the Counter Financial Derivatives Transaction Using the CORDA Blockchain. In: Prieto, J., Partida, A., Leitão, P., Pinto, A. (eds) Blockchain and Applications. BLOCKCHAIN 2021. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, vol 320. Springer, Cham. [17] https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86162-9_13
3. Facchini, S.D. (2022). Decentralized Autonomous Organizations and Multi-agent Systems for Artificial Intelligence Applications and Data Analysis. In: Proceedings of the Thirty-First International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence Doctoral Consortium. Pages 5851-5852. [50] <http://dx.doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2022/828>
4. Facchini, S.D. (2023). XAI-DAOs: Decentralised Autonomous Organisations with Explainable Intelligence. In: Doctoral Consortium of 22nd International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence [51] <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3670/paper86.pdf>
5. De Gasperis, G., & Facchini, S. D. (2023). MAS, DAO and DLT: a 3 Legs Architecture for Intelligent Services. In: 6th Distributed Ledger Technologies Workshop (DLT2024) [] https://dlt2024.di.unito.it/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/DLT2024_paper_68.pdf
6. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S.D. (2025). A Digital Twin Approach to Building's Dossier for Seismic Prevention. In: Mathieu, P., De la Prieta, F. (eds) Advances in Practical Applications of Agents, Multi-Agent Systems, and Digital Twins: The PAAMS Collection. PAAMS 2024.

- Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 15157. Springer, Cham. [34] https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70415-4_8
7. De Gasperis, G., De Masi, G., & Facchini, S. D. (2024). HST-4: An Accountability Extension to Human-Swarm Teaming Architecture. In publication on Springer's Frontiers of Artificial Intelligence, Ethics, and Multidisciplinary Applications, 2nd International Conference on Frontiers of AI, Ethics, and Multidisciplinary Applications (FAIEMA), Greece, 2024
 8. De Gasperis, G., Di Ottavio, D., & Facchini, S. D. (2024). SkRobot with TeleoR/QuLog: A Pseudo-Realtime Robotics Data Distribution Service Extended with Production Rules and Reasoning. In publication on Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Informatics in Control, Automation and Robotics - Volume 1, ISSN 2184-2809, pages 851-858. [32] <https://www.scitepress.org/Papers/2024/130149/130149.pdf>
 9. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S. D., & Letteri, I (2024). Leveraging Multi-Agent Systems and Decentralised Autonomous Organisations for Tax Credit Tracking: A Case Study of the Superbonus 110% in Italy. Applied Sciences, 14(22), 10622. [36] <https://doi.org/10.3390/app142210622>
 10. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S. D., & Letteri, I. (2024). Leveraging Multi-Agent Systems and Decentralised Autonomous Organisations for Tax Credit Tracking: A Case Study of the Superbonus 110% in Italy [Data set]. Zenodo. [37] <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13742335>

A.0.2 National Conferences and Pre Prints

1. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S.D., & Michilli, M. (2022). Distributed Autonomous Organizations as Public Services Supplying Platform. I-CiTies 2022 8th Annual Conference on ICT for Smart Cities & Communities [38] <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2312.05189>
2. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S.D., Susco, A. (2022). Decentralized Autonomous Organizations for Tax Credit's Tracking. [39] In: arXiv preprint <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2205.10075>
3. De Gasperis, G., Facchini, S. D., & Letteri, I. (2023). Secured Fiscal Credit Model: Multi-Agent Systems And Decentralized Autonomous Organisations For Tax Credit's Tracking. IN: arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.01584. [35] <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2311.01584.pdf>

Author Disclaimer

Declaration of Generative AI use: authors used occasionally online generative AI tools to improve the readability of the text; he reviewed and edited the content as needed, and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Acknowledgements

This thesis is the report of a three years adventure born after a crazy suggestion of my tutor, Prof. Giovanni De Gasperis. I must thank him both for the idea of embark in and for the invaluable guidance, support and suggestions given during this journey. Many people helped at various levels. My wife Emanuela, my parents and my in-laws gave a crucial encouragement and constant support during the whole period: at least now you wont hear anymore strange noises coming from the home office room at late night! It was also a pleasure to collaborate with several co-authors and other PhD Students from which I got many insights: Emmanuel Ajibola, Daniele Di Ottavio, Dr. Ivan Letteri, Dr. Patrizio Migliarini, Shahid Salim, Alessio Susco, and last but not least Prof. Giulia De Masi that also helped reviewing this thesis. A special thanks goes to Cip and Nix at BCC Studio and Valerio at Studio Berkana that helped with technical suggestion on various projects. My colleagues at SED SpA and Comune dell'Aquila also had to hear my groans for a while... I'm sorry but thankful of your patience. Finally many other friends gave a special suggestion and an encouragement, thanks to you all.

Sante Dino Facchini, L'Aquila - Italy, January 2025
